

**Factors Affecting the Adoption of Internet Banking:
A study in Khulna City, Bangladesh.**

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Abstract

Internet banking is gaining popularity worldwide due to its convenience for customers and for the banking industry. It offers an excellent opportunity to shift from time-consuming traditional branch banking to a cost-effective, time-saving banking experience. Additionally, it significantly impacts banks' profit maximisation, customer retention, and the country's overall economic growth. Most importantly, Internet banking is essential for banks to sustain themselves in the competitive banking industry through cost reduction, ensuring the highest customer satisfaction and providing excellent banking service. Despite being an ideal medium of providing and getting banking services, the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh is relatively slow compared to other countries. This adoption rate is much lower in rural areas. Different factors individually and collectively are affecting consumers' adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh. Therefore, this study emphasises identifying the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh.

This study has adopted a mixed methodological approach under a pragmatic research philosophy. A purposive sampling technique has been implemented to collect qualitative data through semi-structured interviews with senior bank employees from seven different banks in Bangladesh at lower to mid-senior levels due to their closeness with customers. Additionally, the researcher used a snowballing sampling technique to collect survey data. A total of two hundred survey responses were collected from the current and dormant Internet banking users from Khulna City, Bangladesh to conduct quantitative analysis. The qualitative data were analysed through thematic analysis, and quantitative data were analysed through descriptive analysis. Finally, triangulation facilitated the validation of data through cross-verification from qualitative and quantitative data sources that enhanced the validity and credibility of the findings.

This study highlights how different resisting factors negatively influence customers' decision to adopt Internet banking through the lens of Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT). This study finds that factors associated with culture and local perceptions such as “Complexity Due to Poor English Literacy, Lack of Digital Access and Digital Financial Literacy, Performance Risk, Technostress (Physical Risk), Cash Dependency, Lack of Customer Banker Relationship, Religious Belief, Bad Reputation of Banks” negatively affecting the adoption of Internet banking. Additionally, factors associated with service infrastructure, including “Slow Internet Speed and Cost, Segregation of Mobile Financial Service, Difficulties in Setting Up Bank Accounts, Inconvenient Banking Process, Poor Customer Service, and Economic Loss” are

acting as resistance factors to Internet banking adoption in Khulna City, Bangladesh. These robust findings of this research demonstrate a clear picture of Internet banking adoption barriers in Bangladesh. Therefore, the results of this study will assist customers, banks, and the government in implementing necessary actions to mitigate the problems and it will help to accelerate the process of making digital Bangladesh.

Despite illustrating a comprehensive understanding of the problems regarding the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh, this study is not free from limitations like any other research. This study is conducted on a single social field within a single country which hinders the findings from being transferable to other fields. Furthermore, travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic prevented the researcher from obtaining a larger sample size which would enrich the novelty of the research further.

However, these limitations haven't been found to undermine the contributions of this research and its significant contributions to the practice, policy, and research. In addition, it offers a clear and comprehensive understanding of the Internet banking adoption problems to governments, banks, and other financial institutions to mitigate the associated barriers and uplift the growth of Internet banking adoption. Therefore, this study will be an effective roadmap to develop appropriate strategies and formulate the right directions to attract existing and new customers under the umbrella of Internet banking services in Bangladesh.

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Key Words:

Adoption, Internet banking (IB), Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT), Technostress, Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT).

Key Definition:

Innovation Resistance Theory: Innovation resistance is a natural psychological perception in customers' minds when accommodating innovation.

Value Barrier: Value barriers represent the barriers arising from the inconsistency with the existing value system of customers in the perspective of the cost of the innovation and the amount of effort it requires to learn against its offered benefits and usefulness.

Risk Barrier: Risk barriers are associated with resistance arising from uncertainties that are natural characteristics of any innovation.

Use Barrier: Usage Barriers refer to the complexity of using innovation compared with the existing system due to the possible changes.

Traditional Barrier: The cultural change created by innovation is the first element of psychological resistance to adopting innovation that generates traditional barriers. Consumers resist innovation when it requires them to deviate from their existing Traditions. The resistance level depends on the deviation's merit.

Attitude: An individual positive or negative evolution of performing the behaviour.

Perceived Usefulness: The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance.

Perceived Ease of Use: The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort.

Technostress refers to the negative impacts on human behaviour, thoughts, attitudes or psychology caused by the human inability to adapt to new computer technology that including both computers and software as well as mobile phones in a healthy manner.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 The Context of this Study:

The presence of the Internet in our daily lives is crucial, along with the everyday use of mobile phones and personal computers, which has created both opportunities and challenges for the banking sector. The rapid development of the Internet and information technology has changed the banking sector significantly (Dootson, Beatson & Drenna, 2016). Internet banking is one of the most critical changes in the banking industry, also known as online banking or e-banking. Internet banking refers to using the Internet to conduct personal, retail, and corporate banking electronically, such as bank transfers, payments and settlement, corporate and household lending, and so on, via the bank's website/apps using a mobile phone and desktop computer. DeYoung, Lang, & Nolle (2007) described Internet banking as a manifestation of product and process-related innovation. Internet applications can make banking transactions much more effortless and increase the standards of banking services (Shih & Fang, 2006). To automate the millions of banking transactions, financial institutions have been using robust computer networking systems for a long time, but this facility has reached the general customers with limitations. However, once the customers are connected to the Internet banking system, they can get similar facilities to traditional banking. All banking transactions such as fund transfers, debit or credit card payments, bill payments, and many other services can be done via the Internet (Akhter *et al.*, 2012).

United American Bank offered the first known use of e-banking banking in 1980 through the deployment of home computer banking to consumers, where many customers paid a service charge of \$25-\$30 per month. With the development of technology and faster Internet speed, customers can perform their banking activities swiftly with lower fees than the traditional banking system from anywhere and anytime by using Internet banking (Sayar and Wolfe, 2007). Therefore, banks made themselves available on the World Wide Web (www) to get the full advantage of the Internet and survive in the highly competitive business environment (Mia, Rahman, and Uddin, 2007).

However, the success of financial organisations depends on the level of customer satisfaction achieved and how the institutions meet the customers' needs by collecting, processing, analysing, and disseminating information. By considering the significance of the information system in the banking industry, banks adopted the automated information processing technology earlier than the other industries (Cornelia & Georgiana, 2011; Ho and Mallick,

2010). Internet banking gives the advantages of mass customisation for banks that suit each user preference and developing a more effective and efficient marketing strategy to promote a new product on a large scale at a lower cost. It also helps establish quicker communication with customers to meet their needs (Nel, J. and Boshoff, C., 2021). There are many advantages banks are getting from Internet banking service customisation according to the users' preference, new product and service development, development of effective marketing strategies, and reaching customers at a lower cost. It also helps offer non-core products such as insurance and stock brokerage and rapidly responds to market evaluation (Pavithra, 2021).

The advantages of using Internet banking are not only limited to banks but also massive for general customers. It saves their valuable time, such as paying utility bills and other small daily transactions, which can be a hassle for many people. Accelerating of money cycle and enhancing business productivity, Internet banking saves both valuable time and cost to traditional banking. More importantly, Internet banking brings the highest level of convenience to banking activities. Customers can use banks' websites and apps on their desktop computers, laptops, and mobile phones anytime and anywhere. It is a self-serving banking process that allows customers to monitor their income, expenses, and savings by themselves. Customers can have the opportunity to pay their debts by setting automatic withdrawals from banks quickly. They can check their bank statements, account summaries, balances, and other financial documents.

However, being one of the cheapest mediums of delivering services and banking products, the ability to access financial information and perform financial transactions, banks from every corner of the world have been adopting Internet banking since its first introduction. It has been significantly noticeable in recent years that the Internet banking adoption rate has increased substantially in developing countries (Keskar and Panddey, 2018). The competitive advantage offered by the Internet for banks, such as cost reduction and improving customer satisfaction by meeting their needs, maximising the diffusion and development of Internet banking in recent years (Ortega, Martinez and Hoyos, 2007). Although this significant development of Internet banking is increasing in different countries with different speeds, the position of Bangladesh is far behind the line due to the poor adoption rate of Internet banking among the large population. In developed and developing countries, the Internet is the fastest-growing banking channel because of its advantages and compatibility, and Bangladesh is no exception in welcoming Internet banking (Jahan, Ali and Asheq, 2020). The Internet banking system in Bangladesh is similar to other countries where customers can access Internet banking services via the Internet. A secured user ID and a password are given to the customer to access their account. They can

do all the usual banking activities such as checking balances, making fund transfers, or any specific enquiries Internet anytime from anywhere at a low cost (Nahar, 2021). Internet banking gives customers an easy, quick, and new banking experience, which was missing in the conventional banking system. Contrary, every sector of business is now service-oriented, and whoever provides the best service compared to the others will go ahead because of having the most competitive advantage in business.

There are 56 scheduled banks and five non-scheduled banks in Bangladesh, and the higher competition forces them to provide the best services and develop their services to get and hold customers. Since the first introduction of Internet banking in Bangladesh in 2000, different banks have gradually integrated the Internet banking service into the banking industry. Standard Chartered Bank is the pioneer bank in Bangladesh that first introduced Internet banking services. However, many other banks such as SC Mobile Banking, EBL Sky Banking, City Touch, MTB Smart Banking, and BRAC Bank Mobile are popular among customers offering Internet banking facilities.

Additionally, the process of Internet banking adoption has also been accelerated by the government's initiative to make Bangladesh digitalised. The establishment of the National Payment Switch Bangladesh (NPSB) and Bangladesh Electronic Funds Transfer Network (BEFTN) is playing a crucial role in the swift development of Internet banking (Bangladesh Bank, 2022). According to the Financial Stability Reports, 55 out of 57 banks have set up Internet branches, and 41 banks fully provided Internet banking services till 2016 in Bangladesh. The growth of Internet banking in Bangladesh has been increasing significantly, ↑21.34% in 2016, and 6.39 million and 7.75 million banking transactions took place in 2015 and 2016, respectively (Bangladesh Bank). The number of mobile phone users and people's involvement in Internet-related activities has been increasing rapidly. This factor is working behind the growth of Internet banking transaction value, which had risen from TK. 34036 crore (2015) to Tk. 39661 crore (2016) (BanksBD.Org, 2022).

In the time of real-time transactions, Internet banking is crucial to adjust to rapid globalisation. The people of Bangladesh finally realised the advantages of having Internet banking, and this realisation has been maximised by COVID-19 . During COVID-19 , Internet penetration increased by 28.8% in January 2021. Therefore, the Internet users increased by more than 19%, 7.7 million users between 2020 and 2021. Along with the rise of Internet users, the number of Internet banking users is also increasing. As a result, at the beginning of 2020, Tk.6500 crore worth of transactions were conducted through Internet banking, but by the end of March 2021,

this amount has increased to Tk.10000 crore with 36 lakh Internet banking users in Bangladesh (Khatun, Mitra and Sarker, 2021).

Additionally, Bangladesh Bank had increased the interbank transaction limit. The limit for institutions is up to 10 lakhs, which also helped to boost the usage of Internet banking during this time. The volume of Internet banking transactions increased by 57.42 per cent, and a 31.08 per cent increase in Internet banking users year on year by the end of March 2021 in Bangladesh.

Despite significant growth in Internet banking services along with many benefits, many customers are not interested in Internet banking services through Internet banking (Cheng et al., 2008). To provide adequate Internet banking facilities and bring a large number of traditional banking users under the shadow of Internet banking, finding the barriers behind the adoption of Internet banking is essential. It is not only crucial from the banks' marketing strategy perspective but also significant from the customers' perspective and the way they conduct banking. Additionally, Internet banking and its growth mainly depend on factors such as government support, banks' initiatives, and customers' and users' adoption (Oruç & Tatar, 2017).

1.2 The Background of the Research Problem:

Internet banking has brought revolutionary changes in daily banking activities by offering fast, cost-efficient, and flexible services. However, despite providing many advantages over the traditional 'Brick and Mortar' banking system, many people in developed countries are sceptical about adopting Internet banking in their daily banking activities. This scepticism is also severe in developing countries like Bangladesh. This is due to concerns about banking security, lack of awareness of banking products and services and lack of initiative from banks and the government to change the situation. According to Shah Alam *et al.*, (2007), one of the significant issues in Bangladesh preventing the full-fledged use of Internet banking is the lack of service infrastructure. Also, the lack of initiatives from Bangladesh Bank, governments and policymakers prevents the rapid development and implementation of Internet banking in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is a land of 180 million people, and almost half of the population still does not have a bank account which contradicts the National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS). There are less than 10,000 bank branches in Bangladesh which is not sufficient to bring a large portion of the population especially disadvantaged and low-income groups, under the financial system.

On the other hand, the traditional brick-and-mortar banking system is backdated and expensive for banks to operate. Therefore, Internet banking is a perfect solution from a Bangladeshi perspective. But a challenging factor in this context is that Bangladeshi society is a cash-based society where people feel comfortable using cash in their daily financial activities, therefore, heavy dependency on the use of cash prevents the normalisation of Internet banking activities. However, this situation is changing slowly under the vision of making a digital Bangladesh by the present Bangladesh government and this could be much faster if the implementation of Internet banking is possible broadly. Positively, in recent years, Bangladesh has slowly approached becoming a cash-lite society due to the increasing use of debit/credit cards, mobile financial services, E-Commerce, and Internet banking but many issues collectively slowing down the process of broad implementation of Internet banking to become a cash light society. Therefore, it is essential to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking as it will significantly help Bangladesh to be a cash-lite society and will help to boost the economy of Bangladesh by reducing tax evasion and corruption and economic development (Asadullah and Chakravorty, 2019).

But this slow adoption of Internet banking is mainly noticeable in the big cities where most Internet banking users are educated and belong to the upper class of the society, which is a fraction of the total potential Internet banking users. Most of the potential users believe that Internet banking is not secure for their money. This belief becomes firm when banks only operate based on the Internet without having a branch banking system even though online banks use the same standard for data encryption, computer systems, and electronic protocols. Despite using other Internet services like food delivery services, riding services, or buying products from the Internet, people seem to be more cautious about adopting Internet banking. The reason could be social and cultural factors, local perception, lack of infrastructure, and overall lack of knowledge and information about banking.

Historically, for keeping money and valuable possessions as a safeguard against rainy days or financial crises, people have been relying upon their vaults or other places in their houses, which cause a massive amount of "Lazy Money". Additionally, people feel more comfortable visiting banks and talking to bankers directly rather than using Internet banking, as people think it is too difficult to use. They do not mind time-consuming travel to banks and waiting for service which is a common scenario in banks in Bangladesh.

However, this picture has drastically worsened by COVID-19 in Bangladesh, like many other developing countries in the Indian subcontinent. The first wave of COVID-19, followed by several lockdowns, brought life to a standstill in Bangladesh. Every sector has been disrupted

in Bangladesh, and the banking sector is one of the most affected. As most bank customers in Bangladesh prefer to use traditional banking, the closure of bank branches in the middle of the pandemic made bank customers realise the necessity and convenience of Internet banking (Hossain, 2020).

Therefore, this appears to be important for banks, governments, and policymakers to prioritise and focus on the adoption of Internet banking by mass general as well as protecting the banking sectors from the potential upcoming financial crisis followed by the COVID-19 pandemic. In short, understanding the factors or barriers preventing Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh is extremely crucial. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh.

1.3 Research Questions:

1. How do cultural factors and local perception impact the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh?
2. How does a lack of infrastructure impede the delivery of Internet banking services?

1.4 Rationale for Research:

The vision of being "Digital Bangladesh" of the Bangladesh government has led to rapid development in the IT sector for the digitalisation of every sector in Bangladesh in recent years. As the economy is the backbone of any country, the Digital Economy is the main foundation of making digital Bangladesh. Although the digital economy is an economy focused on digital computing technology, it is commonly viewed as a business-driven economy with an Internet-based market and heavy dependency on the World Wide Web (WWW). The digital economy is also called the modern economy, web economy, and Internet economy, one of the most critical factors of innovation and development that holds massive business potential (Zaman, 2019).

The role of banks is significant in the financial system within an economy. As almost every country's economy is suffering massive damage due to the COVID-19 pandemic, Bangladesh is not an exception with a large population. As a result, all government and non-government institutions apart from emergency services were forced to close to prevent COVID-19

transmission. Surprisingly, banks operating with limited services have had to remain open due to a combination of multiple factors, such as; many people keep their all money in the banks apart from daily pocket money, no history of long-term bank closure in Bangladesh, and most importantly, banks and customers are not used to with Digital banking.

Although many developed countries and their banking industries have been suffering from the same pandemic, banks quickly adapted to the situation as most customers use Internet banking. As a result, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was minimal on the customers' banking experience, and they could conduct their daily banking activities as usual.

Even though Internet banking offers convenience, flexibility, and various benefits, the COVID-19 pandemic has shown the importance and necessity of Internet banking over traditional banking worldwide, especially in developing countries like Bangladesh. On the contrary, banking industries and customers in Bangladesh have had a tough time during the pandemic and lockdown. This massive drawback is caused not only by the banks but also by customers. Both banks and customers are equally liable as 98 per cent of the transactions of the state-owned banks are not digital, and 99 per cent of the banking transactions in Bangladesh are branch-based. Additionally, because of the annual service charge, many customers are not interested in getting digital banking services such as Internet banking, debit cards, and so on. To overcome the limitations and mitigate the challenges and suffering of customers from traditional banking in Bangladesh, bringing all the customers under Internet banking is the best solution to face current and future challenges, business growth, and overall customer satisfaction.

Bill Gates (1997) said, "*People do not need banks; they need banking,*" emphasising the necessity of Internet banking. Nevertheless, being in the era of technological advancement, banks in Bangladesh have not yet been able to bring all their customers under the umbrella of Internet banking. But there are many countries, including the UK, Norway, and Denmark, where four out of five transactions are not cash. Similarly, only six per cent of total purchases in Norway are conducted in cash. At the end of 2017, China had 34% digital transactions. However, surprisingly, Bangladesh has only 6% digital transactions out of total trades (Bangladesh Bank, 2022).

Compared to the PC, Tablets, smart mobile phones are the most popular medium of Internet banking. At the end of 2019, the total number of mobile phone users was 16 crores, 55 lakh 72 thousand, and the total mobile Internet user was 9 crores, 36 lakh 81 thousand. Besides, the total number of bank deposit accounts was 10 crore 3 lakh 37 thousand, and the total number of loan accounts was 1 crore 6 lakh 55 thousand respectively at the end of 2019. According to

the publication "Economic Trends " by (Bangladesh Bank, 2020), the total number of debit cards- was 1 crore 86 lakhs 11 thousand and 681, credit cards- 15 lakhs 56 thousand and 448, prepaid cards – 4 lakhs 28 thousand and 910, and the total number of the customer using Internet banking service – 25 lakhs 16 thousand and 685.

Table 1.4: Banks Users in Bangladesh (Source: banksBD.org)

The above information explains the banking situation of Bangladesh and the massive gaps between the potential and present condition of Internet Banking. Notably, almost 90% of the population have mobile phones, and 50% of the people are using the Internet, which opens the opportunity of using Internet banking. However, by making the banks digital and developing Internet banking services will not bring the expected results unless customers are willing to adopt Internet banking over traditional banking. As we can see, only a fraction of customers are using Internet banking, and a large percentage of bank customers do not take the facility of Internet banking even though they have an Internet connection on their smartphones. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate and identify the factors preventing these customers from adopting Internet banking. This study has investigated the factors that affect the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City from customers' perspectives. The outcomes will help the banks understand factors preventing the adoption of Internet banking and help them to bring all the customers under the umbrella of Internet banking.

Additionally, if the Bangladesh government and banks make it mandatory following the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) suggestion to use banking channels or Internet banking, it will reduce the demand for paper money and pressure from Banks' cash counters. Implementing Internet banking will save BDT 450 Crore of Bangladesh Bank and BDT 9,000 crore yearly in cash dealing. On top of that, three thousand germs were found on the bank's notes, and following the current situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, this is one of the most important things that banks and governments must take seriously for the sake of public health.

This is only possible if banks can bring all the customers under their Internet banking system. Therefore, this study holds significant value to the development of banking industries, government policies, public health and safety, public interest, and finally, ensuring the overall quick, safe, and convenient banking experience for customers (Hossain, 2020).

Many studies on Internet banking discuss many variables that impact the adoption of Internet banking. However, comprehensive, robust, and extensive research on factors affecting the full-fledged adoption of Internet banking is still limited in Bangladesh. There are some small research efforts to identify the determinants of the use of Internet banking in Bangladesh but unable to provide clear answers to the problems. Therefore, there is a necessity for extensive and comprehensive research on the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh exist. Previous study attempts on mobile banking, which is a significant part of Internet banking, have been conducted to identify the customer's preferences in using mobile banking in Bangladesh (Siddik *et al.*, 2014; Rayan, 2014; Kass-Hanna, Lyons and Liu, 2021; Lee *et al.*, 2021).

Also, most of the Internet banking research and the development of theoretical perspective emerged from testing the questionnaires in quantitative analysis. Still, it is noticeable that a significant gap exists between the quantitative and qualitative approaches taken in Internet banking research. Most of the researchers have conducted their studies by using the theory of reasoned action (TRA), theory of planned behaviour (TPB), technology acceptance model (TAM), the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model to find out the factors affecting the adoption of the Internet banking using variables in quantitative methods. All that researches have been conducted focusing on the customers' acceptance factors of Internet banking but avoided the obstructing or resistance factors of Internet banking adoption even though one of the primary reasons for the innovation failure is the consumers' resistance towards innovation such as Internet banking. Innovation resistance is a natural psychological perception in customers' minds when accommodating innovation (Ram, 1987).

The greater the resistance, the slower the innovation adoption will be (Ram and Sheth, 1989). Therefore, it is ideal and practical to look at the resistance factor of the innovation rather than acceptance of the innovation's slow distribution at the early stage of the market, which in this case is Internet banking. Consumers' resistance to adopting a specific innovation is related to Innovation Resistance Theory (Gounaris and Koritos, 2008). As Internet banking is a service innovation, this present study is an excellent opportunity to reduce this empirical gap by conceptualising the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking within the context of Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) (Talwar, 2020).

Additionally, previous studies were mainly focused on the urban area of Bangladesh, especially in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh. However, the study findings cannot be generalised to the situation and populations outside of Dhaka. Therefore, it is believed that this study can demonstrate actual scenarios in other major cities, namely Khulna, to identify the factors affecting the people of Khulna to adopt Internet banking. The findings will be more generalisable to the broader perspective of Internet banking adoption, which will be able to contribute to the existing literature as the importance of Internet banking has been increasing rapidly not only in the banking sectors but also among customers in every part of Bangladesh. Nevertheless, the number of people having the benefits of Internet banking is limited. Therefore, researching to identify the reasons affecting the development and adoption of Internet banking will be fruitful research.

1.5 Research Aims and Objectives:

The study aims to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh and the lack of interest and engagement among customers to adopt Internet banking despite offering greater benefits than traditional branch banking. This study focuses on the cultural factors and local perceptions of bank users regarding Internet banking in south-west part of Bangladesh namely Khulna City due to the diversity among the local population. In addition, this research aims to explore the infrastructural position of banks in delivering the Internet banking service and to identify any associated barriers to providing clear, valuable information to the banking industry and enable them to restructure and develop the marketing strategy for the promotion of the banking services. Additionally, this study aims to identify the most crucial factors that hinder the uptake of Internet banking which will help the bank to increase the number of Internet banking users and boost their profit maximisation in Bangladesh. As this

study aims to identify the significant factor influencing the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city, Bangladesh, the following objectives will drive the achievement of the research aims:

Research Objectives:

1. To understand the current situation and practice concerning Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through in-depth analysis of existing literature review, current news articles and publications from banks.
2. To identify the factors hindering the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh through conducting a survey among customers in the Khulna region and conducting interviews with senior bank employees due to their in-depth knowledge regarding the issue.
3. To understand the demographic characteristics of current users of Internet banking by surveying the population. Survey results help to understand customers' behavioural traits towards Internet banking adoption based on their age, gender, profession, and disposable income.
4. To understand the banks' infrastructural position and its impact on the Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through the review of existing literature and interviewing senior bank employees. Additionally, survey responses from customers will assist in achieving this objective because they highlight the key issues regarding banking infrastructure problems as primarily customers are more likely to face the problems through service experience.
5. To understand the role of customer service in the uptake of Internet banking by analysing the customers' opinions through survey responses and banks' perspectives from the interview of the senior bank employees due to their closeness with the decision-making process.
6. To provide recommendations based on the findings of the research for the sustainable development of Internet banking in Bangladesh.

1.6 Contribution to Knowledge, Practice and Policy:

This thesis has contributed to knowledge incorporating Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) in the Bangladeshi context (*cultural factors & local perceptions, and infrastructural perspective*) to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh through the lens of Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT). There are much research has been conducted adopting the innovation resistance theory from different digital innovation perspectives (Lian et al., 2012; Lim et al., 2013); Laukkanen, 2016; Yu & Chantatub, 2016; Borraz-Mora et al., 2017; Gupta and Arora, 2017). However, based on the researcher's understanding, this research is the first conducted from a Bangladeshi perspective to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking through the lens of innovation resistance theory. The conceptual framework developed for this study provides a robust view of innovation resistance factors and how these factors affect the adoption of Internet banking. As the area of this research is continuously expanding, this research contributes to knowledge by providing an understanding of how different barriers/factors affect the adoption of Internet banking in a developing country perspective. Theoretically, this study complements other empirical studies. The findings of this research present some uniqueness and variances to other research and contribute to further knowledge.

This study has been conducted to determine the resistance factors of Internet banking adoption by customers. The finding of the research suggests that customers face complexity to use Internet banking because of their poor English literacy. Additionally, other cultural factors and perceptual factors such as lack of digital access, performance risk, stress and anxiety caused by new technology use, dependency on cash, their need for banker's assistance and religious beliefs affect them to adopt Internet banking. Also, other factors associated with Internet banking service infrastructure such as slow Internet speed and Internet cost, segregation of mobile financial service, difficulties in setting up bank accounts, inconvenient banking process, poor customer service, and financial loss are playing significant roles in restricting the Internet banking adoption rate in Khulna city, Bangladesh.

Additionally, this research offers a greater contribution to practice. For example, this study finds that people face complexity in using Internet banking due to their poor English literacy, especially the older generation. This finding of the research indicated that the existing banking interface not assisting some customers more specifically the older generation to operate the

Internet banking service freely and therefore, quick attention and rapid developments are needed to counter the language barriers. In addition to the language barriers, this study finds that a lack of digital literacy is also affecting the adoption, therefore, this study highlights the necessity of providing learning materials by banks to educate customers on how to conduct Internet banking by using their own digital devices. Additionally, this study presents the major issues of the adoption process such as limited access to digital devices and limited access to the Internet for a large number of people in rural areas and to solve these issues, banks need to address the issues promptly and take effective initiative to ensure that customer in rural side can have access to digital devices and Internet. Customers doubt on the effectiveness of the Internet banking indicated that further communication between customers and banks is required. Good communication increases awareness about the products and services and the findings of this research indicated that the existing process is not fruitful enough and a new approach is required. As a result, customers especially older and less educated people will find Internet banking less stressful while navigating through their digital devices. Slow Internet speeds indicated that existing infrastructure is not supporting enough and needs faster and more effective development. Existing Internet speed is slow but costly and banks are required to address these problems and offer solutions such as providing cheaper or free data connection to their customers. This study found that many mobile financial services are gaining popularity such as “bkash”, and “Nagod” but they are not fully integrated into the mainstream banking channels. This study highlights that people find these financial services useful and if banks can fully integrate these financial service mediums, adoption of Internet banking will gain rapid pace. This research also presents that existing banking apps and banking interfaces are required to be upgraded on a regular basis according to the customers’ needs. Furthermore, customer service found to be less helpful to the customers indicates effective training programs on how to offer greater customer service are required. Existing way of customer service is not helpful to most of the customers and turning them away from using Internet banking. Lastly, banking security is not well established and safeguarding against fraud is needed to remove customers’ uncertainty caused by negative banking incidents that are common in Bangladesh. Additionally, existing measures are not strong enough to provide higher degree of confidence towards Internet banking process and its full adoption.

This study also highlights the key areas of both customers' and banks' perspectives where supportive policy implementation is necessary. This study highlights the necessity of developing policies to safeguard customers' interests due to their financial loss. Additionally, this study reveals the necessity of financial assistance from the government for building a

strong Internet banking infrastructure and for supporting private-owned banks. Finally, the government needs to consider the fact before implementing new policies that blanket policy will not be equally effective for every bank. Rather implementing policy based on individual cases will boost banks' development and sustainable growth.

The findings and contributions of this research will be useful to the banks to identify the influential factors affecting the customers. It will also help banks to develop appropriate strategies and formulate the right directions to attract existing and new customers to Internet banking. This research paper is combined with different chapters and further details of the research contribution stated in the conclusion chapter.

1.7 Thesis Structure:

Chapter 1 – the introductory chapter provides the background of the research, both Internet banking in Bangladesh and International perspective, addresses the research questions, highlights the research objective, and the rationale for conducting this research.

Chapter 2 highlights the relevant theories and models in Internet banking literature, critically reviews the past research studies related to this research perspective and draws a conceptual framework for analysing the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh.

Chapter 3 discussed the adopted research philosophy (Pragmatism), research design (Mixed Methodology), and data collection process qualitative data – Interviews, quantitative data – Survey questioners.

Chapter 4 addressed the findings of qualitative analysis from interviews and quantitative data analysis from survey questionnaires.

Chapter 5 is constructed by the discussion of the results based on triangulation. Chapter 6 presented a summary of the thesis, conclusion, limitation, recommendation & scope for further research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.0 Introduction:

The previous chapter (*Chapter- 1: Introduction*) has introduced how research into Internet banking has increased in recent years, especially since the development of the Internet and the introduction of the latest technology that allows banks to offer their services and products via the Internet. Additionally, it has stated the main aim of this research to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh. The previous chapter also illustrated the research problem statement, aims and objectives, research questions and the rationale of the research highlighting the value and significance in the literature and practice as well as to banks, governments, and policymakers. In addition, this chapter also briefly reviews the most important discoveries in recent years, as well as current challenges, open questions, and fierce debates within the field of Internet banking adoption.

This present chapter is going to discuss the critical areas of Internet banking and Internet banking adoption around the world with a specific focus on Bangladesh, starting with conceptual clarification, describing different theoretical models of Internet banking and other influential factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the Internet banking literature. Lastly, the discussion of the conceptual framework of the research presented a comprehensive understanding of the adopted framework in this study.

2.1.0 Conceptual Clarification:

2.1.1 What is Internet banking (Service Innovation):

Internet banking allows its users to conduct their financial transactions through a secure bank website with a unique username and password provided by a retail bank, commercial bank, online bank, building society or credit union. Internet banking is familiar with many names such as Internet banking, virtual banking, electronic banking, and e-banking. Lou et al., (2010) define Internet banking as an innovative way of interacting with banks and conducting banking activities through Internet delivery channels but using electronic devices such as mobile phones, desktop computers, laptops, tablets/iPads, or personal digital assistants (PDA). This notion is also consistent with the definition of innovation in the Oslo Manual (OECD/Eurostat, 2005).

Despite having a standard traditional retail banking method, the latest Internet-based banking system has significantly changed personal banking services (Wang et al., 2003). Due to the rapid improvement of modern technologies, ATM banking, daily banking, debit cards, credit cards, and Internet banking have become the most effective delivery channels of banking, which are both used for business-to-business (B2B) and Business-to-customer (B2C) transactions. However, Internet banking has gained the most popularity over other banking delivery channels. As a result, Internet banking has become an essential part of business strategy in the competitive business environment. This aspect is vital in the banking industry as every company wants to hold a significant market share by providing the best customer service and banking products as it is easy to provide practical, rapid, and convenient banking services through Internet banking.

According to Shih and Fang (2004), Internet banking is a new type of information system that uses the Internet's advantage to provide the customer's banking service virtually. Such as opening a new banking account to conducting daily banking activities through bank websites where earlier banking websites were used for only providing banking information. Lymeropoulos and Chaniotakis (2004) described Internet banking as the provision of information or services by the banks to its customers, through a computer. It indicates a system where customers can access their accounts and other general information about the bank's products or services delivered by banks without the necessity of sending letters, original signatures, or any extra confirmation through phone (Safeena et al., 2010; Thulani, 2009).

Smith (2006) stated that customers could perform their daily banking activities from the comfort of their homes with the help of an Internet banking system. The Internet banking system allows users remote access to their accounts to conduct transactions and do shopping or purchases online (Littler and Melanthiou, 2006). Most banks worldwide use Internet banking not only as transactional but also as informational because of the latest developments in asynchronous and secure electronic transaction technologies. Therefore, Internet banking users can write cheques, transfer funds, pay bills, set up a fixed deposit, print statements, enquire about account balances, and purchase investment-related funds. Tan and Teo (2000) described that Internet banking has evolved into a one-stop service and information unit with many benefits for both banks and consumers. The operational structure of Internet banking and traditional banking are similar. Only the main difference is the way transactions are completed. For instance, instead of using paper to complete the transaction, customers use computers, smartphones, and tabs to access their accounts and information, reconcile statements and make payments. For the long-term survival of banks in E-Commerce, adapting and offering Internet

banking services is crucial (Tan and Teo, 2000). According to (Yee-Loong Chong, 2010), The growth of Internet banking is forecasted to increase rapidly in recent years, which will challenge traditional banks' competitive advantage with physical branches.

Last but not least, there is a difference between the Internet and electronic banking or E-banking, even though the term "E-banking" is commonly used to refer to Internet banking. Internet banking is part of e-banking, where e-banking refers to a broader aspect that includes Telephone banking, mobile banking, credit cards, ATMs, debit cards, and Internet banking.

2.1.2 History of Internet Banking:

The journey of Internet banking began in 1981 in New York with four significant banks, namely Chase Manhattan, Citi Bank, Chemical Bank and Manufacturers Hanover, who provided home banking access to their customers as a concerted effort to test innovative ways of doing business by providing remote service. In 1983, the Bank of Scotland was the first in the UK to offer an Internet banking service called "Homelink" to its customers, where people had to connect to the Internet through their telephone to transfer money and pay bills. The development of Internet banking started during this time. The Stanford Federal Credit Union was the first financial institution in 1994 to offer Internet banking services to all its customers. The advantages of Internet banking began to spread after following the footsteps of Wells Fargo, which became the first US bank to add account services to its website in 1995. Following Wells Fergos's approach, the same year, Presidential Bank became the first in the US to open a bank account over the Internet. It provided its customers with the facility to access the account online (Furst, Lang and Nolle, 2002). Over time, Internet banking gained popularity, and its evolution continued with the formation of one of the first successful Internet-only banks in 1996, which was closed later in 2007. In 1999, Bank of USA emerged as part of the incorporation of Bofi Holding Inc, making it America's oldest Internet bank. By this time, people fully understood the convenience and the benefit of Internet banking, such as gaining higher interest rates online than traditional banking, quick and easy account access, and Internet banking transfers. This popularity of Internet banking enabled Bank of America to make history by being the first bank with 3 million Internet banking customers, which was 20% of its total customers in 2001. The evolution of Internet banking gained a significant pace with e-commerce when the big banks started offering their online products and services. This led Internet banking to the mainstream as 80% of US banking were offering Internet banking services by 2006. According to the survey of Fiserv, a financial service technology company

in 2010 on consumers' billing and payments trends, the growth of Internet banking and mobile banking is higher than the growth of the Internet. This growth of Internet banking has been accelerating because of convenience and innovation offered by the banks, such as mobile banking apps, EMV-chip debit cards, Popmoney for money transfer via text or email and mobile check deposits. By the end of 2018, many banks operate only online, and Internet banking has become a common but essential part of daily banking activities for both customers and banks around the world as it allows banks to offer competitive interest rates on savings accounts by minimising overhead costs (Santouridis and Kyritsi, 2014).

2.1.3 Types of Internet Banking:

There are two forms of Internet banking: web-based banking, where customers can access their account via the Internet and dial-up banking, where they need to use a modem to connect to the bank's server through dial-up. Yibin (2003) stated the functional level of Internet banking in the market as informational, communicative/simple transactional and advanced transactional (Thulani, Tofara and Langton, 2009). Informational Internet banking is the primary level of Internet banking used for the promotional purposes of a bank's products and services through a standalone server. The second level of Internet banking is communicative transactional, where customers have the least amount of interaction with the banking system. This interaction is limited to account enquiry, credit update, email, or changing name or address. This type of e-banking does not allow fund transfers. Advanced transactional banking is the third level where customers can do their transactions online, such as transferring funds from and to their account electronically, paying their bills and other types of banking activities online.

2.1.4 E-banking System:

E-banking is classified into incumbent and direct banks (Xu and Zhao, 2000). The incumbent banking system combines the traditional banking system consisting of branches, call centres, ATMs and online services where Internet banking is an additional medium of banking services. In comparison, a direct bank is a virtual bank without branches providing banking services through the Internet, telecommunication, and wireless networks (Yang, Cheng and Luo, 2009).

2.1.5 Importance of Internet Banking:

The Internet banking system is cost-efficient compared to the traditional banking system as the operation cost is lower (Smith, 2006). As the physical labour is replaced by the computer

network in Internet banking, offering transactional services, 24/7 is easier with a lower cost. In contrast, the traditional way of providing services through the physical branch is expensive (WU, Hsia and Heng, 2006). Because of being inexpensive and allows banks to offer better and improved services, Internet banking is the best way to get higher customer acceptance and satisfaction, higher profitability, and more significant competitive advantages for banks (Li, 2021). A bank is one of the most used secured financial platforms that offer different financial services. Banks generally use encryption devices to protect customers' personal information and prevent data breaches. Unlike traditional banking, customers can experience vast opportunities by having Internet banking, such as accessing their bank account from the comfort of their home and performing daily banking activities. The ability to access from anywhere rather than being physically present at the bank branch for many transactions, safely, swiftly, and hassle-free banking can save time and money for all Internet banking users. All those facilities help customers in developing countries where financial transactions are risky as customers have to withdraw their money from banks to complete the financial transaction with a third party. As a result, there is always a risk of theft and other crimes that sometimes cost lives. With Internet banking, customers do not have to carry cash for financial transactions, ensuring maximum security. Internet banking provides a convenient banking experience fast but without extra cost associated with online transactions. All it needs is a few clicks of the electronic device. Not only is it easily accessible, but it's highly convenient as it eliminates the necessity to wait in long queues at the bank. Internet banking has become more convenient with the introduction of smartphones, making it easy for users to access, check balances and perform transactions. People in developing countries like Bangladesh have realised the benefit of having Internet banking in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic due to the countrywide lockdown. As a result, people without Internet banking could not visit the bank to conduct their financial transactions and faced severe inconvenience. Budgeting and managing accounts have become very easy through Internet banking and different budgeting applications that can monitor real-time expenses during purchases or estimate expenses or savings.

2.2.0 Status of Internet banking in Bangladesh:

Despite being common in developed countries, the development of Internet banking in some developing countries still is in the early stages (Sharma, Singh and Sharma, 2020). Especially countries like Bangladesh, which is in the early stage of building IT infrastructure but has seen noticeably significant development in IT infrastructure in the past few years to achieve the

target of making "Digital Bangladesh" taken by the present government of Bangladesh. To do so, one of the economic plans of the Bangladeshi government is the development of the service industry besides agricultural production. As banking is an integral part of the service industry, banks must adopt Internet banking and operate smooth and efficient banking services online. Even though Internet banking is still unfamiliar to many Bangladeshi users and is in the early stage of development, there is a massive market potential for banks (Digital Banking in Bangladesh, Current Status and Obstacles, 2023). According to the Bangladesh Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC) (2020) website, the country's total Internet users are now 90.05 million. Of the total users, 80.47 million are mobile phone Internet users, 570,000 are broadband Internet (ISP + PSTN) users, and 83,000 are WiMax users.

Bangladesh's financial system is consistent with formal, semi-formal, and informal sectors. Until the 1980s, the financial sector of Bangladesh was controlled by state-owned banks. Currently, Bangladesh's banking system consists of three state-owned specialised banks that mainly deal with development finance, six state-owned commercial banks, nine foreign commercial banks and 42 private commercial banks. Despite being introduced first in 1996, the inclusion of the Internet in the banking industry started in 2000. Since then, the Internet has gradually gained popularity among the banking industry and its customers. Standard Chartered Bank is the first commercial bank in Bangladesh to launch Internet banking (Ghosh Kumar Sagib and Barua Zapan, 2014). Following their footsteps, there are many banks providing Internet banking facilities, such as Citi Bank, Brac Bank, South-East Bank, HSBC, Eastern Bank Limited, AB Bank, Premier Bank etc. By the end of 2018, 41 banks provided Internet banking services (Bangladesh Bank, 2022). Regarding Internet banking coverage, 5059 branches of private commercial banks out of 5060 and 3687 branches of state-owned commercial banks provide Internet banking services (Sarker, Sarker, Podder and Robiul, 2020). The number of Internet banking transactions has increased in Bangladesh in the middle of COVID-19 as people have accepted Internet banking over branch banking. As a result, there was a 33.47 per cent year-on-year increase in the Internet banking transactions amount, which was BDT 8,093 crore, by the end of 2020. The growth of Internet banking started with the government's initiative to control the spread of the coronavirus. Also, many banks have taken the initiative to boost the use of Internet banking by offering app-based financial services, which resulted in a 41.88 per cent increase in the total number of Internet banking transactions which was 23.44 Lakh (Uddin, 2021).

However, the growth of Internet banking was consistent after the ease of lockdown restrictions by the government, as people enjoyed the benefit of having Internet banking. Also, the role of

the central bank is significant in this perspective. The central bank has introduced regulations to boost the digitalisation of banking services by increasing the limit of inter-banking fund transfers to Tk 5 lakh, which was previously 2 lakhs. The ceiling of the single transaction amount reached BDT1 lakh, which was 50,000 before, and the number of transactions per day increased by 50%, which was five transactions per day. Along with that, the central bank introduced an interoperable QR code named "Bangla QR" to boost cashless transactions across the country. Customers can pay for their goods and services using QR codes and mobile apps provided by banks and financial institutions (SunBD24, 2020).

2.2.1 Bangladesh Electronic Funds Transfer Network (BEFTN):

Bangladesh Bank deals with many money transfers for the customers of its participating banks through the Bangladesh Electronic Funds Transfer Network (BEFTN), a central clearing system with low cost and short settlement time. 28 ministries and govt. officers get their salary through BEFTN. Compared to 2015, average settled transactions increased by 11.2% (41,859) in 2016 (Financial Stability Report, 2016).

2.2.2 Real-Time Gross Settlement System (RTGS)

To make Internet banking more accessible and more convenient, Real-time Gross Settlement (RTGS) and Bangladesh Electronic Funds Transfer Network (BEFTN) are the most critical Platforms. Real-Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) was first introduced in 2015, which is a central processing and settlement facility system. Through the RTGS system, 222,550 transactions have been settled, a total value of BDT 11283.88 billion. Now 55 scheduled banks with 6111 branches are connected with the RTGS system, and BDT 100,000 or above settlement can be done instantly between participating banks. (Hassan, 2020).

2.3 Analysis of Theories in Internet Banking Literature:

With rapid globalisation and the improvement of modern technologies, new tools and technological services add up in our daily life cycle. Most companies, businesses and service institutions are introducing new technologies to provide smooth services to their customers. However, adopting technology is not easy, and very often, it appears to be a slow process as people do not want to change their habits and shift to a new process leaving their existing practice. Adopting new technology depends on numerous factors such as intention, different

demographic characteristics, and social and cultural factors. Additionally, cultural differences significantly influenced the adoption of Internet banking and its efficiency and effectiveness in different countries differently (Srite and Karhanna, 2006). Many socio-psychological theories and models such as Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), The Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Gefen et al., 2003), The Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991; Shih and Fang, 2004), and Technology Acceptance Model (Davis et al, 1989; Pikkarainen et al, 2004; Cheng et al, 2006) have been developed to address the behavioural aspect of technology acceptance.

2.3.1.0 Technology Acceptance Theories and Models:

There are many theories and models have been developed and utilized to gain a comprehensive understanding of issues relating to the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking around the world. Understanding the models and theories is crucial to selecting an effective model that helps to develop a suitable theory for the research. Hence, some of the most common research theories related to Internet banking adoption are illustrated below:

2.3.1.1 Innovation Diffusion Theory and Perceived Attributes of Innovation (PAI):

The innovation diffusion theory is the most appropriate theory developed by Rogers (1983) named Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) to address the innovation technology adoption and understand the adoption of technology (Del Gaudio *et al.*, 2020). The Innovation Diffusion Theory aims to explain the acceptance of diffusion of a new idea or product over time and how it has gained popularity and diffused in the social system (Owusu *et al.*, 2020). Rogers (2003, p.12) described innovation as *"An innovation is an idea, practice, or project that is perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption"* and technology as *"a technology is a design for instrumental action that reduces the uncertainty in the cause-effect relationships involved in achieving the desired outcome"* (p. 13). The technology consists of two elements one is hardware, and another one is software. Rogers describes hardware as a tool that embodies the technology in physical or material shape. On the other hand, the software is described as *"the information base for the tool"* (Rogers, 2003, p. 259).

Rogers stated the innovation-decision process is *"an information-seeking and information-processing activity, where an individual is motivated to reduce uncertainty about the*

advantages and disadvantages of an innovation" (Rogers, 2003, p. 172). He categorised the innovation-decision process into five steps: Knowledge, Persuasion, Decision, Implementation, and Confirmation (Lee and Kim, 2020; Rogers, Singhal and Quinlan, 2008, Pp. 17).

Figure 2.3.1.1: Innovation Diffusion Process. (Rogers, 1983)

1. **Knowledge:** The first step of the innovation-decision process is knowledge, where an individual first learns about the existence of the innovation and seeks basic information about the invention and its use. In this stage, individuals want to know what this innovation is? How and why does it work? This knowledge motivates individuals to adopt the innovation and seek additional information regarding the invention (Ho *et al.*, 2020).
2. **Persuasions:** in this step, individuals adopt favourable or unfavourable decisions toward the innovation. However, it does not directly or indirectly lead to the adoption or rejection of the technology (Sharma, Singh and Sharma, 2020).
3. **Decision:** Here, the individual decides whether to adopt or reject the innovation. Adoption refers to the "full use of an innovation as the best course of action available," and rejection indicates "not to adopt an innovation" (Rogers, 2003, p. 177). However, rejection may happen at any stage.
4. **Implementation:** Individuals arrive at this step but use the innovation and decide to adopt it. However, the uncertainty of the innovation may still be a significant concern, and the implementer might need technical assistance. Also, the reinvention of the innovation may

happen in the implementation stages. Confirmation is the final stage where individuals seek support for his/her decision. However, the decision might be reversed if the individual receives conflicting messages about the innovation. However, individuals usually avoid these conflict messages and look for supporting information. Therefore, attitude is crucial as it determines the adoption or discontinuation of the innovation at this stage (Shahin, 2006).

Rogers (1983) defined five attributes of innovation that impact the invention's rate of diffusion based on numerous surveys on innovation studies. Those five attributes are:

1. **Relative advantage:** *'the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes'* (Rogers, 1995, p. 212).
2. **Compatibility:** *'the dictate to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, experience and potential needs of adapters'* (Rogers, 1995, p. 224).
3. **Complexity:** *'the degree to which an innovation is perceived as difficult to understand to use'* (Rogers, 1995, p. 242).
4. **Trialability:** *'the degree to which an innovation may be experimented with on a limited basis'* (Rogers, 1995, p. 243).
5. **Observability:** *'the degree to which the result of an innovation is visible to others'* (Rogers, 1995, p. 244).

The innovation diffusion theory and the perceived attributes of innovation have been widely used in IT acceptance research as well as applied in many models, such as the technology acceptance model (TAM) (Chen et al., 2002). Past studies have identified Internet banking as an innovation perceived as easy to use and understand (Liao & Cheung, 2002; Cheng et al., 2006). Lin (2010) stated in her research, consistent with Rogers (1995), that the perception of users on innovation attributes such as compatibility, competence, integrity, ease of use and perceived relative advantage significantly influence their attitude. Moreover, this ultimately directs behavioural intention to adopt or continue using innovative financial services and information systems-related technologies (Jamshidi and Kazemi, 2019).

The application of innovation diffusion theory in the context of Internet banking suggested that the limited Internet banking adoption can be identified by the perception of customers regarding Internet banking services compared with the traditional banking environment. These

theories explain the usability of innovation diffusion theory in the context of innovative financial services like Internet banking (Tiong, 2020).

2.3.1.2 Criticisms of the IDT and PAI:

One of the criticisms of IDT is that despite providing a framework, it is challenging to conduct a single study within the IDT due to the breadth and depth of the theory. This is due to the descriptive nature of the IDT instead of being prescriptive, which explains why adoption occurs rather than how to facilitate the adoption (Straub, 2009).

Regarding perceived attributes of innovation, most researchers did not pay enough attention to the factors related to environmental uncertainties, such as perceived trust and perceived risk. Trust is a significant factor in a social and business relationship in the presence of risk factors such as Internet banking activities (McKnight & Chervany, 2001). Another weakness of PAI is that it is inadequate to provide a clear explanation and understanding regarding the IT utilisation-based task, such as the evolution of IT, its acceptance, use and performance. Therefore, it provides mixed results in IT evaluations (Yoon and Lim, 2020).

2.3.1.3 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA):

Figure 2.3.1.3: Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975)

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) is based on the notion that individuals are rational and use information systematically (Lishomwa and Phiri, 2020). The theory of reasoned action explains a person's behavioural intention as a motivational factor which stimulates a particular behaviour where the strength of the individual's intention determines the performance of the behaviour. Two influential factors, such as "Attitude towards behaviour (AB)" and "subjective norm (SN)" or (Social Influence), determine Behavioural Intention. The greater the intention to perform a behaviour, the greater the likelihood of performing the behaviour (Effendi et al., 2020).

Attitude towards behaviour is a functional factor of an individual's belief system consisting of certain characteristics and justification of those beliefs to act on the behaviour (Saleem et al., 2022). Fishbein and Ajzen, (1975, p.216) define attitude as 'an individual positive or negative evolution of performing the behaviour'. The assumptions TRA specifies that a person's attitudes toward a behaviour are determined by the salient belief of the individual regarding the consequence of performing that behaviour multiplied by the evaluation of the consequences (Gill, Ansari and Tufail, 2021). For example: in the case of Internet banking adoption, an individual believes that Internet banking is worthy of adoption and the evolution (positive or negative) of the consequences after adopting Internet banking, such as whether it is important for that individual or shall other people adopt it as well. If all those questions are positive, the individual will have a favourable attitude towards the behaviour (Kwanrudee Prachaseree, Ahmad and Normalisa Md Isa, 2021).

On the other hand, the subjective norm can be described as the notion or ideology of social groups about a specific group or individual's social boundaries to perform. Subjective norm

refers to an individual's social pressure to perform a behaviour (Gayan Nayanajith, K.A. Damunupola and Cherish Kay Pastor, 2020).

"An individual's subjective norm (SN) is determined by a multiplicative function of his or her normative beliefs, i.e., perceived expectations of specific referent individuals or groups, and his or her motivation to comply with these expectations" (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975, p. 302 quoted in Davis et al.,1989).

However, subjective norms are predicted by two factors, such as an individual's perception regarding the expectations of the significant others (Aji, Berakon and Riza, 2020). For example, what do the family and friends of that individual think about the behaviour, and will they adopt it as well? Secondly, the individual's motivation to comply with these perceived expectations, for example, will the individual be perceived as uninformed and backdated if they do not adopt Internet banking? Does the individual ever care what others think about the individual adopting behaviour? If the individual believes that he or she is expected to adopt Internet banking and the individual is motivated to comply, the individual will have a greater intention to adopt Internet banking (Akhter et al., 2022).

Fishbein further stated that not only the above factors influence behavioural intention but also some external factors such as personal traits, demographics and traditional virtue affect behavioural intention. Additionally, some other research suggested experience and past behaviour can be added to the model for portending the behaviour.

Sheppard et al. (1988) quoted Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) in their paper:

"a behavioural intention measure will predict the performance of any voluntary act unless intent changes prior to performance or unless the intention measure does not correspond to the behavioural criterion in terms of action, target, context, time-frame and/or specificity."

To predict consumer behaviour and intention, the Theory of Reasoned Action is instrumental. TRA model can predict comparatively straightforward behaviour such as under volitional control sufficiently as an intention to buy product or service options and the association of barriers is very limited. This concludes that the TRA model can be used to provide a legitimate prediction of consumers' intention to buy any product or service (Ramayah et al., 2009).

Limitation of TRA:

However, there is a limitation (*TRA is designed to cope with behaviours*) of the TRA model regarding the contrast between a behaviour intention and a goal intention. For example, it deals with the intention of consumers to buy a new car, but it does not deal with the results that come from behaviours such as being the owner of a new car. Furthermore, the model's effectiveness is limited when some actions' outcome requires skills and resources (Harb *et al.*, 2021; Sheppard *et al.*, 1988). However, TRA was originally designed to understand voting behaviour, a single instance activity. Therefore, the theory was criticised as the intention is not an ideal construct for predicting continuing or repeatable behaviour because these behaviours can pose significant challenges and barriers (Alshurafat *et al.*, 2021; Sheppard *et al.*, 1988). So, after ten years, these researchers extended this theory to a new theory named the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), which is an elaboration of the theory of reasoned action with the addition of perceived behavioural control. The details of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) are described below:

2.3.1.4 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB):

The theory of planned behaviour is one of the most influential theories to explain and predict behaviour, which has been used to predict a wide range of behaviours (Hassan, Iqbal and Iqbal, 2018). TPB is developed from TRA by incorporating an additional construct, perceived behavioural control. The third factor explains the intention-behaviour relationship in a situation where an individual has less substantial control over the target behaviour (Abdelghani Echchabi and Dhekra Azouzi, 2015). Therefore, TPB is developed to mitigate the lacking of the TRA model to address the problem where the individual has incomplete significant volitional control (Khasawneh and Irshaidat, 2017).

Figure 2.3.1.4 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Source:(Ajzen, 1991)

The construct of the "Attitude towards behaviour" and "Subjective norms" are identical to the TRA, which has been explained above. Therefore, only the third construct, "Perceived Behaviour control", is discussed here:

Perceived behavioural control refers to people's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour of interest (Ajzen, 1991). Perceived behavioural control is associated with control belief (resources and opportunities) which refers to an individual's belief about the presence of factors that may facilitate or hinder the performance of the behaviour (Aziz, Afaq and Bashir, 2018). Two constraining factors such as external and internal control divided the control belief. External control is associated with the environment, and internal control is connected to knowledge and self-efficiency (Aldammagh, Abdeljawad and Obaid, 2021). Perceived behavioural control involves an individual's perception of his/her ability to perform the behaviour, which means how well the person can perform the behaviour. Actual behaviour is directly influenced by behavioural intention and perceived behavioural control (Farah, 2017). Additionally, attitude towards behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural controls influence actual behaviour indirectly through the behavioural intention (Jouda *et al.*, 2020).

There are two rationales given by (Ajzen, 1991) to address the direct relationship between perceived behavioural control and actual behaviour (Amrutha Sasidharan and Santhi Venkatakrishnan, 2024). Firstly, with constant intention, the collective effort required to successfully implement the behaviour is likely to increase with the perceived behavioural control. For example, if two individuals intend to learn and use Internet banking, the individual who believes that he has the ability and confidence to successfully learn and use Internet banking is more likely to learn and use Internet banking than the person who doubts his/her abilities (Maryam *et al.*, 2021).

Limitation of TPB:

Despite having excellent predictive abilities, TPB has been criticised on several grounds over time. One of the criticisms is that many potentially explainable variances are left unaccounted for, and this unexplained variance can be addressed by including additional variables and moderator variables (Conner *et al.*, 2000). Secondly, precise situational correspondence is necessary to predict the behaviour accurately as TPB considers the temporal cognitive assumption between the behaviour and intention (Foxall,1997). In this situation, the model predicts the current behaviour rather than the future behaviour if the intention and behaviour are measured concurrently. Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) stated that it is very difficult to predict future behaviour because of the time interval between the intention and the actual behaviour. Over time, different unexpected factors or barriers may affect the relationship between the intention and the behaviour.

2.3.1.5 Technology Acceptance Models (TAM):

Although, many technology acceptance models were introduced before the development of mobile technology and the Internet, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one of them and it is widely used still now (Al-Rahmi *et al.*, 2019). Although TAM was initially developed by Davis *et al.*, (1989) to explain computer users' behaviour but this model is extremely relevant today many research studies have been conducted based on this model. Many recent researchers have adopted TAM in their studies due to its robustness and effectiveness despite its developments started before the digital age (Ly and Ly, 2022; Ghani *et al.*, 2022; Alnemer, 2022, Marakarkandy, Yajnik and Dasgupta, 2017).

Figure 2.3.1.5: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Source: Davis et al. (1989)

The technology acceptance model is an information system theory that explains the users' acceptance and usage of technology. The development of TAM by Davis is based on the theoretical grounding of the theory of reasoned action developed by (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The theory of reasoned action explains that beliefs influence attitude, and then attitude leads to intentions, ultimately influencing and guiding the behavioural aspect. TAM adopts this belief-attitude-intention behaviour relationship as an information technology acceptance model (Paul et al., 1999). Actual system use is the ultimate final stage; however, people use the technology. Behavioural intention to use the technology guides people to use the technology. Behavioural intention is influenced by the attitude which highlights the general perceptions of the technology. According to the TAM, when people are exposed to new technology, many factors shape their decisions regarding when and how they will use it. Two theoretical constructs, such as "perceived usefulness" and "perceived ease of use" used by TAM, are the fundamental determinants of system usage. Davis (1989) defined these constructs as follows: Perceived usefulness: *"the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance"*. If a system is considered with a higher degree of perceived usefulness, users' belief regarding the higher positive use-performance relationship will also be firmer (Davis, 1989, p.320).

Perceived Ease of Use: *"The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort"*. If an application appears to be easy to use compared to the others, then the users will be more likely to use it (Davis, 1989, p.320).

TAM has been used over the years as one of the most used frameworks of Internet banking research. It has been considered a robust, powerful, and effective model for predicting consumer acceptance (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

Limitation of TAM model:

Despite widespread use and popularity, TAM may not be universally applicable. The assertion of TAM explains that attitude determines behaviour that indicates the users have a choice in the acceptance of new technology. However, this may not be true in the case of a large group of users within the workplace where the particular technology is mandatory to use and is selected by the management and where users do not have control over choices (Sukkar and Hasan, 2005; (Rahi, Abd. Ghani and MI Alnaser, 2017). Also, TAM assumes that people plan their behaviour and are rational in their actions. This means that people evaluate technology's usefulness and ease of use when they develop an intention to use it and, therefore, actually use it. The problem is that people are not entirely rational in their decision-making or behaviour. So not everything people do is planned or has a reason (Marikyan and Papagiannidis, 2023). The theory does not account for this. For example: when the first iPhone came out, people started to camp in front of the Apple store in order to get a hold of that technology, but interestingly, none of these people or at least very few people, actually had a chance to trial the technology of that new iPhone before that. So, could not have known about the usefulness or ease of use of the iPhone, but clearly, all of them had an intention to buy and get one of the iPhones and use them. That cannot be called reasoned action based on an evaluation of the technology. Another criticism of TAM is that it does not consider external variables such as education and age, which can influence acceptance and willingness to use the technology (Ajibade, 2018; Zahid et al., 2013).

2.3.2.0 Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT):

Innovation resistance is customers' general feedback and instinctive response towards the innovation. An innovation may bring a more significant change in the daily life of consumers and may alter the regular daily habitual activities of consumers.

"Innovation resistance is the resistance offered by consumers to an innovation, either because it poses potential changes from a satisfactory status quo or because it conflicts with their belief structure"- Ram and Shith (1989, p. 2.)

Innovation resistance theory provides insight into consumers' resistance and resistance-oriented behaviour, and it has been widely used recently as an excellent theoretical framework to explain innovation resistance. Innovation resistance may have a significant role in determining the success or failure of the innovation as it introduces changes in individuals' lives and diverts their daily routines or habits in a new direction. However, the resistance to innovation varies at the time of adoption according to the nature of adopters (Ram & Sheth, 1989).

According to Rogers and Scott, (1997), adopters can be classified into five categories: Innovators, Early Adopters, Early Majority, Late Majority, and Laggards. Although rejection or resistance may happen at any stage of the adoption process, innovators do not show any resistance as they are the first to adopt the innovation. On the other hand, Laggards show a high level of resistance as they do not adopt the innovation and other categories show resistance over time according to their circumstances. Innovation resistance can be classified into two categories based on its degree: active resistance and passive resistance. Active resistance can be highlighted by functional barriers proposed by innovation resistance theory, which refers to the resistive behavioural traits of consumers that are generated from the nature of the innovation. Additionally, passive resistance can be described as the contradiction of the innovation between the customer's existing beliefs (Kaur et al., 2020).

The desire of the consumers to adopt and use the innovation can be restricted by different barriers, which can be grouped into two categories; 1) Functional barriers associated with the value of the innovation/ Product, usage patterns of the innovation/product, and associated risk with the usage of innovation arises from the perception of the customers regarding the significant changes brought by the innovation 2) Psychological barrier associated with perceived image of the innovation, traditions and norms of the customers that arise from the

conflict between innovation and customers preconceived beliefs (Ram and Sheth, 1989; Kaur et al., 2020).

According to the literature of Ram and Sheth (1989), the non-adoption of innovation has been explained through functional and psychological barriers. These barriers are displayed below:

Figure 2.3.2.0: Functional and Psychological Barriers to Innovation

Source: Ram and Sheth, 1989

2.4.0 Influential Factors of Internet Banking Adoption under IRT Theory:

Innovation Resistance theory is an appropriate framework due to its comprehensiveness in examining the factors affecting the users' adoption and resistance to Innovation (Ma and Lee, 2018). Existing theoretical frameworks, such as the Technology Acceptance Model, Innovation Diffusion Theory etc., do not focus on examining the user resistance to Innovation (Gupta and Arora, 2017). Innovation Resistance Theory appears to be the effective and robust framework among scholars to examine and explain the consumers' resistance towards innovation such as Internet banking (service innovation) in terms of different barriers such as usage, value, risk, tradition, and image. This study traced and reviewed previous literature on the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking and users' resistance to it. This review is structured in the light

of the IRT framework, which highlights different key resistance factors of Internet banking adoption under the heading of different barriers classification (Usage Barriers, Value Barriers, Risk Barriers, Traditional Barriers and Image Barriers) to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

2.4.1.0 Usage Barriers of Online Banking Adoption:

Usage Barriers refer to the complexity of using innovation compared with the existing system due to the possible changes. Usage barriers occur in a combination of one or multiple factors, such as the effort required to learn and use the new system and shifting existing routines and habits to the new one (Ram and Sheth, 1989; Arif, Aslam and Hwang, 2020). The following section will discuss the critical areas of usage barriers that have been highlighted in the past literature on Internet banking.

2.4.1.1 Complexity:

Access convenience is described as the perception of customers to use Internet banking where customers hold the notion that accessing the service should take minimum effort and time. Access convenience plays a significant part in overall online service convenience in online service delivery (Duarte et al., 2018). This is consistent with the findings of Jebarajakirthy and Shankar (2021) that access convenience significantly influences the mobile banking adoption decision in the Indian banking users' context. They also found that consumers tend to adopt mobile banking, perceiving that they can use the service 24/7 through just a few clicks using the service provider's platform. Additionally, quick access to the service anytime from anywhere, fast transactions, easy access to bank information, convenient evaluation of bank services and the ability to get customer service through the system if they face any issue. Lack of complexity provides customers with higher satisfaction and influence their inclination towards Internet banking adoption.

The lack of complexity or convenience (*Similar to "Perceived Ease of Use" of TAM by Davis, 1989*) of Internet banking is a crucial factor that has been highlighted numerous times in the Internet banking literature worldwide.

Davis (1989) defined the perceived ease of use as the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort. His findings further stated that potential users may find any new application or innovation, which, in this case, Internet banking, is useful,

although believing it is challenging to use simultaneously. The effort of using the application may suppress the performance benefits of usage. This factor highlighted in TAM by Davis (1989) as Perceived Ease of Use is a significant factor that affects the adoption or acceptance of information technology. As a result, if Internet banking is convenient enough, potential customers are more likely to adopt it, or existing customers will continue to use it. Safeena et al. (2012) stated that customers like to use the system if they find it easy to use as it meets their expectations. The performance benefits boost Internet banking adoption. On the other hand, consumers' need for an easy-to-use system attracts banks' attention to developing more user-friendly interfaces and upgrading the existing system to motivate their customers to accept new technologies (Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015).

This notion is also consistent with the findings of (Anouze, A.L.M and Alamro, A.S., 2020) that perceived ease of use significantly impacts the intention to use e-banking services by Jordanian customers. Their findings emphasise the necessity of a more effortless process to use Internet banking services provided by the banks as it uplifts the intention of the customers to use Internet banking services. The breeding ground of the problems is where electronic procedures are complicated with time-consuming financial processes that cause banks to be unable to provide smooth and easy-to-use e-banking services (Ramavhona and Mokwena, 2016). Therefore, it fails to make the customers feel comfortable with their use and daily access. This statement is consistent with Chong et al. (2012) that perceived "ease of use" is essential in Internet banking research. People are looking for technology that is easy to use, convenient, harmonious and fulfils their requirements.

But surprisingly, the perceived ease of use factor appears to be less significant to the Internet banking customers of Sri Lanka. Hettiarachchi (2013) found that the complexity of using Internet banking does not impact the decision to adopt Internet banking in Sri Lanka. The authors pointed out some of the critical factors in their research that the concept of Internet banking is not as complex as other technological concepts in Sri Lanka. Additionally, although most banks in Sri Lanka have adopted Internet banking recently, the idea of Internet banking has been familiar to Sri Lanka for decades. The researcher pointed out that the perceived complexity or convenience plays a significant role once the consumers start their hands-on trial or use of the technology. As a result, perceived ease of use or convenience may not play an essential role in consumers' adoption of Internet banking initial decisions (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). Before adoption, the familiarity of the Internet banking concept to the Sri Lankan customers proves that awareness of the Internet banking concept plays a significant role. This is highlighted in the findings of Siyal et al. (2019), consistent with George (2015) that perceived

ease of use has a significant relationship with consumer awareness in China. Understanding a new technology motivates consumers to investigate further the innovation, which ultimately leads to their intention to use the technology because the perceived ease of use intercedes customer awareness of the service regarding the intention to adopt Internet banking. According to Raza et al. (2017), customer awareness is linked to the perceived ease of use that influences the intention to embrace Internet banking. The author highlighted that the awareness should be increased by the banks through mass media and social network platforms, offering free training sessions for customers and keeping video tutorials on the banks' websites regarding how to use Internet banking its service. This process makes Internet banking convenient and easy to use. As a result, it creates a cost/benefit ratio for achievement-oriented people (Venkatesh and Morris, 2000).

Raza et al. (2017) also argued that consumers easily embrace Internet banking due to its nature of being user-friendly and the minimum basic skills required to use it. However, system compatibility significantly impacts the perceived ease of use. The author emphasised that the availability of more features is essential to enhance the compatibility of Internet banking as perceived ease of use influences the attitude of customers to adopt Internet banking, which requires the banks to make their Internet banking portal convenient and easy to use (Boateng *et al.*, 2016). If the system is interconnected with the online shopping portal such as m-shopping, m-ticketing and other e-commerce platforms, that will bring ease to the consumer's shopping experience and needs (Kaur and Malik, 2019). Banks should provide these additional features with high-speed data transfer and high bandwidth sites so that customers can perform their transactions smoothly without interruption. Additionally, the system of the banks needs to be upgraded with the latest technology to ensure high speed and quicker transactions. These things can be achieved through investment in research and development to improve the system's computability and enhance the customers' awareness (Martins, Oliveira and Popovič, 2014). Besides the customers' awareness and system compatibility, customers' feedback through daily interactions and periodic surveys are essential for Internet banking adoption (Toto et al., 2024). Consumers' recognition through their feedback of the development of the banking system leads to the higher adoption of Internet banking as it points out the necessity of the system being easy to use. Similarly, if the customers think that Internet banking can be learned quickly, it will drive their thinking that the usage of Internet banking is beneficial and adopt the Internet banking service overall (Mehrad and Mohammadi, 2016)

2.4.1.2 The Roles Infrastructure of Bank to Provide Internet Banking Services:

As critical infrastructure is mandatory for any country's economic growth, technology infrastructure (TI) is the backbone of financial industries like banks. IT at banks consists of several things such as software applications, hosting networks, data centres, ATM booths, customer service centres, all electronic devices and sophisticated tools for banking (Murinde, Rizopoulos and Zachariadis, 2022). Banks have been using IT for decades to store financial information in the mainframe. However, IT has become crucial for banks along with the development of networking, communication bandwidth and software products. With the Internet's appearance and the mobile revolution, IT has become essential to consumers' daily lives, especially in the banking industry.

Banks' infrastructure acts as a central nervous system that is a foundation for providing core services and higher quality to customers. Core service quality includes Internet banking service quality, smooth and accurate banking operation, responsive and friendly customer service, reliability, and accessibility of bank services (Borena and Negash, 2015). Assuring high-quality services differentiates banks' performance from its competitors and helps banks shift their traditional banking customers to easy-to-access Internet banking. It also assists in holding accurate, updated service information and features that boost customers' confidence and access convenience and increase banks' credibility (Toto et al., 2024).

However, due to the rapid improvement of the Internet infrastructure and remote access technology, more and more banking services have become decentralised from branch-based banks to the virtual world. As a result, the psychical interaction gap between customers and banking service providers is growing, forcing customers to deal with the new services virtually by themselves (Bauer and Hein, 2006). Therefore, uncertainty and fear affect customers coping with new and unfamiliar services.

Therefore, ensuring a smooth banking experience for their customers is crucial for building customers' trust and maximising banks' credibility (Fu and Mishra, 2021). Any weakness in IT causes massive crashes in banking apps, transfer rejection and delays that affect delivery core services, impact customers' confidence in bank services and question the banks' credibility, ultimately resulting in resistance towards adopting Internet banking. Blinder (2000) stated that one of the most important factors customers look at when dealing with commercial banks is credibility. Although banks' credibility is not easy to measure, it is believed to be a vital matter to customers. According to the findings of Schnieder (2012), good quality products with higher

consumer familiarity are comparatively easier to sell over the Internet because of the low-risk association of selling them. The author further stated that customers would adopt Internet banking services easily if they have a positive experience with the same bank during their physical interaction through traditional branch-based banking as it creates confidence and credibility among customers to adopt something new. On the contrary, those customers who have had negative experiences earlier in obtaining services in their interaction with their banks tend to hold themselves back from adopting new services provided by their banks due to their earlier negative experience and poor credibility (Firmansyah, Yasirandi and Utomo, 2022).

The robust infrastructure of Banks uplifts their credibility to the customers, which is mainly associated with customers' belief that banking transactions are safe, reliable, and convenient, which assures the highest confidentiality and security (Matarina et al., 2008). However, most banks have integrated banking services with their management information system to maximise operational precision and serve their customers without error. Poor or weakness in banking infrastructures hinder this effort causing banks to lose their trust and credibility among their customers (Alam, et. al, 2007).

Liao and Cheung, (2002) stated that operational precision through good service infrastructure is one of the essential factors in customers' decision-making process to adopt new services, especially where money and investment are involved. Belinda et al., (2021) researched 128 banking industries to investigate the impact of information technology and its diffusion, adoption and infrastructure. Their study suggested that implementing robust information technology in the banking industry boosts the bank's performance and profitability. The return on investment is far greater than the initial cost of implementation (Shirinova, 2022). This study also highlighted that although the consequence of the modernisation of information technology in the banking industry presents challenges such as staff downsizing and staff retention, it also opens new job opportunities for IT experts. Also, the technological development of banks to reduce costs and introduce innovation in banking, such as introducing new banking tools and developing new systems that allow banks to capture new customer segments (Tsindeliani *et al.*, 2021).

Failing to ensure the highest operation precision by integrating banking services into the banks' management information system ultimately fails to convince their customers to adopt Internet banking. It takes revolutionary technology with the certainty of more significant advantages to encourage people to shift from traditional habits to adopting new ones (Brand, 2020). Most people in developing countries like Jordan tend to have higher uncertainty avoidance and prefer to use existing services and practices. People prefer face-to-face interaction during

communication and like to see and touch the products before making a purchase decision (Alkailani, et. al, 2011). This preference is primarily noticeable in developing countries. Rawashdeh, (2015) stated that people have more trust in "seen" over "unseen or virtual", and banking over the Internet comes with a higher degree of uncertainty. Therefore, developing banking infrastructure by upgrading bank websites and user-friendly service channels with the latest software and apps and ensuring the highest quality of customer service will make it easier for banks to mitigate the challenges. Also, it will enhance banks' credibility and acceptability of Internet banking (Greta Benedetta Ferilli *et al.*, 2024).

2.4.1.3 Design Constraints of Banking Apps:

Due to pandemics, social distancing and evolving banking policies, many people are pushed towards the digitalisation of banking. As a result, mobile apps appeared to be the primary interface of Internet banking activities that connected banks and customers (Fadli, 2020). Mobile apps, which are software programs run on smartphones and tablets, are key distribution channels of Internet banking. Well-designed mobile banking app that provides all Internet banking features, increasing consumer interactions and customer engagement (Castillo-Villar and Castillo-Villar, 2022).

However, design constraints of banking apps are automatically inherited during the app's design. These design constraints, such as complexity, unsuitable devices, and discomfort, significantly affect the system quality. System quality refers to design features that are easy to use, quick and easy to navigate and have visual appeal. Kumar et al., (2018) stated that customers evaluate the visual aesthetics of mobile banking apps subjectively and holistically, which means consumers do not assess the design features of apps such as colour, graphics, and text as individual elements but rather as composite. The author also suggested that to maximise customer engagement and experience, complexity, coherence, and legibility should be considered holistically during the design of apps instead of focusing on individual key feature development of apps (Wisuwat Sunhem and Kitsuchart Pasupa, 2020).

Bhandari et al., (2017) found that originality and valance are the critical factors in consumers' evaluation of mobile applications to be more pragmatic and hedonic, respectively. Although valance was found to be insignificant in hedonic quality, it connects to practical values and provides a sense of usability to the app's design. Pragmatic qualities illustrate how consumers think about the functional value of the app (Zhou, 2013). This notion is supported by the study of Pal et al., (2021) that design constraints are less significant in terms of future use intention than the actual usage. Even though customers consider design constraints a significant usage

barrier to using Internet banking, eventually, they overcome barriers and adopt Internet banking if it appears necessary (Kala Kamdjoug *et al.*, 2021).

However, apart from the appearance of apps, other design constraints appear significant for adopting Internet banking apps. Cruz *Et al.*, (2010) found in their research that barriers related to an unsuitable device for bank apps are common in lower-income customers. Also, mobile devices that are not technically compatible or suitable with banks' apps and services are a common problem among lower-income consumers in Brazil (Mogaji *et al.*, 2021). However, the perceptions of the complexity level of using Internet banking apps depend on the customers' income level. This complexity level decreases along with the increase in the income level of customers (Souiden, Ladhari and Chaouali, 2020). The authors further suggested that the problem of having unsuitable mobile devices could open new commercial opportunities for banks as banks could sell app-suitable mobile devices to their customers directly to standardise banking services and maximise Internet banking adoption (Nawaz, Motiwalla and Deokar, 2018).

2.4.1.4 Compatibility, Digital and Financial Literacy of Customers:

Compatibility is an essential element that connects innovation to its potential users. The adoption of innovation depends on the compatibility of their customers' existing value, present needs and previous experience that is aligned with the Innovation (Rogers, 2003). Innovation should meet the potential adapters' necessity and the value system that assists them in completing their purpose efficiently and successfully (Yoon and Lim, 2020).

Internet compatibility is a significant factor in adopting Internet banking as potential Internet banking users are expected to be confident in using the Internet in their daily lives. As the Internet is the delivery channel of banking services, customers with Internet literacy are more likely to be able to use Internet banking because of their previous experience (George, 2015). Customers who have experience in using computers and have a strong comprehension of the English language are more likely to be compatible with Internet services. Most of the online services have English interfaces that are mainly designed to focus on Western customers. As a result, language appears to be a great resistant factor to Internet banking adoption (Perera, 2018). As a result, the language barrier is a significant obstacle factor for people whose first language is not English or whose English language comprehension is poor. Ghaith, Sanzogni and Sandhu, (2010) conducted their research in Saudi Arabia, where most people speak Arabic,

but all the software and Internet applications are developed in English. As a result, people not compatible with the English language have difficulties using Internet banking in daily life.

Musa et al., (2015) highlighted the study of Shahin (2006) and stated that despite requiring Internet banking services, customers with a lack of information technology compatibility might find it challenging to use IT-related services. The author suggested that this factor should be addressed as a perceived challenge faced by potential users to increase the adoption rate. The author added that designers should give priority during the design of service technology, and it should maintain the goals and objectives of the banks and should not completely change the customers' existing values and previous habits (Mohd Thas Thaker et al., 2021).

Farida, Soesatyo and Aji, (2021) stated that a minimum level of digital literacy is required for Internet banking, which means the ability to access and use mobile phones, computers and the Internet is required to operate digital financial services. People with advanced levels of digital literacy tend to have more confidence in using digital financial services and, ultimately, frequently use the services (Andreou and Anyfantaki, 2020). A study conducted in seven developing countries in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa, where they found a significant relationship between digital literacy and resilience-building financial behaviour (Lyons *et al.*, 2019). This study also concluded that digital literacy associated with financial literacy uplifts the rate of financial inclusion among poor and women living in rural areas. Despite having variance in the effectiveness across the population, financial behaviour and geographical location, both digital literacy and financial literacy were found to have potential in resilience-building financial behaviour. Also, in some cases, digital literacy is more effective than financial literacy (Kelikume, 2021).

The digital literacy support programme introduced by the European Union and Spain is an effective way to boost universal Internet access for the population (Vasilescu *et al.*, 2020). Not only do many universities run programs like 'University Programmes for Seniors (UPS)' to increase Internet literacy among older people through classes, but also different community centres run different active aid programs, namely 'Centres of Public Access to Internet (CPAI)' to increase Internet literacy among the population (Chen et al., 2005). However, the finding of Tirado et al., (2018) suggests that University programmes for seniors in Spain can offer better assistance to maximise Internet literacy through a robust and systematic approach to the programme. On the contrary, the 'Centre of Public Access to Internet' was found to be less effective due to a poor systematic approach to the programme.

Therefore, raising public awareness through different training programmes can boost digital and financial literacy. Morgan et al., (2019) conducted their research in Lao People's Democratic Republic (PDR) to examine the relationship between financial literacy and awareness and adoption of financial technologies such as financial products provided through the Internet and mobile-based platforms. Their study concludes a significant positive relationship between financial literacy and lower adoption of financial products. Their study highlighted that a low level of financial literacy is associated with lower awareness about financial technologies and their adoption and with the country's underdeveloped Information technology infrastructure (Safari, Bisimwa and Buzera Armel, 2020).

In Bangladeshi perspective, recently, many public services have become digitalised, and digital literacy is crucial to meet the objective of providing efficient and transparent services to Bangladeshi people (Islam and Inan, 2021). BRAC Institute of Governance and Development (BIGD) has conducted countrywide research to understand the digital literacy rate of Bangladeshi people. According to the research findings, more than half of the population of rural areas has no familiarity with the Internet, where 75% of surveyed households have no access to digital devices and 77% of rural households have low digital skills (Digital Literacy in Rural Bangladesh: Survey 2019). Their study concluded that the digital literacy rate in rural area in Bangladesh is significantly low, and most of the families in rural areas are not ready to enter the digital age when Bangladesh is the fastest-growing economy in South Asia with rapid digitalisation (Jahan et al., 2020).

2.4.1.5 Customer Services and Customer Satisfaction:

Broderick et al., (2002) conducted their research in the UK to identify the role of customer service on Internet banking service quality. Their findings suggested that negative issues in service encounters and cues in service settings have a more significant impact on the evolution of service quality than the traditional elements such as responsiveness, reliability, and assurance (Nghah, ABD.Ghani and Rahi, 2020). Their research also highlighted that the service provider's lack of assistance and empathy and poor interactivity within the service settings promote switching and negative word of mouth. Rahi et al., (2017) surveyed 500 Pakistani Internet banking users in major cities and found that Internet banking is a key service delivery channel to hold customers' loyalty towards the bank. And e-customer service is crucial to

maintain customer loyalty as the relationship between online customer service and Internet banking adoption is significant which helps to attract more customers and maximise Internet banking adoption. Raza et al., (2020) concluded that e-customer service is a key factor in creating new marketing opportunities. It influences customers' behavioural intention towards adopting Internet banking as customers demand quick and efficient transactions along with personal attention towards their queries and problems (Arifin et al. 2021). The study suggests that Pakistani banks should provide consistent, fast, and efficient e-customer service to retain brand loyalty and to create a strong positive image of banks in the customers' minds that will ultimately enhance Internet banking adoption in Pakistan (Ghani et al., 2017).

Sarbabidya et al., (2020) researched the role of chatbots in Internet banking customer service in Bangladeshi. The use of robots in live chat service is a standard customer service strategy adopted by many organisations because of its ability to provide one-to-one customer service as well as the ability to provide customised product information 24/7. According to their findings, the use of chatbots not only offers various services to customers but also assists employees in possessing banking procedures faster (Alt, Vizeli and Săplăcan, 2021). Their study also found that using chatbots helped the bank retain customer loyalty and strengthened customer-bank relationships. As it helped banks provide the latest information regarding services and charges and respond to customer queries conveniently and efficiently in a friendly, customised, and cost-efficient manner (Hwang and Kim, 2021).

However, according to the findings of Hwang et al., (2021), the introduction of chatbots in banks' customer service according to the product and age classification maximises the banks' profit. The author also suggested that the financial industry is rapidly introducing AI platforms. It is essential to consider that introducing new technologies in banking services requires consumers' acceptance and adoption, which is a time-consuming and public relation-building process. It ultimately may result in internal conflict and loss of short-term profit and economic opportunities if banks fail to implement suitable investments at the right time (Mulyono and Sfenrianto, 2022).

2.4.2.0 Value Barrier of Online Banking Adoption:

The value barrier is the second functional barrier of an innovation that depends on the associated value of that innovation. According to Sheth (1989), if any innovation is unable to provide greater performance-to-price value compared to its substitute available in the market, then the customer will not have any incentive to change and adopt innovation (e.g.: ATM has overcome the value barriers by not charging for usages). Value barriers represent the barriers arising from the inconsistency with the existing value system of customers in the perspective of the cost of the innovation and the amount of effort it requires to learn against its offered benefits and usefulness (Arif, Aslam and Hwang, 2020). Consumers' perceived value is associated with customer satisfaction, increased customer loyalty, positive word-of-mouth, customer retention, a strong position in the market and a higher market share (Morar, 2013).

2.4.2.1 Usefulness:

Usefulness is an essential element in the evolution of the associated value of innovation. Perceived usefulness is a significant and positive variable that shapes consumers' attitudes toward Internet banking facilities (Chen and Aklikokou, 2019). It is a degree of belief where customers perceive that acquiring innovation will increase his/her functional performance (Devis, 1993). Perceived usefulness represents customers' belief that using Internet banking in their daily financial transactions will help to meet their financial needs and provide satisfaction in their economic activities.

Perceived usefulness is a good reflection of the value barrier, which is one of the main barriers to adopting technologies. Consumers who resisted embracing the innovation often found no value in using it, or it did not offer sufficient utility (Kanchanatane, Suwanno, and Jaremvongrayab, 2014). It is more challenging to adopt an innovation willingly in new banking channels if a customer believes that the innovation provides limited usefulness for his/her needs (Morar, 2013; Laukkanen, 2016). Additionally, the usefulness is an important variable of the TAM model, which is one of the most used and important references in the analysis of Internet banking adoption. Therefore, usefulness significantly impacts value barriers to explaining customers' intention to use and the resistance factor of Internet banking adoption (Borraz-Mora, 2017).

Perceived usefulness shapes the attitude of customers toward Internet banking adoption. The customer's attitude will be more positive if they perceive Internet banking as an easy-to-use

tool and valuable. Therefore, customers' intention to adopt Internet banking depends on its usefulness. Customers anchor their interest in Internet banking, considering all the beneficial outcomes of its uses and its easy-to-use facilities (Mufarih , Jayadi, and Sugandi, 2020). This notion is highlighted by Vietnamese customers of Internet banking, where customers tend to be more willing to adopt Internet banking once they perceive that it offers a higher level of usefulness (Lin et al., 2014).

Therefore, if the perceived advantage or usefulness of Internet banking is more significant than Traditional banking, customers will be more likely to adopt Internet banking. Such as, customer can track their transactions or the movement of their income/expenses whenever they want (Brown et al., 2003). This notion is supported by the findings of (Wu and Wang, 2005). Their finding suggests that the relative advantages of mobile banking technologies made the banking experience of customers in South Africa more accessible. Quick access to bank accounts, affordable pricing of smartphones, the availability of mobile services in local languages and the service infrastructure's reliability are playing a significant role in the maximisation of Internet banking adoption (Sudarsono, Nugrohowati, and Tumewang, 2020).

However, the perceived usefulness of innovation is based on the individual direct personal assessment of the technology rather than the subjective norms once they have started using it initially. However, if Internet banking offers a positive result or effects beneficial for the users, Potential users will be more inclined to adopt Internet banking (Tahar, a. et al. (2020). However, potential users may not be closely associated with Internet banking. Therefore, it will be hard for them to understand the positive or negative results. Therefore, demonstration of perceived usefulness is essential (Chan and Lue, 2004). Adopting technological innovation requires substantial learning efforts, information, and guidance from service providers. Banks must make customers aware of the available banking technologies and how technological innovation can add value to their banking experience. Information and advice provided by the banks significantly decrease the value barrier and assist in uplifting the positive image associated with Internet banking (Lukkanen and Kiviniemi, 2010).

Sinkkonen, and Lukkanen (2009) stated that either the non-users and dormant Internet banking users have yet to identify the true benefits of Internet banking or banks have failed to demonstrate to them its usefulness. Their study suggested two strategic options, e.g., "Pull" and "Push", to maximise Internet banking adoption (LU and Wung, 2021). The pull option allows banks to increase their number of customers through intensive marketing by illustrating the benefits of Service innovation to the customers. On the contrary, the push option makes

customers pay service fees for traditional branch banking, ultimately pushing them to use Internet banking (Fan, L. *et al.* 2021). This kind of strategy is found in Finland, where banks increase their service charge to make customers use alternative self-service banking channels Hundal and Zinakova, 2021; Hati, Gayatri and Indraswari, (2020).

Usefulness is vital for encouraging Internet banking adoption that is closely connected with push strategy by Internet banks and indirect persuasion that covers pull strategy. Raising public awareness regarding the usefulness of Internet banking is crucial in the early stages of adoption, especially in developing countries (Lisana, 2022). Using all media advertisement options such as brochures, leaflets, and web pages is effective in demonstrating the benefits of Internet banking to wider audiences and helping to educate potential customers. Information from bank assistants at the branches and bank tellers is essential to capture potential adopters. Provided information should include key phrases such as "Convenience at any time anywhere", "Low costs", "Timesaving", and "Information availability" (Loh et al, 2020).

Although people know that Internet banking provides greater convenience, time and cost-saving opportunities, people still are reluctant and slow to adopt Internet banking (Yoon and Lim, 2021). So apart from that, banks should let the customers gain substantial benefits such as providing them cash rebates during subscription, points reward per transaction, instant financial consultation, and other value-added services. It will increase the value of using Internet banking among customers (Yu and Chantatub, 2016). Similarly, adopting a pull strategy for the diffusion of Internet banking is fruitful in increasing the potential adopters as they are more likely to come from the Internet population. In addition, collaboration with service providers, merchants and suppliers and offering free Internet access can maximise the adoption rate (Jaruwachirathanakul and Fink, 2005).

2.4.2.2 Cost of the Internet, Smartphone, and PC for Internet Banking:

Although Internet banking may be helpful to customers, the cost of operating the services (such as the cost of the Internet and the cost of smartphones or computers) is significant in the "performance-to-price" Judgment. With the rapid development of information technology, the smartphone has become an inseparable tool for communication in people's daily lives (Chaimaa, Najib and Rachid, 2020). Banks have been trying to capitalise on this opportunity to

maximise their banking activities conveniently. In this regard, smartphone and smartphone apps have played a vital role in providing Internet banking services. However, various factors such as the simplicity and time effectiveness of Internet banking apps represent the ultimate usefulness of Internet banking (Salimon et al., 2021). Time effectiveness defines the efficiency and effectiveness of Internet banking apps in terms of time-saving, faster payment, and information processing, as time is essential for Internet banking adoption. Additionally, simplicity refers to easy-to-use and easy-to-learn mobile banking apps with interactivity and clear understanding (Chopra & Sharma, 2021).

However, Arif et al., (2020) found that non-adopters of Internet banking may find Internet banking unnecessary due to the lack of competitive advantages for their needs as they must invest in smartphones or computers as well as the Internet connection. Therefore, a lack of competitive advantages and ease of use may appear to be a barrier to Internet banking usage. Chigori et al. (2020) suggested that providing the best value-to-performance to customers can reduce the barrier to adopting Internet banking. Providing one-to-one suggestions regarding how to use Internet banking efficiently and effectively to conduct their financial transactions through online customer service or bank branches will boost customers' confidence in Internet banking. Providing customers feedback and giving them a sense of control can eliminate value barriers (Pavithra and Al, 2021).

Despite having advantages, the associated cost of Internet banking can be challenging for many people. Cost is the most important factor to the people living in the 'Base of the Pyramid (BOP)' regarding new technology adoption (Baishya and Samalia, 2019). The base of the pyramid refers to people with low purchasing power and average monthly household income from \$2 per day according to purchasing power parity (PPP) to \$29.61 per month (Chipp and Corder, 2009). People living at the 'base of the pyramid' have low purchasing power and price sensitivity. Therefore, people living at the base of the pyramid in developing countries shape their consumption patterns towards their basic necessities such as food, housing and household goods. As a result, people tend to spend less on information and communication technology (ICT) (Guesalaga and Marshall, 2008).

As 54% of households in rural Bangladesh are out of Internet access, Internet banking has to provide greater value to this population to switch from traditional branch banking to Internet banking. According to the BRAC Institute of Governance and Development (BIGD), the Mymensingh, Rangpur and Sylhet divisions have comparatively less digital access and lower digital literacy rates than the Chattogram, Dhaka and Khulna. This study further stated that less

than one person has an online income, and the income of the household has a significant impact on digital access and literacy (Daily Star, 2020).

The following maps highlight the cost and speed of the Internet and their comparison among countries around the world:

Figure – 2.4.2.2 (1): Worldwide broadband speed league 2021.

Source: Cable.co.uk

● 00-01 USD ● 01-02 USD ● 02-05 USD ● 05-10 USD ● 10-20 USD ● 20+ USD

Figure – 2.4.2.2 (2): Worldwide Mobile Data Pricing 2021. (Source: Cable.co.uk)

Figure – 2.4.2.2 (3): Mobile Internet Download Speed (Source: Opensignal 2022).

From the above maps, it is noticeable that Bangladesh has comparatively lower Internet pricing than the neighbouring country India. Bangladesh holds the #8 ranking position in the world for providing the cheapest Internet, with an average price per 1GB cost of \$0.34. Customers can get the cheapest Internet as low as \$0.11, and the most expensive 1GB Internet costs \$2.22. On the other hand, the neighbouring country India holds 28 positions in the world ranking providing cheaper Internet connections to its customers where the average Internet price is \$0.68. Customers can get an Internet connection as cheap as \$0.05; the most expensive Internet costs \$2.73. Another South Asian country, Pakistan, holds the 19th position in the world ranking to provide more affordable Internet connections to customers. An average Internet price costs \$0.59, whereas a customer can get an Internet connection as cheaply as possible at \$0.06 per 1GB, and the most expensive one costs \$8.59 per 1 GB. Although the cost of the Internet is comparatively cheaper in South Asian countries, the speed of the Internet is extremely slow compared to other countries. Bangladesh provides cheaper Internet compared to its neighbours, but the speed of the Internet is at the bottom of the world list. Bangladesh holds 197 ranking in terms of Internet speed, where the download speed is 2.90 Mbps. But its neighbouring country India holds the 18th position in all ranking, providing 22.53 Mbps (Opensignal, 2022).

2.4.3.0 Risk Barrier of Online Banking Adoption:

Risk barriers are associated with resistance arising from uncertainties that are natural characteristics of any innovation (Kaur et al., 2020). Risk is a key element of the consumer decision-making process, and the adoption rate of the innovation depends on the merit of the uncertainties related to the innovation (Ansari, 2018).

Numerous studies have highlighted the risk factor in Internet banking adoption as the perceived risk. Perceived risk is very often defined as a combination of uncertainty and consequences that is a complex, multifaced and dynamic concept (Mitchell, 1999). Featherman and Pavlov, (2003) defined the perceived risk as the possibility of consumers suffering a loss due to the pursuit of consequences of having innovation. Lee (2009) classified the risk into five categories: security/privacy risk, financial risk, social risk, time/convenience risk, and performance risk. According to Ram and Sheth (1989), there are four risk factors connected with any innovation: Economic risk, Physical Risk, Functional Risk and Social Risk. In this study, the elements of perceived risk are highlighted under the four risk variants classified by Ram and Sheth (1989) to illustrate the relevant risk barriers associated with the adoption of Internet banking.

Although Internet banking assists banks in increasing their profitability and efficiency by addressing consumers' needs, improving consumers' banking experience and maximising interactivity, there may be possible risks associated that come along with the benefits (Aldás-Manzano et al., 2009). And from the customers' perspective, it can cause customers resistance to adopting Internet banking (Black et al., 2001). However, concerning the adoption of Internet Banking, resistance from risk barriers associated with customers' loss of money, suffering from the risk of fraud, problems with Internet connectivity or poor battery power of their devices and configuration of their smart devices to use Internet banking and so on (Kaur et al., 2020).

2.4.3.1 Physical Risk:

Physical risk is associated with the inherent risk of innovation that may harm a person or property. Customers resist innovation as it may affect their health or their property by using it (Sheth, 1989). Although technology makes people's lives easier, some people may find it stressful to use it at the beginning (Arif, Aslam and Hwang, 2020). Technostress refers to the negative impacts on human behaviour, thoughts, attitudes or psychology caused by the human

inability to adapt to new computer technology that includes both computers and software as well as mobile phones in a healthy manner (La Torre et al., 2018).

Dunphy and Herbig, (1995) stated that technostress is one of the crucial barriers for customers to adopt Internet banking. Technostress refers to the condition of the individual's inability to adapt to introducing and implementing new technology. However, many variables determine the level of technostress of the individual such as the individual previous experience with the technology, their age and perceived control over new tasks etc., that collectively suppressed the usefulness of the innovation to them (Ho et al., 2020).

2.4.3.2 Financial Risk:

The economic risk is connected with the cost of innovation. The level of perceived financial risk increases with the higher cost of innovation (Kaur and Arora, 2020). Customers always perceive that superior innovation may appear in the market at a lower price if they wait, which refers to the concern of customers losing money due to poor purchasing choices in pursuit of innovation. Any product that comes with new technology is susceptible to this risk (Sheth, 1989). As developing countries possess a higher uncertain social and economic environment, customers are uncertain about the consequences of their transitions due to the absence of personal assistance and face-to-face interactions that boost the associated functional risk of Internet banking among customers (Nguyen, 2020; Lee, 2009). As a result, doubts in customers' minds leave them wondering whether they have successfully conducted their transaction. These doubts lead to fear of losing their personal information and money (Asif, Aslam and Hwang, 2020).

Trust:

According to Mayer et Al., (1995), perceived risk is closely associated with trust. If the level of perceived risk is higher than the level of trust, the trustor will not be involved in trusting behaviour. On the contrary, if the level of trust overcomes the threshold of perceived risk, then the trustor will be involved in trusting behaviour. This notion is supported by (Alalwan et al., 2018) that trust plays a significant role in shaping customer perceptions and intention to use information technology as the use of information technology is associated with concern and uncertainty from customers' perspective due to the absence of human interaction (Cuong, Linh and Ha, 2015).

Customers' trust is associated with data protection and system reliability. As the customers need to register in the service system using this sensitive information, it is the financial service providers' highest responsibility to ensure the data protection and data security of customers (Kaur and Arora, 2020). Banks' integrity and ethics, along with system reliability, are the fundamental component of customers' trust that leads to the adoption of the service innovation (Moghavvemi et al., 2021). Enhanced trust increases customers' intention to use Internet banking services and reduces perceived risk by eliminating behavioural uncertainty and associated risk with service providers' intention to be an opportunist (Souiden, Ladhari and Chaouali, 2020). Customers trust service providers with the expectancy that the service provider will behave as expected with minimum complexity in their interaction without involving in opportunistic behaviour (Kesharwani and Singh Bisht, 2012).

Customers with high uncertainty avoidance countries shape their adoption decision of Internet banking, focusing on performance expectancy and trust (Lin, Wang and Hung, 2020). Bayar, Gavriletea and Păun (2021) found that most of the countries in Eastern Europe have lower adoption rates, such as Greece and Bulgaria, where higher uncertainty avoidance influences customers' trust in Internet banking. On the contrary, people from Scandinavian countries such as Denmark and Finland are more individualistic and open to adopting innovation. As a result, performance expectancy and trust appeared to be key factors for uncertainty in adopting Internet banking (Zhang, Weng and Zhu, 2018).

Security:

The breach of cyber security is one of the biggest security risks in the banking industry of developing countries. One of the major challenges is insufficient advanced technology to prevent the cyber security threat and respond to the security breaches once detected (Ali et al., 2021).

The banking industry of Nigeria, one of the most developing countries in Africa, is experiencing a higher rate of cybersecurity breaches where the cyber-enabled breaches such as viruses, worms, Trojan viruses and hackings are significantly higher than cyber-dependent breaches such as spam email (Siano et al., 2020; Aduba, 2021). The use of sophisticated technology in cyber security breaches outruns the effort of banks to protect consumers' security and personal information (Hassan et al., 2024). However, poor management support and training, along with insufficient legislation, fail to prevent these risk factors that ultimately increase consumer resistance to Internet banking (Wang et al., 2020).

From the Middle Eastern perspective, perceived risk is an essential factor in the decision-making process of adopting Internet banking (Alhakimi and Esmail, 2020). Perceived risk, along with a lack of security assurance, is playing a major role in mitigating the willingness of customers to adopt Internet banking channels (Li et al., 2021). Also, the increasing number of cybercrimes that appear to be a serious problem in Middle Eastern countries like Jordan is fuelling the risk factors. Additionally, many viruses such as Trojan horses associated with Internet use maximise the uncertainty and risk connected with the use of Internet banking (Nangin, Barus and Wahyoedi, 2020). Lack of security that drives the fear of suffering loss appeared to be a greater concern for the Jordanian customer. This is due to the increasing number of cybercrimes related to a financial transaction in Jordan and all over the Middle East that have been reported by the news media (Hassan and Farmanesh, 2022). This also creates negative perceptions in the minds of Jordanian customers who already use Internet banking service channels, which could further jeopardise and threaten the security of their personal information and the safety of their money (Alalwan et al., 2018).

Sarker et al., (2020) cybercrimes against bank accounts and credit cards, such as hackings, intrusion, malicious code, abusive content, fraudulence etc., have increased in Bangladesh more than the growth of Internet banking adoption (Hossain et al., 2020). Many customers in Bangladesh have lost their money to hackers who use skimming devices in ATM booths to steal customers' card information or make duplicate cards. More than 10 million takas were stolen, forcing many banks to repay significant amounts of money to the customers as most of the banks are not fully equipped to fight against cyberattacks to protect their Internet banking service providing infrastructure (Khan, Rana and Hosen, 2021).

Cyber security risk is not only a massive problem in developing countries but also in developed countries (Hassan and Farmanesh, 2022). Cyber security risk is the main concern among customers aged 55+ in the UK as they are aware of cyber security breaches and similar incidents published in media to help keep their concerns afloat (Hanif and Lallie, 2021). As a result, most customers feel the bank does not possess sufficient prevention measures to assure security (Hassan et al., 2024). Therefore, cybersecurity prevents these age groups from using mobile banking applications for Internet banking. However, interestingly, they have more trust in banks than the use of banking applications due to doubts about technology (Dragan, Belov and Grishunov, 2019)

Belinda et al., (2021) stated that barriers to implementing new flexible regulations related to the introduction of technological changes are another determinant for the perceived risk of data security. Hybrid policies and rules assure the reinforcement of data security and facilitate the

establishment of an open platform of banking. It also aids in private partnerships to boost the diffusion of the innovation process (Li et al., 2021).

Fraud:

Due to the abundance of cash resources and the introduction of automation in the banking process, bank accounts and transactions have become the main target of fraud in South Asia, especially in India and Bangladesh (Chhabra Roy and Prabhakaran, 2022). According to the Reserve Bank of India report, the total number of incidents of fraud reported by banks and financial institutions operating in India was 45,613 till March 31, 2021, which was rupees 4.92 trillion (Saha, 2021).

Although fraud in ATMs and credit cards has been increasing in Bangladesh, many banking frauds have raised concerns among customers (Karim and Hossain, 2021). Banking frauds are generally conducted through loan accounts, deposit accounts and different banking transactions using fraudulent papers, data, and IT software /hardware (Moreira et al., 2022). Due to the rapid growth of the banking industry in Bangladesh, the use of technology has been increasing rapidly for the automation of transitions and installing new ATMs, POS (point of sale), and mobile and Internet-based banking. Along with the improvement, internal fraud committed by corrupted employees, external fraud committed by other service providers, and third parties are sometimes connected to the scam (Ahmed et al., 2022). Technology-related fraud committed by fraudsters uses the loopholes of technologies. They also use email and SMS to ask to deposit a certain amount of money against a fraudulent lottery program. Deposit-related fraud targets wealthy individuals and customers living in foreign countries (Sarma et al., 2020). Lack of customer monitoring, poor due diligence, and inadequate KYC (Know Your Client) are the main reasons for this kind of fraud. Although loan account fraud is common in Bangladesh, the amount of money involved in the fraud is shocking (Hossain et al., 2022). Fraudsters take advantage of the poor loan appraisal system, lack of post-disbursement supervision and inadequate follow-up (Rashid, 2022).

Research on European citizens highlights those customers who are concerned and experienced, cybercrimes did not restrict themselves from using online services more than the people who are only concerned without experience (Kuzmenko et al., 2021). The study also highlighted that victims not only resist using a similar service but also distance themselves from different online platforms, which is not even related to the negative experience. For example, if people are the victim of cybercrime from e-commerce, they tend to hold themselves from using

Internet banking. The report of cybercrime in news media also plays a significant role in raising consumers' concerns (Bohme and Moore, 2012).

Consumer liability in Internet banking fraud is a major concern among users (Islam et al., 2022). Although banks refund any financial loss associated with Internet banking fraud, some exceptions are noticeable in the EU Countries (Roškot, Wanasika and Kreckova Kroupova, 2020). Such as in the Netherlands, where banks judge each incident on a case-by-case basis, and banks hold the right not to refund if they believe there is gross negligence from the customer side. However, the lack of clarity in identifying consumers' negligence leaves customers in the dark and concerned. As a result, it causes a lack of trust in Internet banking and boosts customers' concern about losing money (Van Der Meulen, 2013).

The study of Laukkanen et al., (2008) suggests that the implementation of innovative strategy can mitigate security risk factors. Nnachi et al. (2020) stated that the Innovative modification strategy encourages banks to use biometric technology systems such as fingerprints, face recognition, voice recognition and iris recognition to access Internet banking accounts by customers. Using biometric technology to access Internet banking accounts and conduct financial transactions and other banking activities provides higher simplicity and safety assurance than traditional password methods (Melnychenko, Volosovych and Baraniuk, 2020). Normalini and Ramaya, (2012) conducted their research on Malaysia to understand the effectiveness of biometric technology. Their study highlighted the benefits of having a biometric authentication system in Internet banking that not only assures the security of login information and users' passwords to reduce vulnerability but also provides greater convenience to the users to access their account quickly using their fingerprints and help banks to reduce desk cost by eliminating the password resets (Moriuchi, 2021). Martins et al., (2013) urged that banks should focus on advertising to their potential customers to promote the notion that Internet banking is not risky by providing information about the safety and security of banks' Internet banking service channels (Arora and Bhatia, 2021). Morake, Khoza and Bokaba, (2021) suggested that educating customers about the encryption systems in the Internet banking operation process and providing the assurance of a money-back guarantee in the event of any financial loss is effective in easing the consumers' concern about perceived risk (Belinda et al., 2021). Additionally, Maryna Utkina (2023) highlighted that flexible regulation is essential for the implementation of new technology where the policymakers play a crucial role in reducing the barriers in heavily regulated sectors.

2.4.3.3 Performance Risk:

The functional risk is associated with performance uncertainty where customers conceived the notion that innovation may not be thoroughly tested; thus, it inherits the higher uncertainty of not functioning reliably and properly (Seth, 1989; Owusu Kwateng, Osei-Wusu and Amanor, 2019). Featherman and Pavlov (2003) described the functional risk as the possibility of not performing as it was expected at the time of design of innovation.

Martins et al., (2013) conducted their study in Portugal to understand the adoption of Internet banking and its association with the perceived risk. Their study found that performance risks are closely associated with time risk and significantly affect the adoption decision of Internet banking of Portuguese customers (Martínez-Navalón, Fernández-Fernández and Alberto, 2023). Time risk arises due to the losses of time from making poor purchasing choices, which consists of doing research, making the purchase and learning how to use it (Kaur *et al.*, 2021). Matsuo, Minami and Matsuyama, (2018) suggested that social influence plays a meaningful role in reducing Innovation resistance by eliminating performance risk barriers through recommendation. Santos and Ponchio (2021) found that as the pre-adoption belief formed based on indirect experience and post-adoption belief formed based on experience, experienced customers are more able to use Internet banking and evaluate the effectiveness and performance as they can inherent easily the lessons learned from performance accomplishment of others due to their previous experience. Therefore, providing trial service to customers could be a good solution to minimise the performance barrier (Yoon and Lim, 2020). Providing a demi or random Internet banking account for trial may boost customers' confidence and comfortability in using Internet banking, and the effectiveness of Internet banking in their daily banking activities will ultimately erase their fear of losing personal information and funds (Asif, Aslam and Hwang, 2020).

2.4.3.4 Social Risk:

Social risk refers to the customers' resistance to adopting innovation due to social influence, the concern of being ridiculed by their peers or the fear of being criticised by social interaction because of the use of Innovation (Sheth, 1989; Marafon *et al.*, 2018). Venkatesh et al., (2003) address the social influence as the impact of an individual's friends, family and relatives on his/her mind that guides the decision-making process in terms of adopting innovation or new service. Social pressure plays a resisting factor in the adoption of innovation, which is more

influential among older workers and women in their early stages of usage of Innovation (Islam and Ahmed, 2020). The fear of social criticism for doing something new or adopting something out of the box is a common concern among people in developing countries like Bangladesh (Harun, 2022). From the Bangladeshi perspective, senior citizens dependent on their family's adult members are more likely to be influenced by social pressure (Hoque and Sorwar, 2017). However, this notion appeared to be different from the Indian perspective, although both Bangladeshi and Indian social structures represent the same characteristics (Hafez, 2021). Dutta and Sarma, (2022) conducted their research in India to identify the factors affecting the adoption of digital service innovations. Their research suggested that social influence doesn't influence the behavioural intention of customers to adopt new service innovations. This indicates people who are inclined toward service innovation due to its optimum usefulness in their daily lives are not likely to be influenced by their social support groups to form their adoption decision (Patel and Patel, 2018).

2.4.4.0 Traditional Barrier of Online Banking Adoption:

The cultural change created by innovation is the first element of psychological resistance to adopting innovation that generates traditional barriers. Consumers resist innovation when it requires them to deviate from their existing Traditions. The resistance level depends on the deviation's merit (Sheth, 1989; Afshan and Sharif, 2016).

If the innovation requires a person to drift from his or her daily habits and accepted norms, then the innovation will be opposed (Roy et al., 2016). The higher the level of differences between the innovation and the traditional habits of the consumer, the greater the resistance to accept the innovation (Singh and Srivastava, 2018). People have routines in their daily lives, and innovation may alter those routines and may cause conflict between the routines and the use of the innovation. For example, A customer can be used to visit the bank branch and get service directly from the bank employees. To the customer, this social contact is comfortable as it is inherited in that customer's traditional routine of getting banking services (Al-Ajam and Md Nor, 2015). So, switching to Internet banking eliminates the physical interaction between customers and bank employees, which is totally out of customers' traditional habitual activities, and it causes refusal to accept Internet banking by customers (Serener, 2019).

Although the traditional barrier is found not significant in the research of (Arif et al., 2020) on Pakistani customers, the result shows that if the physical presence of customers increases in

banks to conduct financial transactions, it will minimise the use of Internet banking. Traditional barriers significantly influence traditional banking customers' cognitive-base initial distrusting beliefs (Sharif and Raza, 2017). Therefore, traditional banking customers hold stereotypes, thinking that a traditional branch banking system is required to conduct their financial activities, and this ultimately makes them sceptical and cynical about adopting a digital banking system (Neil and Boshoff, 2021).

Preference for using traditional branch banking is the main reason for heavily being dependent on cash as a society which is the main deterrence of reducing currency management costs, checking tax avoidance, tracking transactions, fraud and so on (Khan *et al.*, 2021). The main motive of the financial inclusion strategy taken by the Indian government to make digital India by reducing cash dependency is making India a cash-lite society (Chawla and Joshi, 2017). This traditional habit of cash dependency costs India 3.5 billion per year in currency operations, including printing new currency, disposal of old banknotes and investing in counterfeit note detector machines (Revathi, 2019). Therefore, Internet banking is an essential medium in this perspective, but there are many challenging factors in the Indian perspective, such as lack of electricity, lack of education, lower income, mobile network, data connectivity, cost of Internet and above all, traditional dependency on cash use (Chaudhry and Dimri, 2018).

Similarly, despite significant growth during COVID-19, the Digital payment system in Bangladesh is still in the early stages (Aziz and Naima, 2021). A country is considered a cash-light society if more than 50% of financial transactions are conducted digitally, whereas Bangladesh has only 29%. More than 71% of transactions are conducted in cash, and a major portion of digital transactions end up with cash withdrawals which diminishes the purpose of cashless payment (Chowdhury, 2020).

Although many countries are trying to shape from a cash-dependent society to a cashless society, it is difficult to say which one will be able to first eliminate the dependency on cash as total elimination of cash use has both advantages and disadvantages (Gupta and Dua, 2018). The definition of a cashless society is a society without reliance on cash or coin currency, and all financial transactions are conducted electronically. Although a cashless system reduces crime rates by eliminating the possibility of stolen tangible money, it minimises money laundering (Taskinsoy, 2020). Above all, it maximises time and cost efficiency in handling, storing and depositing paper money. It also reduces other disadvantages such as possible personal data breaches, unavailability of alternative currency during technical problems or hacking activities and technological learning curve (Pritchard *et al.*, 2022).

Many countries are pressing the initiative to eliminate cash from the country's financial systems, Such as Sweden and India. This push was not only initiated by the government but also gained support from the consumers. The "No Cash Accepted" sign is everywhere in Swedish supermarkets and other shops (Horne and Collins, 2023). Sweden has taken the initiative to become the first country in the world to be a cash-free society with a 100% digital currency economy by 2023 (Simatele and Mbedzi, 2021). The track of this initiative has been noticeable in the past few years. Just less than 2% of cash transactions have been accounted for in the Swedish economy, and it's expected to drop to 0.5% by the end of 2022, along with a 10% per cent steady decline in cash withdrawals yearly (Kumar and Kumar, 2017). Cash is used barely 20% for transactions which is 75% below the global average. Surprisingly, 900 out of 1600 Swedish banks are no longer accepting cash deposits or keeping cash on hand, and ATMs are no longer visible in rural areas. The circulation of the Swedish krona has fallen to 80 billion, which was 106 billion in 2009 (Henley, 2016).

On the other hand, the Indian government banned 500- and 1000-rupee notes to catch criminals who are working informal economy in 2016. Although this initiative draws massive criticism as those notes are associated with 86% of the country's currency circulation, electronic transactions also increased rapidly during this period. Still, the situation went back to pre-demonetisation by the end of 2017 (Rowlatt, 2016).

From the Bangladeshi perspective, women are more likely to be associated with cash transactions than men, as men are traditionally more likely to be employed and have higher-paid jobs (Khatun, Mitra and Sarker, 2021). Therefore, the growth of account ownership is entirely dominated by males. The gender gap in account ownership in Bangladesh is 29% which is one of the highest in the world. Although this bank account ownership of women has increased from 10% to 36% since 2014, it is still far behind the men's account ownership which is 65% (Manzoor *et al.*, 2021). Due to traditional boundaries, and social restrictions, women are often subject to discrimination and left behind in society and their daily needs. Patriarchal social norms hinder women's involvement in financial decision-making and entering the workforce by limiting their mobility in this society (Islam, Basher and Enamul Haque, 2022). Additionally, being a cash-heavy society, employers are paying the salary in cash, demotivating employees to open bank accounts. As only 30% of women contribute to the labour force compared to 70% of men, therefore due to their lack of participation in the formal labour force, women don't find any reason to open any sort of bank account (Bader, 2018).

Furthermore, the ownership of a mobile phone for women is only 33%, and 63% are more likely to use mobile Internet than men (Tareq Hasan, 2020). Therefore, this massive gender gap in mobile ownership is causing massive disadvantages for women in acquiring mobile phones and technology to use Internet banking (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017)

Religious Belief:

Although Bangladesh is a Muslim-majority country, most of the banking activities are conducted in conventional banking compared to Islamic banking. As traditional banking is associated with Riba (interest), forbidden in Islam, many people perceive a negative image of traditional banking (Uddin and Ahmmed, 2018). Islamic banking provides all the banking products which are interest-free Sharia principles; therefore, it's also known as an interest-free banking system (Salman and Nawaz, 2018).

"An Islamic bank is a financial institution whose status, rules and procedures expressly state its commitment to the principle of Islamic Shariah and to the banning of the receipt and payment of interest on any of its operations"(Ali & Sarkar 1995, pp.20-25)

Muslim scholars defined interest as riba, which refers to any premium amount that borrowers must pay to lenders along with the principal amount as a condition for a loan or the extension of this its maturity. According to the verdicts of the Quran against riba:

"Those who devour Riba will not stand except as stands one whom the devil hath driven to madness by [his] touch [2:275]."

Quran strongly condemns the system of interest as well as imposes penalties against those who deny the verdict:

"O ye who believe! Observe your duty to Allah and give up what remains (due to you) from Riba, if you are (in truth) believers. And if you do not, then be warned of war (against you) from Allah and His Messenger. And if you repent, then you have your principal (without Riba). Wrong not, and you shall not be wronged [2:278-9]."

Religious belief can have a significant impact on customers in the decision-making process regarding banking. This study of Hassan et al. (2023) showed that interest has a significant positive impact on customers' decisions regarding bank deposits in non-Muslim countries. On the contrary, People in Muslim-majority countries are not concerned about their interests due to religious restrictions while conducting banking transactions due to established regulations in the banking system (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). Although Bangladesh is a Muslim-

majority country, it does not follow Islamic law to govern the country. Nonetheless, people are becoming more religious day by day, and they are developing and practising Islamic values and principles (Ahmed and Mohamad, 2019). The findings of Khan and Mohamed (2017) show that Islamic values have a significant role in shaping individuals' decision-making to accept products offered by banks in Bangladesh. Islamic values cause concern among individuals regarding God's punishment as well as strong religious beliefs, which divert their attitude and mindset toward Shariah-based banking and avoid the conventional banking system (Mbawuni and Nimako, 2018). Another important factor that plays an essential role in diverting people's attention from traditional banking to Islamic banking is the reputation of banks. Also, recent banking scandals significantly ruined the reputation of many conventional Banks. Therefore, people have developed a negative image of traditional banks. On the other hand, Islamic banks have held a positive image among the population for a long time due to their reputation (Hoque et al., 2022).

2.4.5.0 Image Barrier of Online Banking Adoption:

Every innovation has its own identity that arises from its origins, such as the category of product, its industry, and the manufacturing country. If any of these associations appear to be unfavourable to customers, they develop a negative image of the product and ultimately resist the innovation creates barriers to its adoption (Mani and Chouk, 2018). Image barrier is a perceptual problem which is excluded from the contemporary notion of the customers making the adoption process of innovation challenging (Sheth, 1989). For example, Internet banking is not usually considered a secure medium for financial activities. Therefore, it assists in creating a negative image. *"If the user has an unfavourable impression of the originating country, brand, industry, or other side effects of/to the innovation, it produces an image-based obstacle."* (Lian and Yen, 2013, PP. 666).

Customers' level of technological orientation defines the significance of the image barrier. The study by (Kaur et al., 2020) on young adults suggested that the image barrier doesn't affect young adults as they are more likely to be technologically advanced and hold a positive image of different technology-oriented social and commerce platforms. Generally, they are more familiar with various mobile applications and the latest technologies (Ameen, Willis and Hussain Shah, 2018).

Although massive development in banking apps makes the banking service easier and easier to communicate, many non-adopters perceive new technology as a matter of concern, and it is not easy to use (McDonough, 2016). Banks should take the initiative to create a positive image of Internet banking to customers by informing them that Internet banking is not only for banking transactions but also can be used as a smart tool to track their real-time transactions, their account balances as well as recent transaction history (Claudy, Garcia and O'Driscoll, 2014). Yu and Chantatub (2016) conducted their research on Thai and Chinese consumers, and their study suggested that image barrier negatively affects consumers' decision to adopt service innovation. This study indicated that the bank should introduce an experiential marketing strategy to eliminate the consumers' resistance to adopting Internet banking. Experiential marketing strategy effectively maximises the consumers' willingness (Koksal, 2016). It changes their negative perceptions of Internet banking if banks are confident enough about the effectiveness of their Internet banking services over the traditional ones (Arcand *et al.*, 2017). In this way, the consumers will be able to gain positive experience through practical use, and it will be able to influence their perceptions of Internet banking services that it can make their life easier and fulfil their daily business and financial requirements. Therefore, providing Internet banking experience to potential users is an effective strategy as long as Internet banking exhibits apparent advantages over other banking channels (Shareef *et al.*, 2018).

2.5 Conceptual Framework:

The following conceptual framework is developed on the foundation of the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) and demonstrates the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City. This conceptual framework consists of two main aspects, Cultural factors & Local Perceptions and Lack of Infrastructure. Cultural factors refer to societal attitudes, beliefs, norms, or values that are common to a particular demographic group or population, or the determinants of these beliefs (Valerie Kincaid Oppenheimer, 2001).

Local perceptions encompass cultural values, beliefs, and historical aspects (Fernández-Llamazares *et al.*, 2016) and Lack of Infrastructure (The financial infrastructure is made up of technical systems through which payments are made and transactions with financial instruments are handled (Neos Networks, 2023)).

Both Cultural factors & Local Perceptions and Lack of Infrastructure independently and collectively work as resistance factors that ultimately influence Internet banking adoption. Additionally, Cultural factors and lack of infrastructure are intertwined and influence each other elements. Usage Barriers, Value Barriers and Risk Barriers directly influence “Lack of Infrastructure” and Traditional Barriers and Image Barrier directly influence cultural factors and Local perception.

However, demographic factors directly influence “Cultural Factors & Local Perception” that passively influence risk barriers, value barriers and usage barriers and these barriers affect Internet banking adoption through the “Lack of Infrastructure”. On the other hand, demographic factors shape the local perception regarding Internet banking adoption through Image barriers and Traditional barriers.

Usage Barriers, Value Barriers, and Risk Barriers altogether work as functional barriers to the Internet banking adoption process where image barriers and traditional barriers act together as psychological barriers in Internet banking adoption.

Figure- 2.6: Factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city, Bangladesh.

Usage barriers are one of the most critical barriers to Internet banking adoption. Usage barriers associated with consumers' negative experience of using Internet banking. Usage barriers arise due to the lack of service infrastructure in Internet banking. Uses barriers and cultural factors influence local perceptions through lack of infrastructure, leading to resistance to Internet banking adoption. Value barriers caused by a lack of infrastructure affect innovation and raise questions among customers about its worthiness to adopt by customers. It shapes local perception and other cultural elements that ultimately create resistance factors to Internet banking adoption.

Additionally, risk barriers affect Internet banking adoption through poor service infrastructure that fails to mitigate the inherent risk of innovation. Furthermore, traditional, and cultural barriers are interconnected with cultural factors and perceptions of the local population that

cause resistance to Internet banking. Lastly, demographic elements influence all the factors that affect Internet banking adoption.

This conceptual framework proposed above can be operationalised in the banking sector in Bangladesh to understand the factors behind the slow adoption of Internet banking. This conceptual framework demonstrates all the critical areas of resistance factors that directly and indirectly shape the consumers' perceptions in combination with local perception and lack of service infrastructure. Therefore, this framework can help to implement a new policy for the development of Internet banking and to eradicate existing flaws and resistance factors to enhance the Internet banking adoption rate.

Chapter 3: Research Design, Methodology & Data

3.0 Introduction:

The previous chapter (*Chapter- 2: Literature Review*) discussed the critical areas of Internet banking and Internet banking adoption around the world with specific focus on Bangladesh, starting with conceptual clarification, describing different theoretical models of Internet banking and other influential factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the Internet banking literature. Lastly, the discussion of the conceptual framework of the research presented a comprehensive understanding of the adopted framework in this study.

This chapter illustrates the research design and methodology that have been used to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. Research design is a generally structured roadmap for collecting and analysing data with clear objectives and methods that combine relevance to the research purpose. The accessibility of the data also combines with the process, for example, the availability and accessibility of the data of the selected organisations (Saunders, 2016).

This chapter is going to present the research paradigms such as epistemology, ontology, methodology and methods. Furthermore, this chapter also demonstrates other significant aspects of research design, such as the data collection process, sample selection, research approaches, strategies and methods adopted for data analysis to support the research objectives. In short, the overall discussion of this chapter focuses on pragmatic epistemology, a descriptive analysis of survey data, and a thematic analysis of qualitative data.

3.1 Theoretical Assumption and Research Paradigm:

3.1.1 Ontology:

Ontology is the study of nature that tells us what reality is. Bryman (2004) defined ontology as a theory of social entities' nature. Saunders, (2016) described ontology as an assumption of the nature of social phenomena that contributes to knowledge. Ontology is a human assumption that people make about their surrounding's nature of reality (Esterby-Smith et al., 2002). Ontology addresses three basic questions such as, what is reality or knowledge? What shapes reality or knowledge? What is the relationship between each component that shapes reality or knowledge? (Staiton-Rogers, 2006). There are many beliefs of ontology. However, one of the

three beliefs is the singularity which addresses that there is only one reality and only one universal set of truth or solutions or reality available for any issue or problem. This reality exists without how people perceive reality. The second concept of ontology, adopted by qualitative strategy researchers, is that some multiple realities or truths are not independent of perception as it depends on how people perceive the truth or knowledge of reality. Qualitative researchers accept the ideology of having multiple realities rather than believing in a single reality (Cresswell, 2007). Therefore, Burrell and Morgan (1979) stated that the assumptions of reality (ontology) could be studied through subjectivism and objectivism (which is also known as constructionism). The third belief is that one or maybe multiple realities exist.

3.1.1.1 Constructionism/Subjectivism:

Subjectivism is also known as constructionism or social constructionism (Saunders et al, 2007). The development of the subjectivism paradigm is based on a reaction to the application of the positivism paradigm in social science from the assumptions that reality is not objective but rather socially constructed and added meanings by the people. The core concept of ontological assumption in the subjectivism approach is that reality is shaped by the human imagination and their perception of it (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Qualitative researchers nurtured the idea that social reality is constructed through the interaction of social actors and shaped by their belief systems. Subjectivism is believed to be associated with the social phenomenon created by human assumptions, perceptions and social actions concerned with that existence, and this can be perceived as a continual process. Therefore, it is the process of continuous revision and improvements through the social interaction of social actors (Saunders et al., 2007). In short, the main purpose of constructivist research is to interpret the thinking and feelings of people, and the communication channels, including verbal and non-verbal, as well as to develop understanding and explain the underlying concept of people's different experiences in social settings.

3.1.1.2 Objectivism:

Objectivism is associated with quantitative research where reality is perceived objectively. The objectivist assumptions address that the existence of social phenomena, and their meanings is independent of social actors (Bryman, 2004). The core concept of objectivism addresses that experienced social phenomena and their meanings in everyday life are independent of the social actors. Social science aims to predict reality as objectively as possible (Davis et al., 1993). The

objective view of knowledge suggests that theories that originated from science provide an explanation of the actual description of reality. Objectivists believe that empirical knowledge involves in universally recognised structure or theory that can be tested against objective data. Therefore, the adoption of natural science methods that utilise numbers in the measurement is acceptable to understand the relationship between things in social settings (David and Sutton, 2004). In a nutshell, the objectivist's view addresses reality as concrete and real as the natural world. It emphasises the necessity of identifying the relationship between elements in which they are constituted as a whole.

3.1.2 Epistemology:

Epistemology is the study of the philosophical issues underlying theoretical knowledge (Crotty, 1998). Epistemology is the branch of philosophy that studies the nature of experience and process (Gall et al., 2003). Epistemology describes the assumptions about knowledge as well as the constitution of acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge and how to communicate that knowledge to others (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). Epistemology highlights the most appropriate way of enquiring into the nature of the world and seeks the answer to the question of "what is knowledge and what are the sources and limits of knowledge (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). Bryman (2004, p. 24) define epistemology as a theory of knowledge that concerns the question of what is considered acceptable knowledge in a particular discipline. Saunders et al., (2007) address epistemology as a branch of philosophy associated with the study of the nature of knowledge and what represents acceptable knowledge in a study.

Couper (2022) defines epistemology as a study of knowledge and seeking the answer to the questions of "what is knowledge" and "how do we know something". Cooper emphasised that the significance of epistemology is not only to critically evaluate the reliability of knowledge but also to understand the active influence of that knowledge in our society. However, Saunders et al., (2007) raised the question of whether epistemology in social science and the social world should be studied according to the same principles and procedures as natural sciences.

Easterby-Smith et al., (2002) address the question of the acceptability of knowledge developed from the adopted research process. Therefore, it can be concluded that the epistemological assumptions are closely interconnected with the nature of knowledge and adopted research processes and methods from which knowledge can be developed and acquired.

Three epistemological assumptions will be discussed in the following section, namely positivism, Interpretivism and Pragmatism.

3.2 Research Philosophy:

Selecting a research philosophy is crucial as it sets the right direction for conducting the research. The nature of the research methodology (research design, research strategy and data collection methods) is determined by selecting the right research philosophy.

3.2.1 Positivism:

One of the most used epistemologies within the field of research is positivism which holds objectivist ontological assumptions. The assumption of objectivism is that knowledge cannot be obtained unless someone is exposed to or physically comes into contact with an item or phenomenon. Positivism addresses the objective reality that exists independently from the individual's beliefs. Therefore, the significance of knowledge depends on whether it is based on observation of external reality (Esterby-Smith et al., 2002). The core concept of positivism is that the existence of social facts is external; therefore, the researchers should be independent of the properties of the research, and the research should be conducted in accordance with objective methods such as the experimental method in which testing theory or hypothesis gradually refine or develop universal law of nature. Positivist researchers believe that events and entities in the outside world settings are closely constituted in a straightforward relationship as well as people's knowledge of it (Staiton-Rogers, 2006). Positivist researchers are also known as resource researchers as they try to predict and explain social phenomena by investigating casual relationships and regularities between the entities. The experimental design that emerged from natural science dictates the research methodology of positivist views. Positivist research methods constitute a large-scale survey population, formal questionnaire, and standardised interviews to conduct research on numerous topics through statistical analysis, including measurement scale and the development of measurement models. A positivist style theoretical perspective that describes that meaning can only be understood when it is scientifically verified, tested and proved. However, it is well recognised in business, management and marketing research that a positivist theoretical perspective is superficial and does not allow for further scope for the research to construct an in-depth understanding of the research phenomenon.

3.2.2 Interpretivism/Constructivism:

Interpretivism is developed from a subjective perspective as a critique of positivism. Interpretivism insists that human and physical phenomena are different as human creates meanings, and these meanings are studied by interpretivism. Interpretivist insists that human beings and their social world cannot be studied together in the same way as physical phenomena. People make different meanings based on their cultural backgrounds, circumstances and time differences and, therefore, create and experience different realities (Saunders et al., 2007). Interpretivist researcher believes that facts and values are not different, and the outcome of the resource is significantly influenced by the perspectives of the researcher and their values. However, the interpretive view is also known as phenomenology. This philosophical aspect highlights how people understand the world around them and make sense of it and how the researchers describe their preconceptions about it according to their understanding of the world (Bryman, 2004). In short, phenomenology refers to the core concept of the researcher's participation in the socially constructed phenomenon, which is closely related to creating meanings and obtaining a deeper understanding of those phenomena. Constructionism evaluates the development of a jointly constructed understanding of the world that forms the basis for shared assumptions about reality. The theory centres on the notion that meanings and reality are developed in social settings by people's perceptions and experiences (Leeds-Hurwitz & Wendy, 2009).

Interpretive research aims to create new, deeper understandings and interpretations of the social world and its context. According to some researchers, the positivist approach is perfect for business and management research, especially in marketing and human resource management (Saunders, 2007). This is due to the fact that the social world cannot be understood through the methods of natural science as the social world (Business and Management) is not dictated by law-like regularity but rather understood through meanings and social actors (Lewis, 2003). This notion in business and management research means observing the organisation from the perspective of different groups of people. For example, in a banking company, the CEO, board of directors, managers, employees, cleaners, and customers view and experience the banking and organisation differently. It undoubtedly can be concluded that they are experiencing workplace realities differently. So, if the researchers focus on the experiences that are common to everyone, the richness of the differences between them and their circumstances will be lost, and this will affect the understanding of the organisation by the research. Therefore, no single reality is to be found, only multiple realities to be constructed by the people who co-construct

meaning and knowledge. Therefore, establishing models driven by natural science is not suitable for the explanation of human behaviour; therefore, researchers in social science should gain deeper insights or meanings through both participants' and the researcher's understanding.

Ontological Stance	Epistemological Stance	Research Philosophy
Singular Reality	Examine Using Established Design and Tools	Positivism
Multiple Realities	Examine Using Interpretive Approach	Constructivism
Singular And Multiple Realities	Examine Using Best Tool Available	Pragmatism

Table – 3.2: Research Philosophy.

3.3.3 Pragmatism:

This research has adopted the pragmatism philosophy. Unlike positivism and interpretation, Pragmatism distinguishes itself from continuous metaphysical concepts such as truth and reality (Bishop, 2014). Therefore, Pragmatism accepts the notion of the existence of having a single reality or multiple realities that are the subject of empirical inquiries (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). The belief of pragmatic scholars recognises the existence of objective reality separated from human experience. However, reality is embedded in the environment, which can be encountered through human experience (Coates, 2020). Pragmatism provides the concept that knowledge and reality are socially constructed through beliefs and habits. However, this socially constructed knowledge sometimes matches individuals' experiences more than others. Pragmatists not only believe that reality cannot be determined once and for all but also a normative concept and reality is what works. Therefore, the reality is true if only it assists in establishing a satisfactory relationship with other parts of human experiences (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2021).

The decision to accept one reality over others depends on the effectiveness of that reality on the desired outcomes (Shaw, Connelly and Zecevic, 2010). For example, a positivist researcher may claim that an object with four legs and a flat surface shall always be a table. On the other hand, constructivists may believe that based on his or her perspective and observation. For a

constructivist, the same object would be a table if he/she ate food from it. He/she might address it as a platform if he/she was standing on it. However, the pragmatist will define the object based on its use. Such as an object will be a table if he/she intends to use the object for eating food from it, similarly, if he/she intends to use it to stand on it, it can be a platform if he or she intends to use it for sitting, can be called a bench. In short, the definition of an object to a pragmatist is not based on what it is or the object's purpose but rather on how this object assists the pragmatist in achieving the desired outcomes. From the perspective of the research paradigm, pragmatism focuses on solving practical problems in the real world and is used as a method of inquiry by problem-solving practical-minded researchers (Allmark and Machaczek, 2018). Pragmatists believe that the inquiry is only fruitful if it can successfully meet its target outcomes. Instead, Pragmatism aborts traditional subjective/ objective philosophical concepts and idealistic and rationalistic approaches; it focuses on empirical outcomes. Pragmatism guides researchers to focus on both post-positivism and constructivism, two approaches to inquiry, rather than assigning them into ontological and epistemological categories (Hall, 2013).

Pragmatism is the guiding principle for this study. The theoretical perspective of this research has followed a Pragmatic research philosophy. Pragmatic research philosophy has defined the philosophical position of forming the research methodology of this study and has provided a direction and setting for this research to find the answers to the questions of how cultural factors and local perceptions impact the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City and how does lack of infrastructure impede the delivery of Internet banking service. The adoption of the Pragmatic research philosophy in this research is consistent with the mixed methods research approach and research design. It provides flexibility to the researcher to find the answer to the research questions considering the limitations and challenges this study has faced due to the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic.

3.4 Research Approach:

Selecting the right research approach is crucial as it defines the aims of the research and the direction of the research, which solely depends on the right selection of the research approach. The research approach is mainly classified into two categories: inductive and deductive approach. It also defines the scope of the research and assists the researcher in the justification of the research to develop credibility and usefulness.

In the deductive research approach, researchers use hypothesis testing to investigate the relationship among variables under any previously established theory or study. The deductive approach is commonly used to identify the credibility and truthfulness of prior research. Additionally, in the deductive approach, there is a high chance of having differences in the results. A deductive approach is associated with quantitative research, positivist epistemology, and an objective ontological worldview. Quantitative research is related to a large number of data and cases where the deductive approach is used for collecting, analysing, and predicting certain results using quantitative data to develop/ test theory. Quantitative research tests the relationship between variables by measuring numerically and analysing by using a number of statistical and graphical techniques. The data used for the quantitative research approach is secondary data from primary sources collected from observation and measured through a ratio scale. (Saunders, 2016).

In the inductive approach, completely new outcomes in terms of theory, model or any suggestions are being developed by researchers. In inductive research, the results can be based on any philosophy but relatively new or incremental and refined in nature in which researchers add improvements to existing research (Nicholas, 2011). The inductive approach is associated with qualitative research with interpretive epistemology and a constructive ontological worldview. Qualitative research helps explain the social world, understand reality, and help develop explanatory models and theories. According to (Field, 1996), "*Qualitative is constrictive systematically, and even 'tested' or verified during the process of constriction, a qualitative-derived theory has minimal risk of invalidity.*"

Apart from this domain of research approaches, another research approach, which is a combination of both qualitative and quantitative approaches, is known as the mixed method, a widely adopted research approach in the literature. Despite being divided into three categories, qualitative, quantitative and mixed research methodological approach, the primary purpose of qualitative, quantitative and mixed research is to construct a solid theory or develop an existing theory as an outcome.

This research has adopted a mixed-method approach in combination with the qualitative method (Interview) and quantitative method (Survey), which is inductive reasoning in nature (as there is no developed hypothesis for quantitative analysis). The researcher has adopted a mixed method approach in line with the pragmatism philosophical perspective discussed earlier. The use of mixed methods in this research is due to its usefulness and distinctiveness in business research as findings from different methods have the potential to enrich the

understanding of business problems and add value and contribute to research (Molina-Azorín *et al.*, 2012)

Reason for Using Mixed Methods Approach:

The main purpose of adopting a mixed method approach in this research is that a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches provides a better understanding of the research problems than adopting any of the mono methods alone (Creswell and Piano Clark, 2007). Triangulation of one set of findings with another set of results enhances the validity of this research and provides a better understanding. Another important factor for adopting mixed methods research in this study is the design of the research method as it helps the researcher design the method that is best suited for the study by considering two factors such as priority and implementation of data collection. In relation to priority, the researcher has the flexibility to prioritise both qualitative and quantitative parts equally or prioritise either qualitative more or quantitative more. This emphasis may come from research questions, practical constraints on data collection, or the necessity to understand the data before proceeding to the next set of data. Implementation of the data collection addresses the sequence the researcher follows to collect both qualitative data and quantitative data such as concurrently (data collected at the same time) and Sequential (Introducing the data in phases) (Molina-Azorin, 2016).

As this study initially attempted to prioritise both qualitative and quantitative parts equally, it wasn't possible to maintain due to time constraints and lack of access due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, the mixed method approach allowed the researcher to emphasise the qualitative part more than the quantitative part of this research while implementation of the data collection process followed a concurrent process due to time constraints (Creswell and Piano Clark, 2007; Molina-Azorin, 2016). Further details of mixed methods are going to be discussed below:

3.4.1 Mixed Method Research:

This study has adopted a convergent parallel mixed method design. Mixed method research is simply known as a study combined with multiple research approaches. However, many researchers have found inconsistencies in conceptualising or defining mixed-method research. Tashakkori and Creswell, (2007) addressed the mixed method into categories: the first category

addresses the mixed method as a collection and analysis of two types of data, such as qualitative and quantitative, which is closely focused on "methods". Another category of the mixed method is integrating two quantitative and qualitative approaches, which are more focused on "methodology". Although this inconsistency in defining mixed method is indicated in many research (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2003; Sandelowaski, 2003); Tashakkori and Creswell, (2007) broadly defined mixed method as a study focused on qualitative and quantitative approaches or methods in collecting & analysing data, integrating findings and drawing conclusions in a single study or single program of inquiry. Bazeley (2010) define the mixed method as a study consisting of multiple research paradigms, methodological approaches, more than one way of the data collection process and data analysis to achieve one common objective despite the classification of the methods, whether qualitative or quantitative or somewhere in between. Tashakkori and Creswell, (2007) found numerous ways to mixed-method resources in social, behavioural and Health Sciences and adopted qualitative and quantitative approaches in their study, such as:

- Adopting two types of research questions in conjunction with qualitative and quantitative approaches.
- Process of research questions development such as participatory and pre-planned.
- Two different data collection procedures. Such as surveys and semi-structured interviews.
- Two types of data such as textual and numerical.
- Two types of data analysis such as statistical and thematic.
- Two ways of concluding such as objective and subjective.

This study has adopted two data collection procedures, such as survey and semi-structured interviews, and two types of data analysis: statistical and thematic. Mixing the qualitative and quantitative components of research is supported by the study of Yin (2006), where the author insisted on having multiple or different mixes or combinations of methods in the study. In addition, Bergman, (2008) stated that there is no necessity to distinguish between qualitative and quantitative methods or approaches to research.

3.5 Research Methodology:

Research methodology refers to procedures, techniques or models that are used to find out the result of a research question. Research methodology established the principles of organising, planning, designing, and conducting research. The adoption of methodological research choice is determined by the research paradigm followed by the researcher, which provides direction for selecting data collection and analysis methods (Sayer, 1992). In short, research methodology provides a clear road map for conducting the research, indicates what type of data will be required for the research and what appropriate tools are required in the research process (Adil &Khalid, 2016). Research methodology also guides the researchers in what type of procedures and practices researchers should follow when using any method according to research philosophy (Guba, 1990). The qualitative method is associated with social reality, and the quantitative method is generated from natural science. Qualitative and quantitative methods are established on the researcher's epistemological and ontological viewpoints directed by the research methodology (Robson, 2002). As the reader of the research draws their conclusion based on the data presented in the research, it is the researcher who interprets what is worth knowing, how to get the knowledge and how to interpret it, which is the fundamental aspect of truth or reality. Therefore, the relationship between methodology (How and why knowledge), epistemology (knowledge) and ontology (the reality we seek to know) are interconnected in the research, which has been discussed earlier in this chapter.

3.6 Research Strategy:

A research strategy is a step-by-step plan of action that guides the researcher's thoughts and efforts systematically to conduct the research to produce quality results. This research has used a semi-structured interview and a survey strategy. Many researchers have adopted multiple research methods in a single study as the combination of multiple research methods improved the quality of research and findings. Therefore, the researcher has chosen a mixed-method strategy in this research, which is the best fit for this study to get the best results and ultimately achieve the research objective.

Questionnaires and interviews have been adopted in this research because the nature of this study will allow the researcher to adopt both qualitative and quantitative techniques to address the factor affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh. Adopting this research

strategy is based on the researcher's understanding of research philosophy and methodology in line with the research objective. Therefore, this research strategy is based on pragmatism philosophy with a descriptive research approach and mixed methodology.

Adopting mixed approaches increases the reliability and the validity of the results. However, the problem with mixed-method approaches is that the mixed-method approach consists of qualitative and quantitative methods traditionally associated with contrasting worldviews. So, it is a common question in the perspective of mixed method approaches which worldview shall be chosen? And how to justify it?

However, one of the most common approaches is an exploratory study to address this problem, starting with quantitative methods and then followed by qualitative methods. In this approach, researchers begin by assuming a positivist worldview about being scientific, objective and stable. The second phase of this approach is associated with interviews and focus groups, which is a sudden shift from a positivist to a flexible and interpretable worldview. So, in this mixed-method approach, researchers cover two different worldviews and explain how they shift from one worldview to another.

However, in this approach, adopting both scientific inquiries while being objective and the importance of individual perspective and individual beliefs and experiences makes it an inclusive, flexible, and single worldview. So, the question is how we can believe one thing for the sake of this study and methods to fit in our purpose to achieve the objective and then shift towards a completely different and contrasting worldview because people following one worldview tend to disagree with another worldview. As a result, this creates a conflicting approach to the research.

Hence, the researcher adopted Pragmatism in this research as Pragmatism argues for adopting one worldview no matter how flexible or inclusive it is. And we should choose one worldview that suits all the assumptions underlying the study. Pragmatism is a very flexible approach and worldview that emphasises and encourages the use of whatever works in this study. The most crucial aim is to answer the research questions, especially during the data analysis. So, the main priority of Pragmatism is to answer the research question and to use whatever means possible just to achieve the goals without necessarily thinking about the dichotomy and distinction between positivism, interpretivism and other approaches.

Pragmatism encourages researchers to do whatever researchers perceive will help answer the research questions and collect the data required to answer the questions. As Pragmatism recognises that individuals construct reality simultaneously, this is a reconstruction of something relatively stable that exists. Therefore, Pragmatism recognizes both interpretivist

and positivist views. It assumes that the individuals construct reality, which is an interpretivist way of thinking. Still, at the same time, it recognized that these are the reconstruction of something relatively stable, typically a positivist viewpoint. Pragmatists emphasise the importance of empirical observation, which is something traditionally associated with positivism. Still, at the same time, they stress that these observations rely on the researcher's interpretation of these observations, so this is again interpretivism.

Pragmatists recognise the existence of specific established stable social structures, again a positivist idea. Still, at the same time, they acknowledge people's roles and establish and construct these social structures, which is very interpretive. So, this can be concluded that Pragmatism holds certain assumptions from both positivism and interpretivism approaches. Therefore, the interview and survey methods have been used in this study along with the data triangulation method, which helps overcome any possible philosophical and methodological distinctions within this study (Polit et al., 2001).

3.7 Research Design and Methods:

Research design is the structure of the research that holds all the elements of research together, and overall, it is the plan of the proposed research work. It can be defined as the blueprint of data collection, measurement, and analysis. *"A research design is the arrangement of conditions for the collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy and procedure"*- Jahoda, Deutch & Cook, (1965) quoted in Akther, (2016).

This research has adopted a convergent parallel mix method, also known as the concurrent triangulation, mixed-method approach. In the concurrent translation approach, qualitative and quantitative data are collected concurrently or at the same time. Then, the researcher analyses both datasets to investigate the convergence, differences, or combinations. The convergent parallel mix method approach is one of the most popular among researchers due to its familiarity and acceptance (Creswell, 2003).

3.7.1 Survey Questioner:

Survey design is a sub-design of the descriptive research design, which is used to collect primary data. In this research, a survey design is used to collect primary data for frequency distribution analysis as there are no hypotheses. Frequency distribution analysis helped the researcher analyse the factors affecting the adoption of online banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. Survey design is chosen to accumulate quantifiable data that could be transferred into statistical software such as SPSS for conducting frequency analysis and crosstabulation.

There are some other reasons for choosing a survey design to collect quantitative data for this research which are illustrated below:

- It was easy and convenient for the researcher to distribute the survey questionnaires via emails, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger and other social communication media to online banking customers (both active users and dormant users), which saved both time and cost.
- It is also convenient for the participants as they can complete the questionnaires according to their convenience and own time, which maximises the objectivity of their responses.

- It allowed the distribution of clear, concise, and straightforward standardised questionnaires without leading to further questions, making the questioners answer adequately and return accordingly.
- In addition, the researchers couldn't visit Bangladesh for data collection due to the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, adopting the survey method allowed researchers to collect necessary data using distant communication mediums such as email, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and other communication channels.

Close-ended questionnaires were designed where respondents what about to select one answer. The questionnaire was designed considering the respondent's convenience in answering the question such as:

- The questionnaires were designed in simple and understandable ways not to challenge respondents' memory to answer the question and keep them interested in the process.
- The language of questioners is carefully chosen in a conventional manner and restricts the possibility of further leading questions.
- Respondents were given an opportunity to review their answers.
- The questionnaires were designed to keep the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.
- Respondents were given enough time to answer the questions without giving time restrictions.

The survey questionnaires consisted of two sections. The first sections consist of demographic questions, and the second section consists of questionnaires related to factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna, city Bangladesh. The theme of this question developed from relevant Internet banking adoption literature in the shadow of the innovation resistance theory element that addresses different adoption barriers to Internet banking adoption. The survey questionnaires were close-ended as close-ended questionnaires are self-explanatory and do not require any interpreter or researcher's assistance. Close-ended questionnaires are time-saving, and they allow respondents to answer the questions swiftly during their daily activities. Close-ended questions require minimal instructions to answer the questions without confusing the respondents, and it also holds respondents' attention in the survey answering process.

3.7.2 Semi-structured Interview:

A semi-structured interview is a data collection method that relies on asking questions within a predetermined thematic framework. However, the questions are not set in order.

3.7.3 Interview Protocol:

Semi-structured interviews were conducted for this research which lasted 30 to 40 minutes each. Some of the interviews were conducted in the office environment of the participants. However, the interview data collection was conducted in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic and most of the bank employees in Bangladesh had limited working hours in the banks. Therefore, some of the interviews were conducted in the participant's home environment, which was comfortable and free of interruptions from outside, which ensured a smooth interview process with any interruptions.

The researcher carried out a pilot study before the final interview data collection process went 'live' to determine the clarity of the questions and to check that they convey a clear meaning which meets the purpose of the research. Two participants were interviewed for the pilot test using a purposeful sampling technique, and their interviews were recorded. All the questions in the primary questionnaire were covered in the Interviews. However, before conducting the pilot interview, signed consent forms were collected from the participants before conducting the pilot interview. The consent forms were clearly highlighted with all the interview requirements, such as recording the interview for thematic analysis purposes. After finishing the interviews, the transcribed interview data was sent to the respondents just for the accuracy and correctness of the information. After conducting the pilot study, the data collection was found to be unbiased. According to Given (2008), pilot testing not only helps to find out the potential methodological errors while conducting interviews but also assists the researchers in mitigating those issues beforehand. After conducting a pilot study, minor changes were made to the interview questionnaire and recording process. According to the guidelines of the supervisor, although the respondents were found to be comfortable, no major issues were found.

Final interviews were requested and pre-arranged via emails after conducting pilot interviews. A consent form and invitation were sent to each participant before the meeting with each of them. After getting their consent, the interview time and location were decided; due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it wasn't possible to take the interview face-to-face. In this case, all the interviews were conducted virtually using Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Google Meets and

WhatsApp to record video conversations of the interviews, along with "OTTER.AI" software to record the participants' responses in transcribed format for the thematic data analysis. Before conducting the interview, the interviewer familiarised himself with the research questions and objectives and provided a brief to the interviewee about the core purpose of conducting this research and its objectives. All the interviews were conducted in a friendly and professional manner to capture accurate data. Additionally, the researcher noted verbal and non-verbal clues during the interview session by observing respondents' body language, which enhanced the interview's quality and increased the data's value. The average length of each semi-structured interview was 35-40 minutes, which is considered the appropriate length for conducting a semi-structured interview (Kolar, 2011). All the interviews were conducted in the English language. The selection of the interviewees was conducted according to purposive sampling to get the answer to the research question from the banks' internal employees who are knowledgeable about Internet banking adoption and the associated barriers, as well as local perceptions on the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city, Bangladesh. As the interviews were conducted online, the researcher identified targeted bank employees and contacted them via email. The researcher requested assistance from close friends and families to contact particular bank employees and requested the bank employees to participate in the interview on the researcher's behalf. After getting initial confirmation, formal invitations were sent along with constant forms.

As the interviews were conducted online, the richness of in-person interviews is missing in some cases to capture the participants' body language. However, social platforms appeared to be a great medium for conducting interviews considering the pandemic at that time, which was beyond anyone's control. As some of the interviews were held at the participants' homes, participants were relaxed and focused in the interview, which is different from the interviews conducted in the office environment. Additionally, participants were engaged in daily office tasks and also had to interact with their colleagues some cases, participants were distracted, and their body language appeared inconsistent. However, due to the lack of a physical face-to-face interview process, the lost data in the process were minimal and insignificant, and it did not affect the data collection process overall.

At last, the researchers were successfully able to conduct all the resources according to plan. Although all the interviews were conducted in English, in some cases, further clarification was needed after conducting the interview as English is the second language of the respondents, And the data was collected accordingly.

3.8 Research Population and Sampling:

Khulna is one of the biggest cities for the baking industry, and Khulna city is one of the few cities where Internet banking is receiving higher importance. For that reason, Khulna city is chosen as a case study area. All the active and dormant Internet banking users in Khulna city were the research population of this research.

3.8.1 Quantitative Sampling: “Snowballing Sampling Method”

The snowballing sampling method was followed to collect survey data as it was not possible for the researcher to travel to Bangladesh and physically conduct the survey due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown and travel restrictions. Therefore, social media platforms were the only way to collect data to finish the research in a timely manner. In addition, the response rate of the academic survey has decreased gradually over the years. Therefore, the snowballing sampling method helps to collect data through social media from a hard-to-reach population in a timely and cost-effective manner at the same time maintain appropriate research standards (Dusek, Yurova and P. Ruppel, 2015).

To maintain rigor when collecting survey data from hard reach population, targeted sampling is useful (Watters & Biernacki, 1989).

“It [targeted sampling] draws from both survey and qualitative research methods.... through an interactive process of adjusting research targets, recruitment methods, and research questions and instruments, inquiry can be focused on the most appropriate subjects for study” (Watters & Biernacki, 1989, p. 427).

One such targeted recruitment method is snowballing sampling or chain of referral. As snowballing sampling (targeted sampling) allows researchers to have greater control over sending invitations to participate in the survey, it also provides some control over the resulting sample through the adjustment of all available tools such as recruitment methods, research question, research targets and instruments to make the sample a close reflection of the population under study (Baruch & Holtom, 2008).

“Nearly all studies of hidden populations are carried out in circumstances that do not permit true random sampling. Under these conditions, and if properly conducted and tied to what is known or can be learned about population parameters, targeted sampling provides a more

powerful sampling mechanism than convenience sampling and a more feasible approach than random sampling” (Watters & Biernacki, 1989, p. 427).

Comparison between externally obtained values of the targeted population with collected sample values helps to identify the success of the targeted method. Significant differences indicate adjustments are required in the targeting. Therefore, this comparison indicates the sample’s representativeness of the population (Baruch, 1999).

In this this research, demographic information was collected from existing literature and data source to compare with the sample demographic statistic. The comparison indicated that sample was representative of the targeted population. In addition, survey questioners were distributed in different parts of the population area through different social media channels that ensured response are true representation of targeted population and ensured the results free from biased. In snowballing sampling, the personal recommendation of the participants to their close contacts increases the number of participants to meet the expected sample size of the research. Although, participants of the survey were asked to recommend others who have Internet banking experience to take part in the survey, researcher had control over the distributing the survey questioners to ensure the true representation of all different group of people based on age, income, education.

The sample size of Quantitative Data:

$$\text{Necessary Sample Size} = \frac{(Z - \text{score})^2 \times \text{StdDev} \times (1 - \text{StdDev})}{(\text{margin of error})^2}$$

Based on Unknown Population Size: a 95% confidence level, .5 standard deviation, and a margin of error (confidence interval) of +/- 5%.

$$\begin{aligned} &= ((1.96)^2 \times .5(.5)) / (.05)^2 \\ &= (3.8416 \times .25) / .0025 \\ &= .9604 / .0025 \\ &= 384.16 \\ &= (385 \text{ respondents are needed}) \end{aligned}$$

Z-scores for Confidence Levels:	
90%	Z Score = 1.645
95%	Z Score = 1.96
99%	Z Score = 2.576

The required sample size of the survey was 385 respondents based on an unknown population, as the Internet user population was changing rapidly at the time of data collection. Therefore, the researcher calculated the sample size based on the unknown population formula, which appeared most appropriate to the researcher.

In collecting the survey data, a survey questionnaire was distributed through the snowballing sampling method. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was impossible to collect all 385 necessary sample data. A total of 219 participants responded, and 19 did not qualify. Therefore, the final sample size was 200 for this research.

As this research adopted a mixed method research approach which allows the researcher to have more emphasis on the qualitative side of the research, the final sample size of the quantitative part of the research didn't affect the novelty of the study. The survey questionnaire is appropriate as it is cost-effective and gives participants the flexibility to complete the questionnaire at their own time and pace. The questionnaires were made easy to understand and concise to avoid a low response rate.

3.8.2 Qualitative Sampling: “Purposeful Sampling Methods”

Sampling is one of the most important factors to maximise the validity and efficiency of the research regardless of qualitative or quantitative methodology (Robinson, 2014). In qualitative methods, the consistency between sampling and the assumption innate in the research design is crucial (Patton, 2002). Luborsky and Runinstein (1995) stated that qualitative sampling is a process of choosing a sample of individuals and groups with relevant knowledge and significant life experience related to the research phenomenon under investigation.

This study has adopted a purposeful sampling technique. Purposeful sampling is one of the most commonly used sampling techniques in qualitative research as it helps to identify and select well-informed individuals or groups of individuals in terms of the best use of the resources (Given, 2008). Purposeful sampling is helpful for selecting knowledgeable and information-rich individuals. It helps select individuals with good communication skills, and the ability to articulate and express their points of view through their life experiences in a reflective manner. On the other hand, probabilistic random sampling gives research control over the outcomes through the predetermined assumption, and that leads to generalised findings where purposeful sampling helps researchers to conduct an in-depth investigation of the social phenomenon to provide applied understanding through the use of existing theories to provide a clear understanding how a particular phenomenon works in real life (Sandelowski, 2000).

By using the purposeful sampling technique in this study, two factors have been taken into consideration to choose participants for semi-structured interviews. Such as their position in the organisation because these are employees with a clear understanding of the online banking operation and have at least a minimum influence on the organisation's decision-making process to support the uptake of online banking and their close interaction with customers. Also, they had to use online banking in their daily financial activities.

This study integrated reflexive inquiry into the methodology where the researcher gets involved by connecting with the participants who share their experiences and views through a semi-structured interview data collection method. A semi-structured interview is instrumental in revealing the unexpressed meaning of individual experiences through their expression, experiences and activities during the interview in audio or video format (Tong et al., 2007).

This study used this method to record the participants' attitudes and views towards adopting Internet banking in Bangladesh to understand the barriers preventing their adoption, transcribing and converting the recorded interviews to extract the facts with a broader meaning regarding online banking adoption in Bangladesh. In this research, seven semi-structured interviews with bank employees were conducted.

3.8.3 Sample Size of Qualitative Data:

There are no fixed, established rules for qualitative sample size as it depends on the researchers' knowledge, research purpose and associated credibility and usefulness of the research (Sandelowski, 1995). Usually, the emphasis goes on small-scale data in qualitative research methodology, whereas quantitative research methodology consists of large-scale numerical data (Saunders et al., 2018). The sample size in qualitative research methodology is based on saturation which means researchers continue to sample the individuals for a clear understanding of the phenomenon to the point where no new theoretical insights or patterns can be revealed. Therefore, it is impossible to determine the sample size in advance. However, until saturation is reached, the researcher must proceed with qualitative interviews.

A semi-structured interview format was used to get the responses from the respondent. The semi-structured interview is used over structured and formal interviews because of its methodological superiority (Adams, 2010). It allows the researchers to understand and contextualise the phenomenon as an investigator. The semi-structured interview technique allows the researchers to approach the respondents from their point of view and allows the researcher to adjust questions and ask sub-questions during the interview to have a detailed, comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and allows researchers to ask open-ended questions with follow-up queries.

In this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with seven participants who are employees of seven different banks. The sample size is often justified by interviewing participants until reaching 'data saturation' in interview studies. However, there is no agreed method of establishing this (Francis *et al.*, 2010). Saturation is the most common guiding principle for assessing the adequacy of purposive samples in qualitative research (Morse, 2015). After conducting seven interviews, no new data was found through the interview and

saturation of qualitative data was established. Saturation is a point where no new code or categories can be found in data and repetition of the issues without providing further understanding and contribution to the phenomenon and its dimension (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). According to Morse, Lowery and Steury (2014), saturation should be only if there are no issues to be found in two or three consecutive interviews or it was determined by two researchers.

No.	Bank Name	Code Name of participants	Job Position	Experience
1	Mutual Trust Bank	S.I	Bank Manager	10 years
2	HSBC	Pro.	Bank Manager	12
3	Dutch Bangla Bank	Sa.U	Customer Service Supervisor	13 years
4	City Bank	Em	Bank Manager	11 years
5	BRAC Bank	Ts	Bank Manager	15 years
6	Prime Bank	Su	IT Manager	10 years
7	Eastern Bank Ltd.	Tr	Bank Manager	8 years

Table – 3.8.3: Profile of Interview Participants.

3.9 Qualitative Data Analysis:

The collected survey data were transferred into numeric, quantitative data for analysis using data analysis software "SPSS" to conduct frequency analysis and Cross-tabulation Analysis. The interview data were transcribed by A.I. software "OTTER.AI" in Word format for the Thematic Data analysis in Nvivo12, where different constructs were extracted to create themes.

3.9.1 Thematic Analysis:

The thematic analysis identifies, analyses, and reports themes or patterns within qualitative data-rich details. Thematic analysis is essential for new qualitative researchers because of its flexibility and accessibility in conducting qualitative research compared to the other available approaches, making it easily understandable for new researchers. It also provides core skills that help to conduct further research. The necessity of theoretical and technical knowledge of approaches is required in other techniques such as grounded theory, but it is not required in thematic analysis; therefore, the thematic analysis offers greater accessibility for the analysis to the new qualitative researcher, especially in their early career in qualitative research.

Thematic analysis is not a methodology but rather a method, which makes it a very flexible method for learning and teaching (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Despite being widely used, there is no clear collective opinion regarding the definition of thematic analysis and how to conduct it (Tuckett, 2005). Unlike other theories, thematic analysis is not associated with any pre-existing theoretical framework, which makes it flexible to include in any theoretical framework. Therefore, thematic analysis can be a wide variety of methods such as the essentialist or realist method that highlights meanings experience and the reality of participants, the constructivist method that reports socially constructed meaning experience and reality as well as the contextualist method which is also characterised by critical realism theory (Willig, 1999).

A thematic analysis theme represents patterns of meanings or responses within a data set. There is a question of what makes a theme and what is the ideal size of a theme. However, in qualitative analysis, there are no hard and fast rules on the data set size that need to be presented as a theme or considered a theme. Therefore, it depends on the researcher's consideration to define what makes the theme. Researchers are suggested to provide room for flexibility as rigid rules do not work in thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

However, the overall nature of the thematic analysis makes it widely acceptable to wider audiences; therefore, this research has adopted thematic analysis for the qualitative data. The primary qualitative data of this research were collected through interviews, and the interviews were recorded in audio format to transcribe them for the thematic analysis.

As qualitative analysis only provides guidelines, there are no fixed, established rules for conducting thematic research. As it is not a linear process but a recursive process where you need to move back and forth, thematic analysis develops over time, and the researcher should not rush in the process. Braun & Clarke, (2006) provided a thematic analysis guideline which consists of six phases that were followed in the research.

Phase 1 - Familiarising with Data:

In this phase, the researcher got familiarised with the data set through in-depth reading of the data set and transcription of data and repeated readings, actively searching for meanings and patterns, and making initial notes. Therefore, it was essential to read the entire data set as it allowed the researcher to shape the ideas and helped to identify the crucial patterns of the data set.

Phase 2 - Generating Initial Codes:

After getting familiarised with data through repeated reading, researchers needed to make initial notes of the data based on the interesting patterns and their importance, which helped later to create initial codes.

Phase 3 - Searching for Themes:

After finishing coding and collating initial data, the researcher re-focused on the broader themes and allocated Coded data and the data extracted under the potential and relevant themes. The researcher analysed the codes broadly to identify how the combined codes fit into the overarching themes.

Phase 4 - Reviewing Themes:

In this phase, the researcher reviewed the themes with coded data extracted and the entire data set to check the themes' quality and generate an overall thematic "map" of the analysis.

Phase 5 - Defining and Naming Themes:

This phase consisted of the specification of the themes through refinements. Understanding what the theme was all about and what aspect of data represented by themes and naming the themes according to their specification.

Phase 6 - Producing the Report:

This was the final phase of thematic analysis, where the researcher fully worked out what themes were involved in the analysis. The researcher wrote the thematic analysis for the research. It is important to remember during the write-up of thematic analysis that the researcher needs to explain the complicated story of the data in a concise, coherent, logical, non-repetitive and interesting way so that it ensures the highest merit and validity of the analysis to the readers. Therefore, the representation of data extracts as sufficient evidence is important to showcase the prevalence of the themes.

3.10 Validity, Reliability and Triangulation:

Triangulation is a technique of analysing the same study's findings using multiple data collection methods. Triangulation aims to increase the validity, evaluate the understanding of the research problem in different ways and illustrate a clear and in-depth picture of the research problem (Nightingale, 2009). This study has collected quantitative (survey) and qualitative (interview) data from two different sources to triangulate research findings that ensure validity and rigour. Additionally, detailed descriptions of research procedures increase transferability (Bitsch, 2005). Therefore, this study has provided a detailed justification of the qualitative and quantitative data collection process that increased the transferability. Dependability refers to the researcher's or participants' capability to evaluate recommendations and interpret the findings that are stable over time (Bitsch, 2005). The research of this study evaluates the data multiple times for the trustworthiness of the recommendation and interpretation of the findings. The credibility of the results is maximised by including multiple methods with different participants (Anney, 2014). This study adopted a survey of Internet banking users and interviews with the internal employees of banks to ensure the credibility of the findings.

3.11.0 Ethical Consideration:

Four major principles by the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee guidelines were taken into consideration to ensure this research meets the ethical practice of the business research standards and contains no ethical issues. The interests and integrity of the participants were protected from physical, psychological, and cultural harm. During this research process, no one was harmed or did not create any discomfort or distress during the research process.

3.11.1 Confidentiality and Anonymity: In the questionnaire, there was no identifying information, this would protect the confidentiality of the participants, and the participants were informed about this before they gave their consent. The participants were assured that their data would be treated and protected with high security. The computer with saved data will be password-protected, and data will be deleted after finishing the research. Participants were assured that their information and responses could be deleted upon their request at any time.

3.11.2 Access Issues: A set of questionnaires was used in this study to collect the primary data. In order to do that, Internet-mediated access is needed. Therefore, an initial informal request was sent to the bank branch employees via email to access data. Then a formal email was sent with the full description of the research, what kind of information would be collected as well as a sample questionnaire that would be given to the participants. They were further assured that the privacy of their institutions would be protected, and they may refrain themselves from providing sensitive information during the interview. Participants were assured that no access to their institution or database would be requested during the whole process, and they may withdraw their participation if they are not comfortable.

3.11.3 Autonomy: During the data collection process, informed consent was sought from participants to make sure that they were fully aware of the purpose of the research and ensure they were willing to participate in the research. The information provided by the researchers to the participants was sufficiently detailed, relevant, and accurate. The participant information sheet outlined clearly and honestly all aspects of the research that are relevant to a decision to consent. A verbal and written briefing of the research was given to the participants before they gave their consent. No written consent was asked by the participants.

Participants were fully aware that they could withdraw their participation at any time. The contact details of the authors were provided. Consent was freely given. There was no undue influence or coercion e.g., by the offering of disproportionate reward or disincentives for not consenting. It was ensured that the potential participants understood the nature of the research and the procedures involved. Potential participants were given sufficient time to consider the information and to make a decision regarding participation.

3.11.4 Justice and Inclusiveness: There was fairness and equity for all research participants. They were selected randomly and fairly without justifying their age, race, language, disability, culture or religion. They were also aware that all the information was treated equally and fairly for this study, and assurance also was given that they would have the same opportunity to benefit from this research, such as having a copy of the publication after finishing the study.

Chapter 4: Analysis & Findings

4.0 Introduction:

The previous chapter (*Chapter 3: Research Design, Methodology & Data*) presented the research paradigms such as epistemology, ontology, methodology and methods. Furthermore, the previous chapter also demonstrated other significant aspects of research design, such as the data collection process, sample selection, research approaches, strategies and methods adopted for data analysis to support the research objectives. In short, the overall discussion of this chapter focuses on pragmatic epistemology with a mixed method approach, descriptive analysis of survey data, and thematic analysis of qualitative data. Lastly, highlighted the ethical consideration of the research.

This present chapter illustrates the outcomes of survey analysis and the interpretation of interview-based qualitative responses of bank employees on the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the Khulna region in Bangladesh. A total of 14 themes (reflecting five categories of innovation resistance factors adopted for this study from Innovation Resistance Theory) have emerged from the qualitative data analysis for this study in accordance with the literature review and which significantly illustrates the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. The identified themes and patterns in this study significantly enrich the quality of the study and describe how the cultural factors and local perceptions shape the customers' decision on Internet banking adoption and the role of infrastructure in the uptake of the Internet banking adoption process within the innovation resistance theory framework.

The design of the survey and the selection of the banks for interviews were based on the following criteria:

- The necessity of maintaining the diversity of the banks that are providing Internet banking services includes small and large banks, Sharia-based banks, Bangladeshi banks, and foreign banks during interviews.
- As the focus of this research is to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking, it just essential to include the most popular and digitally innovative banks that are providing Internet banking services.

- The presence of the coronavirus pandemic just before the data collection forced the researcher to adopt some element of "convenience" selection in the data collection process. Due to the travel restrictions, it wasn't possible to take the interviews in person in Bangladesh. Therefore, the interview was conducted remotely through the Online communication medium. Contacting banks regarding the interview arrangement was difficult; therefore, the researchers had to largely depend on social contacts, friends and family and the recommendations to find out suitable bank employees to conduct the semi-structured interview.
- The survey questionnaire was designed considering participants demographic factors. In addition to that conceptual framework shaped the design of both questionnaire sets (Survey & Interviews) by ensuring that the questionnaire sets represent all the research questions, and it is aligned with the research aim and research objectives. Lastly, past studies in the Internet banking literature provided guidance as well to prepare the final questionnaire sets for this research.

Research Objectives:

1. To understand the current situation and practice concerning Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through in-depth analysis of existing literature review, current news articles and publications from banks.
2. To identify the factors hindering the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh through conducting a survey among customers in the Khulna region and conducting interviews with senior bank employees due to their in-depth knowledge regarding the issue.
3. To understand the demographic characteristics of current users of Internet banking by conducting survey on the population. Survey results help to understand customers' behavioural traits towards Internet banking adoption based on their age, gender, profession, and disposable income.
4. To understand the banks' infrastructural position and its impact on the Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through the review of existing literature and conducting interview of senior bank employees. Additionally, survey responses from customers will assist in achieving this objective by highlighting the key issues regarding banking infrastructure as primarily customers are more likely to face problems through service experience.
5. To understand the role of customer service in the uptake of Internet banking by analysing the customers' opinions through survey responses and banks perspectives from the

interview of the senior bank employees due to their closeness with the decision-making process.

6. To provide recommendations based on the findings of the research for the sustainable development of Internet banking in Bangladesh.

4.1 Analysis and Findings of Survey:

4.1.1. Demographic Analysis and Background of Respondents:

The analysis of respondents' Gender, Age, income, and educational qualifications are presented below:

❖ *Gender of the Respondents:*

Out of 200 respondents, 60% or 120 respondents are male, and 40% or 80 respondents are female.

Table: Gender of the Respondents				
Respondents	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	120	60.0	60.0	60.0
Female	80	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table – 4.1.1 (1): Gender of the Survey Respondents (Source: Own Survey.)

❖ *Gender and Age of the Respondents*

This study finds that 6.5% of users belong to the '18 or below' age group, where 2.5% represent male users and 12.5% represent female users. So, in this age group, females are 10% more knowledgeable about Internet banking than males. Age group 18 – 25, The response rate of the female is 21.3% which is 10.5% higher than the male response (10.8%). But Male response rate suppresses the female response rate in the age group 25 - 30, where the Male response rate was 30%, and the Female response rate was 22.5%. This explains male started their decision-making at the age of 25, which is much later than females. In the age group 30 - 40, both male and female response rate was found to be the same, but this changed with the age group 40 - 50, where the female response rate dropped to 18.8%, which is 2% lower than the male. And

this difference increases in the 50-plus Age group, where the male response rate of 20.8% and female-only 10%, which is 10.8% lower than the male response rate. This explains that male dominates in work-life while females are more concerned about household matters (See: Table-3).

Table 3: Gender vs Age (in years)							
	Age in years						Total
	>> 18y	18y – 25y	25y – 30y	30y– 40y	40y – 50y	50y+	
Male	2.5%	10.8%	30.0%	15.0%	20.8%	20.8%	100%
Female	12.5%	21.3%	22.5%	15.0%	18.8%	10.0%	100%
Total	6.5%	15.0%	27.0%	15.0%	20.0%	16.5%	100%

Table – 4.1.1(2): Gender vs Age Crosstabulation. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Educational Qualification and Income Per Month:**

Out of 200 respondents, 23.5% of customers have finished their high school education. 21% have completed their bachelor's degree are the highest percentage of respondents (29.5%) finished their master's degree. 13.5% of respondents held PhD or higher degrees, and 12.5% of respondents attended trade school for education.

Educational Qualification		
	Frequency	Per cent
SSC/HSC.	47	23.5
Bachelor's degree.	42	21.0
Master's degree.	59	29.5
PhD or Higher.	27	13.5
Trade school.	25	12.5
Total	200	100.0

Table – 4.1.1(3): Education of the Respondents. (Source: Own survey)

As people's income is directly associated with their education, the following table illustrates respondents' income Versus education. Out of 200 respondents, 16% of customers' monthly income was 10K or below, where 19.1% of the customers only attended high school for their education and 20% of customers attended trade school. However, the percentage of respondents with master's degrees earning 10k Is higher than those holding bachelor's degrees (11.9%). However, the higher percentage of respondents earning 30K to 50K per month is 18% who hold a master's degree (30.5%) and a PhD or higher educational degree (33.3%). Out of the respondents, 17% earn 20K to 30K per month, whereas customers who have trade school education earn the highest percentage per month, which is 28%. Out of 200 respondents, 12% of customers make 50K plus per month, whereas PhD or higher degree holders hold the highest percentage, 51.9%, earning that 50k+ BDT per month category. 23% of respondents were found to be unemployed, having 200 respondents, where 40.4% of respondents have just high school qualifications, and the second-highest unemployment rate found among bachelor's degree holders was 35.7% (See table: 4).

Table 4: Educational Qualification * Earnings per month Crosstabulation							
Educational Qualification	Earnings per Month in Bangladeshi Taka.						Total
	>> 10k	10k to 20k	20k to 30k	30k to 50k	50k+	Unemployed.	
SSC/HSC.	19.1%	14.9%	14.9%	6.4%	4.3%	40.4%	100.0%
Bachelor's Degree	11.9%	21.4%	19.0%	9.5%	2.4%	35.7%	100.0%
Master's Degree	22.0%	11.9%	15.3%	30.5%	5.1%	15.3%	100.0%
PhD or Higher	-	3.7%	11.1%	33.3%	51.9%	-	100.0%
Trade School	20.0%	16.0%	28.0%	8.0%	16.0%	12.0%	100.0%
Total	16.0%	14.0%	17.0%	18.0%	12.0%	23.0%	100.0%

Table – 4.1.1(4): Education vs Income of the Respondents. (Source: Own survey)

4.1.2 Cultural Factor and Local Perception and Problem-Specific Analysis and Findings:

In this section, many factors have been studied from the literature review and respondents answered based on their experience. The following section explains all the issues regarding cultural factors, customers' perceptions and the associated problems with Internet banking:

❖ Convenience of Internet Banking:

Consumers' perceptions about the convenience of Internet banking over traditional banking is an essential factor in the adoption of Internet banking. This study finds that 46.5% of respondents believe that Internet banking is more effortless than traditional banking; however, 22.5% of respondents believed otherwise. However, 15.5% of respondents confirmed that they know about the convenience Internet banking provides, and they intend to use it soon. Although 15.5% agreed that Internet banking is more effortless than traditional banking, they are not interested in using it.

Figure 4.1.2 (1): Convenience of Internet Banking

The following table represents a cross-tabulation of respondents' Gender and their perceptions of the convenience of Internet banking. The main intention is to identify which gender group mostly perceived Internet banking as convenient. According to the research, 46.5% of 200 respondents believe Internet banking is more convenient than traditional banking. However, 46.5% of female respondents (55%) believed more than male

respondents (40.8%) that Internet banking is more convenient than traditional banking. However, 31.7% of male respondents said that Internet banking is not convenient enough; only 8.8% of females responded that Internet banking is not convenient. 12.5% of males were familiar with Internet banking, and they have planned to use it were, 20% of female respondents well familiar with Internet banking and planning to use it, but 15% of males said they were aware of Internet banking convenience but not interested in using it and 16.3% female respondents showed no interest to use it even though they are familiar with the convenience of Internet banking.

Gender * Convenience of Internet banking Crosstabulation						
		The convenience of Internet Banking				
				I'm familiar with it and planning to use.	I'm familiar with it but not interested to use.	Total
		Yes.	No.			
Gender	Male	40.8%	31.7%	12.5%	15.0%	100.0%
	Female	55.0%	8.8%	20.0%	16.3%	100.0%
Total		46.5%	22.5%	15.5%	15.5%	100.0%

Table 4.1.2 (1): Convenience of Internet Banking

❖ **Promotion of Internet Banking:**

Promoting Internet banking through different communication channels is essential to make people aware of it and maximise its adoption. This study finds that respondents know about Internet banking through various communication channels. Out of 200 respondents, the highest percentage of customers (30%) learned about Internet banking through social media. 15.5% of respondents read about Internet banking in newspapers, and 20.5% of respondents learn about Internet banking through television programs and advertisements. 18.5% of respondents became familiar with Internet banking through search engines, while 15.5% confirmed that they have learned about it through communication and recommendations from their friends.

Figure 4.1.2 (2): Promotion of Internet Banking. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Regularly Used Device:**

Internet banking requires a smart electronic device to conduct banking activities. Therefore, it is essential to know what type of electric device people frequently use, and it will assist banks in developing a strategy to boost Internet banking adoption. This study finds that 55% of respondents frequently used their mobile phone, 18.5% regularly used their tablet device, and 26.5% of respondents regularly used their laptop or desktop computer.

Figure 4.1.2 (2): Regular Used Device. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Banks Notification:**

Notification from banks makes customers aware of the Internet banking service and products offered by banks and keeps them updated about the latest information and changes in the banking industry, which is essential for the maximisation of Internet banking adoption. This study finds that 28.5% of respondents confirmed they get notifications from banks once a month, whereas only 10% of respondents said they get the notifications from banks every day, 17% said they get them regularly, and 12% said they get a notification once a week. However, 10% said they never get any notification from their respective bank about Internet banking services.

Figure 4.1.2 (4): Notification from Banks. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Internet Service in Bangladesh:

Internet service is the fundamental element of providing Internet banking service. Understanding the situation of Internet services in Bangladesh is essential to Determine the underlying facts and issues about Internet services that are hindering the promotion of Internet banking. Out of 200 respondents, 38.5% of respondents confirmed that the Internet speed in Bangladesh is very slow, and 19% of respondents believe that the Internet is expensive. However, significantly, 21% of respondents say that the Internet is not available everywhere in Bangladesh. However, 16% of respondents found Internet speed and cost satisfactory from their experience, and 5.5% of respondents found that the Internet service is good.

Figure 4.1.2 (5): Internet Service in Bangladesh. (Source: Own survey)

The following table explains cross-tabulation between Internet banking services in Bangladesh and whether customers think that banks should provide free training and cheaper Internet connections to their customers. The main intention of this question is to understand the situation of Internet service in Bangladesh from the customers' perspective and how they find it to conduct their Internet banking, as well as understand their need for training and cheaper Internet connection from their respected banks. This survey finds that 60.5% of respondents believed the Internet is expensive and they expect free training from their bank as well as a cheaper Internet connection, whereas 21.1% believed otherwise and 18.4% were not sure about

that. However, in terms of Internet speed, most of the respondents who were 62.3% believed the Internet is very slow and also expected free training and cheaper Internet connections from banks. 61.9% of respondents expect a good Internet connection from their banks as they stated the Internet connection is not available everywhere. However, 25% of respondents believed that banks should not provide Internet connection and training as they found the Internet speed and cost satisfactory. Only 9.1% of respondents believed that Internet service is good, and they do not expect further training or cheaper Internet connection from their bank.

Internet service in Bangladesh * Banks should provide training and cheaper Internet connection Cross-tabulation					
		Banks should provide training and cheaper Internet connection			
		Yes.	No.	Not sure.	Total
Internet service in Bangladesh	Internet is expensive.	60.5%	21.1%	18.4%	100.0%
	Internet speed is slow.	62.3%	18.2%	19.5%	100.0%
	Internet is not available everywhere.	61.9%	14.3%	23.8%	100.0%
	Internet speed and cost satisfactory.	53.1%	25.0%	21.9%	100.0%
	Internet service is good.	54.5%	9.1%	36.4%	100.0%
Total		60.0%	18.5%	21.5%	100.0%

Table – 4.1.2(2): Internet service vs Need for Free Training & Internet Connection. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Frequency of Bank Visits by Customer:

How frequently customers visit their bank branches explains the dependency on traditional branch banking. This study finds that 25.5% of people confirmed that they need to visit their bank branch regularly, and 25.5% said they visit their once a month their bank. 23% of respondents say they visit their bank once in six months, and 16.5% said they visit their bank branch every week. However, only 9.5% of respondents said they needed to visit their bank branch every day.

Figure 4.1.2 (6): Frequency of Bank Visit by Customer. (Source: Own survey)

The following table shows across tabulation between customers' frequent visits to their bank branch and their satisfaction with the customer service provided by their bank. The main intention of this table is to identify the effectiveness of customer service that determines customers' necessity to visit their bank branch to conduct their banking and find the solution. This study finds that the highest percentage of customers, 74.5%, who are not satisfied with banks' customer service regularly visit their bank branch. The second-highest percentage of respondents who are not satisfied with banks providing customer service is 52.6%, and they visit their bank branch every day for their banking purposes. However, 43.5% of respondents who visit their bank branch once in six months are satisfied with the customer service provided by their banks and 45.5% of respondents who visit the bank where are found to be satisfied with the customer service provided. However, the highest, 33.3% and 30.4% of respondents who visited their banks once a month and once in six months, respectively or not sure about whether the customer service provided by their banks why is satisfactory or not. Therefore, most of the customers had to regularly visit their bank Date to the unsatisfactory customer service provided.

How frequently do you visit your bank branch? * I am not satisfied with the bank's customer service Crosstabulation

		I am not satisfied with the bank's customer service			Total
		Agree	Disagree	Not Sure	
How frequently do you visit your bank branch?	Everyday.	52.6%	26.3%	21.1%	100.0%
	Once a week.	30.3%	45.5%	24.2%	100.0%
	Once a month.	45.1%	21.6%	33.3%	100.0%
	Once in six months.	26.1%	43.5%	30.4%	100.0%
	Regularly.	74.5%	9.8%	15.7%	100.0%
Total		46.5%	28.0%	25.5%	100.0%

Table – 4.1.2(3): Frequency of Bank Visit vs Satisfactory Customer Service. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Reason for the Unpopularity of Internet Banking in Bangladesh:**

This study investigated the reason behind the unpopularity of Internet banking unpopularity among Bangladeshi customers. This study finds that 10.5% of respondents believe it is not easy to open an Internet banking account. 24.5% of respondents out of 200 believe that security is the main concern for not being popular among the population. Also, 17.5% of respondents believe that Internet banking is not available in most banks, and 19% of respondents pointed out a lack of knowledge of customers about Internet banking. Interestingly, 12% of people suggested that Internet banking has an English interface, and most people don't know English; therefore, Internet banking has failed to be a popular banking medium among ordinary customers. Additionally, 16% said they don't see any real value in having this type of account.

Figure 4.1.2 (7): Reason for Unpopularity of Internet. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Need for Training and Free Internet Connection Provided by Banks:**

As training facilities help customers to know how to use Internet banking effectively and cheaper Internet connections motivate customers to use Internet banking channels to conduct banking activities, banks can take essential steps to promote Internet banking. This survey question was intended to find out what customers think about this notion. This study finds that 60% of customers believe banks should provide training facilities to customers along with cheaper Internet connections to promote Internet banking. 18.5% of respondents did not agree with this concept, and 21.5% weren't sure about the idea.

Figure 4.1.2 (8): Free training & Internet connection from Banks. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Common Problems Faced by Customers:

Respondents were asked what problems they usually face during their Internet banking. 20% of respondents out of 200 say that Internet banking is convenient, but it's not always faster for them. Additionally, 14.5% of respondents shared their experience that they faced difficulties accessing their account. However, the highest percentage of respondents (28%) said there is a lack of personal banker relationships, which is a problem for them. 14.5% of respondents say it does not fulfil their needs, and 9.5% considered the deposit limitation a problem for them. Above all, 20% of respondents believed Internet banking provides a limited scope of services.

Figure 4.1.2 (10): Common problems faced by Customers. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Most Used Banking Services:

Understanding the consumers' needs and demand for services is essential to improve service quality and implement new strategies to promote Internet banking. This study shows that the highest percentage (22.5%) of respondents use Internet banking services to make money transfers. The second-highest 22.5% of respondents used Internet banking services to check their bank balances. However, only 6.5% of Respondents' Internet banking service usage is associated with applying for a credit card, loan or opening a bank account. 18.5% and 17% of respondents use Internet banking to shop and access banks' Internet portals, respectively. Also, only 8% of respondents use Internet banking services to set up direct debits or standing orders for making their payments.

Figure 4.1.2 (11): Frequently Used Services (Source: Own survey)

❖ Bangla Interface:

As most of the bank's operating system is in English and English is the second language in Bangladesh, understanding what kind of banking interface customers prefer is essential for adopting Internet banking. This study finds that 59% of respondents believe that it is convenient and easy to do banking tasks more effectively if the bank uses the Bangla interface in their operating system for Internet banking. However, 21.5% of respondents did not agree with this notion, and 19.5% were unsure about this idea.

Figure 4.1.2 (12): Bangla Interface. (Source: Own survey)

Bangla interface makes banking easy * Educational Qualification Crosstabulation							
% within Bangla interface makes banking easy							
		Educational Qualification					Total
		SSC/HSC	Bachelor's degree.	Master's degree.	PhD Higher.	or Trade school.	
Bangla interface makes banking easy	Agree	22.9%	28.0%	28.8%	6.8%	13.6%	100.0%
	Disagree	16.3%	11.6%	37.2%	27.9%	7.0%	100.0%
	Not Sure	33.3%	10.3%	23.1%	17.9%	15.4%	100.0%
Total		23.5%	21.0%	29.5%	13.5%	12.5%	100.0%

Table – 4.1.2(4): Need for Bangla Interface vs Education. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Risk of Fraud:**

The incidents of fraud in recent banking history forced customers to be reluctant to adopt Internet banking. Therefore, understanding customers' perceptions of fraud is essential to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking. This study finds that 50.5% of

respondents believe that Internet banking increases the risk of fraud. 25.5% of respondents said they were not sure about this, and 24% did not agree with this statement.

Figure 4.1.2 (13): Risk of Fraud (Source: Own survey)

❖ Inconvenience Banking Apps/website:

Convenient banking apps and bank websites help customers conduct banking activities smoothly and swiftly; however, inconvenient banking apps and websites create negative perceptions and discourage them from using Internet banking frequently for their banking tasks. Understanding how customers think about their banking apps and websites is essential for the improvements. This study finds that 40.5% of respondents found their banking apps and websites are not user-friendly, 34.5% are not sure about it, and only 25% of people found their banking apps and websites convenient for their banking tasks.

Figure 4.1.2 (14): Inconvenience banking Apps/website (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Internet banking App compatibility:**

Although most people have personal mobile phones, the banking app needs to be suitable for that particular mobile device of the customer to conduct Internet banking activities. Survey results show that 40% agreed that the banking apps are not suitable for mobile phones. However, 30% said their mobile device is suitable for mobile Internet banking apps, and 30% of respondents are not sure about it.

Figure 4.1.2 (15): Internet banking App compatibility (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Cash Preference:**

Using cash for the transaction is one of the most popular mediums worldwide, especially in developing countries like Bangladesh. This study finds that 54.5% of respondents said they prefer cash for further financial transactions, 25% of respondents prefer other transactions, and 20.5% are unsure whether they prefer using cash or other transactions.

Figure 4.1.2 (16): Preference of Cash (Source: Own survey)

Gender vs Cash Preference:

		Gender * I prefer to use cash. Cross-tabulation			
		I prefer to use cash.			
% within Gender		Agree	Disagree	Not sure	Total
Gender	Male	60.8%	21.7%	17.5%	100.0%
	Female	45.0%	30.0%	25.0%	100.0%
Total		54.5%	25.0%	20.5%	100.0%

Table – 4.1.2(5): Gender vs Cash Preference. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Customers Service:

Customer service is crucial in sustaining existing customers through providing excellent Internet banking services. Swift and effective customer service helps customers to conduct their banking tasks quickly. It also creates trust in Internet banking. However, this survey finds that 46.5% of respondents are not satisfied with their banks' customer service when they face any problem concerning Internet banking. 28% of respondents disagree with the statement that they are happy with the service provided by their banks, and 25.5% of respondents are not sure about it.

Figure 4.1.2 (17): Customer Service from Banks. (Source: Own survey)

❖ Security of Personal Data and Money:

concern about personal data and money is a common subject in Internet banking. How customers feel assured about their personal data and financial safety is an essential factor determining the adoption of Internet banking. This study finds that 50.5% of respondents believe that Internet banking is not secure enough for their data and money; however, 28.5% of respondents disagree with that, and they believe their money and personal data are protected; however, 21% of respondents were not sure about whether their personal data and money safe in the Internet banking system or not.

Figure 4.1.2 (18): Security of Internet Banking. (Source: Own survey)

Intention to Recommend:

If customers are happy with the Internet banking service, they will recommend it to their parents and family, which will maximise the adoption of Internet banking. However, this still finds that 47.5% of respondents want to recommend their friends and family to adopt Internet banking services, and 20.5% of respondents did not agree to recommend it to their close circle; however, 30% of respondents were not sure about whether they will recommend their friends and family or not.

Figure 4.1.2 (19): Customers' Intention to Recommend. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Internet banking promotion through digital marketing:**

Nowadays, social media plays a vital role in promoting Internet banking worldwide. However, it's the banks' task to take the initiative to spread the message and raise awareness among customers through social media about the benefits of having Internet banking. However, only 25% of respondents out of 200 believe that the media is full of reports, articles and news that suggest Internet banking. 48.5% of respondents believe that the promotion of adopting Internet banking is not available enough in the media. However, 26.5% of respondents were not sure about these promotional activities over media.

Figure 4.1.2 (20): Media Presence of Internet Banking. (Source: Own survey)

❖ **Banks' initiative to promote Internet banking:**

Banks' policy and intention to promote Internet banking determine the speed of adoption of Internet banking. It's the banks' responsibility to raise awareness among the population, encourage people and provide training for their customers to adopt Internet banking. This study finds that 52% of respondents believe banks do not frequently inform, encourage, and provide the necessary training for their customers to use Internet banking. However, 26% of respondents believe banks are doing enough to encourage and inform and provide training to their customers, and 22% of respondents said they were not sure about banks' initiatives in promoting Internet banking.

Figure 4.1.2 (21): Banks Initiative for Internet Banking Promotion. (Source: Own survey)

4.2.0 Analysis and Findings of Interviews:

4.2.1 Introduction:

This section (*Chapter 4*) highlights the interpretation of interview-based qualitative responses of bank employees on the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the Khulna region in Bangladesh. A total of 14 themes (reflecting five categories of innovation resistance factors adopted for this study from Innovation Resistance Theory) have emerged from the qualitative data analysis for this study in accordance with the literature review and which significantly illustrates the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. The identified themes and patterns in this study significantly enrich the quality of the study and describe how the cultural factors and local perceptions shape the customers' decision on Internet banking adoption and the role of infrastructure in the uptake of the Internet banking adoption process within the innovation resistance theory framework.

4.2.2 Findings of Thematic Analysis:

Thematic Analysis: Major Themes and Codes				
Category	Themes		Codes	
Usage Barrier	Complexity		Poor English Literacy and Service Interface	
			Hard To Set Up Bank Apps	
			Inconvenient Banking Process	
	Poor Customer Service			Customer Satisfaction
				Face-To-Face Service
				Limited Online Service
				Online Customer Service
				Service Through Apps
	Lack Of Digital Access & Financial Literacy			Illiteracy
				Lack Of Access To E-Device
				New In Internet Service

		Unable To Use E-Devices	
	Segregation Of Mobile Financial Service	Mobile Financial Service	
		Poor Internet Infrastructure	
		Problem With Access Bank Website	
		Service Limitation	
Value Barrier	Slow Internet Speed and Cost	Cost Of Internet Free Internet Connection Slow Internet Speed	
	Usefulness	COVID-19 Customer Satisfaction Negative Perception Lack Of Awareness	
	Service Charge	High Bank Charge Usefulness	
Risk Barrier	Financial Risk	Financial Loss Fraud Lack Of Digital Protection Measures Against Hacking	
	Performance Risk	Lack Of Trust	
	Physical Risk	Customers Responsibility Customers' Trust	
Traditional Barrier	Cash Dependency	Money Transferring App Mobile Financial System Use Of Cash	
	Lack Of Customer Banker Relationship	Preference For Branch Banking	
	Religious Restrictions	Interest And Religious Constraints Zero Balance Account	

Image Barrier	Banks' Bad Reputation		Negative History of Bank	
Demographic Factor	Age			
	Education			
	Location			
	Employment			
Table- 4.2.2: Thematic Analysis				

4.2.3 Major Themes Reflecting Usage Barrier of Internet Banking Adoption:

4.2.3.1 Main Theme 1: Complexity

Nothing has reshaped the banking industry more than information technology and its rapid development in the last few decades. IT technology has enabled banks to develop new and complex products, establish faster communication within and across banks, and facilitate easy access to bank customers through Internet and mobile communications channels. In this transition from a rigid and orthodox banking structure to a complex, quickly evolving, and interconnected banking industry, banks have already gone too far in developing exclusively complex products and banking processes in the process of boosting product variation, customisation, and diversifications to lower the risk from borrowers, regulators, credit rating agencies and other capital market participants. Therefore, customers face complexity according to their merit in different countries, but this complexity is severe to the majority of the people in developing countries like Bangladesh, where Internet banking is a comparatively new concept to most of customers. The following section illustrates the findings from the interview of bank employees regarding the associated complexity of the Internet banking adoption process and how customers perceived it:

- **Poor English Literacy:**

Poor English literacy refers to people's incompetency and the lack of comprehensiveness of the English language that restricts their ability to read, write, speak, and operate any instruments

with an English interface. Poor English literacy affects people to adjust to their social circle openly. Due to the modernisation of our society, English is the common language for communication mediums both in English-speaking countries as well as the non-English speaking countries. Although English is the second official language in Bangladesh, most people are not competent enough to operate Internet banking in English. Therefore, people always perceive the psychological scarcity of Internet banking. Although there are many learning materials available online, mostly in English, customers cannot access those learning materials to know about Internet banking and how to operate Internet banking in general. For example, a bank manager (S.I) shared his experience with customers who are interested in Internet banking, but due to a lack of English competency, customers are unable to comprehend the basic functions of Internet banking: *"Bangladeshi people are not too much literate in English. Most of the Customers do not know how to operate Internet banking apps and how to conduct Internet banking overall, especially in English"*.

Although few banks have addressed this issue, they recently introduced Internet banking apps. According to the bank manager (EM), *"Because as you know, besides the English version, the Bangla version is also provided to the customers as most of the people who do not know English very well. That's why they can operate the mobile banking apps in Bangla. Also, our Internet banking app or digital banking services are very easy to understand."*

However, despite a few banks providing Internet banking services in the Bengali interface, many people who lack English competency also struggle to conduct Internet banking with the Bangla interface. That is probably because of their lack of technical knowledge as well as little grasp of Internet banking procedures. The bank manager (T.S) Commented on this point: *"We do have a Bangla interface as well. We do have English and Bangla both, but the fact is people are not that much knowledgeable about procedures overall, and they don't know how to use the Bangla interface as well. They don't even know how to use that manual interface of banking due to their dependency on their local bank branch. And I think besides Bengali interface, I mean, Bangla interface, we have to improve our technology which is also very is also important."* ___ **Bank Manager (T.S)**

- ***Hard to Set up Banking Apps:***

The first step of using Internet banking is to set up banking apps. As Customers have more

access to a mobile phone than a computer PC Or laptop, the use of the phone to conduct Internet banking is more popular and common in Bangladesh. However, customers first need to download their respective mobile apps from their mobile platforms, which is either the Android or IOS platform. After downloading their mobile banking apps, they need to complete the initial online registration using bank-provided credentials. They also need to set up their PIN or password and memorable words for the future in case they need to reset their password if they forget it. However, the whole process may be very complex and uncomfortable to most of the customers who are not comparatively sound in using technology or mobile apps. Additionally, some banks require additional verification and authentication procedures for the safety of customers' bank accounts, which makes it more complex for customers with little education and poor digital and financial literacy in rural areas to set up their banking apps. The bank manager (T.S) addressed this issue as follows:

"Customers feel stressed about using Internet banking because most of our bank customers are not well experienced about Internet and apps. As they have to download Internet banking apps in order to conduct banking activities, customers find it very hard to set up banking apps most of the time. They actually disturb us about our Internet banking because they couldn't use the app". – T.S (Bank Manager).

- **Inconvenient Banking Process:**

The convenient banking process is the fundamental requirement to bring customers under the umbrella of the online banking system. The purpose of Internet banking is to make the banking experience a convenient, easy, and time-saving process that should allow customers to conduct their banking activities swiftly from the comfort of their homes without having further concerns and worries. However, Internet banking service in Bangladesh is still in the early stage, which often comes with inconvenient banking experiences for the consumers. Customers often face problems accessing their respective banking portals due to having a poorly configured electronic device that is not compatible with banks' web portal and their mobile apps. It is a very common issue for customers to have difficulties making online payments during their online shopping as they are often unable to process the transactions. The reason behind these issues is a combination of complex mobile banking apps and payment procedures as well as customers' incompatibility with Internet banking overall. One of the respondents of the

interview addressed this issue in his own words:

"The banking process is not convenient through the Internet banking and Internet banking infrastructure is not well developed, customers find the system very complicated because they have some problems especially, they don't have a well-configured mobile phone that is compatible with banks app, and it's a real problem to access the bank website as well. Also, sometimes they cannot connect with the bank's web portal. Sometimes our server also shows some problems." _E.M (Bank Manager).

Another bank manager (T.S) addressed the same issue in her own words:

"Customers are using the Internet banking service mostly for transactions and shopping. They try to pay online, and most of the time, I mean, basically because of security reasons, they have to follow through with some PIN and questions and passwords to make payments to shopping portals. Most of the time, customers don't remember their PINs and passwords. Most of the time, they provide the wrong information. Their account gets blocked very easily. And as usual, because of security reasons, if they do anything wrong in their transaction process, we obviously close the account temporarily. So, this sort of problem we regularly face. I think the main reason because the customers are not that much familiar with Internet banking till now. But yes, we are working on to make Internet banking process as convenient and smooth as possible." - T.S (Bank Manager).

However, the complexity of Internet banking appears differently in the different age groups. However, younger generations are more exposed to the new technology that enables them to handle complexity with more ease. On the contrary, older generations, as well as rural people comparatively more incompetent to deal with technological complexity and resolve any technical issues during the Internet banking process, such as resetting the password or PIN. One of the bank managers addressed this issue in his own words as follows: -

"Actually, the middle-aged people they are not. They don't find it so convenient because they don't know how to use a smartphone. That's why they don't find it convenient, but people who are whose age is like 20 to 30 years. They are very convenient in using mobile banking apps." _E.M (Bank Manager)

4.2.3.2 Main Theme 2: Poor Customer Service

Customer service is the key element of providing outstanding banking services to customers that ensure maximum customer retention and the highest level of customer satisfaction. However, poor customer service consists of a lack of assistance and empathy from the service provider to resolve any technical issues and conflicts faced by customers during their banking activities. Although most banks have online customer service hotlines that allow customers to contact their respective bank's customer service portal to solve problems due to the quality of customer service provided by the banks and customers' inability to play their part from the other side of the phone to solve the problem such as inability to follow the step-by-step instructions provided by the customer service assistant force customers to visit their physical bank branch to get help from the bank employees. This issue was addressed by one of the bank managers in the interview. In her own words: *"We do provide two types of customer service; one is face to face and another online. They can directly come to our office and talk to us. I personally handle quite a few customers every day. Also, we do provide a 24/7 customer service phone. I mean they can call our number of staff, and they can complain, or they can ask about their questions or their inquiries by phone. Our customer service providers do their level best to help them out. Definitely, if they can't, if they are not able to solve the problem, then they transfer the customers to the office and then we do solve the problem. But most of the time, the customers manage to get help But as I said, if they are not able to solve their problems and if higher authorisation is required, then, in that case, they have to come to the office for further solutions."* – TS

However, having a customer service hotline and providing customer service is totally different from ensuring effective problem and conflict resolution that assures the highest degree of customer satisfaction. One of the bank managers acknowledged this issue during the interview: *"Customer service is also not effective in Khulna. Most people complain that they don't get a proper solution for their complaints. So first of all, Customers are not used to the functions of Internet banking, and when they ask for customer service, Customer service is not able to advise properly"* – SU

Therefore, this inability to resolve the issues over the phone by customer service leads customers to visit the bank branch, ultimately diminishing the purpose of having Internet banking which is supposed to make customers' banking experience swift and easier from a distance without needing to visit their bank branch. This problem is highlighted in the statement of one of the interviewees. He stated: *"Customer service, basically we provide the customer service from a bank branch and 90% customers, they come to our office, and they take their*

service from our front desk, and we have a helpline, also, helpline number and some customers they use the Internet and some apps." – SI

Despite having a number of banks in Bangladesh, customer service improvement is well below the satisfactory level to ensure seamless and effective Internet banking surveys all over the country. In this regard, private banks are comparatively well ahead of government-owned banks in shooting and providing effective customer service. One of the senior bank managers expressed his opinions in the interview to address the quality of customer service provided by different banks in Bangladesh. In his own words:

"So if I talk about this, the Internet-based services are not available to customers from all the banks. You will already know that there are too many banks in our country, but the services of the banks or most of the banks are not on the top line. The private banks and the multinational banks that are operating in our country or providing the services and Internet services efficiently, but most of their government's banks, Sonali banks, Janata banks and Agrani banks are not even 10 or 20% in the process of providing the Internet banking services that are available to the customers. So that's lacking in our banking sector right now. Apart from that, roughly ten banks effectively operate Internet banking and other online services. But most of the other banks are new and not that technologically advanced and yet to provide services to customers from all over the country. But a few banks like Citibank, HSBC, Standard Chartered Bank, they're doing good work on Internet banking, but all other banks are not doing the same."
_ Su.

4.2.3.3 Main Theme 3: Lack of Digital Access & Digital and Financial Literacy:

Digital access refers to potential customers' ownership of a suitable electronic device to conduct Internet banking, and digital literacy refers to customers' ability and knowledge to navigate the electronic device and perform Internet banking activities successfully through the electronic device. Additionally, financial literacy refers to customers' overall knowledge of banking procedures to conduct Internet banking. This financial literacy and digital literacy depend on the customers' age, location, income and education. As the potential users of Internet banking are expected to be financially literate and capable of accessing and navigating digital devices, understanding customers' capability is the fundamental component of resolving the problems in promoting Internet banking adoption. one of the bank managers illustrated his experience:

"First of all, the people in Khulna, they're not used to the technology. They're struggling with technology, and they're not used to online banking. They're also not technologically literate, so they struggle to use the Internet. And also, they don't have enough digital literacy. That's another problem." _ Sa.U.

Local culture is another key factor that determines the level of customers' digital access and digital literacy and their perception of adopting new technology. Bank manager TS addressed this issue in the interview: *"Culturally, any new technology is not that easily adopted by the Bengali people, especially in Khulna, especially in rural areas. So yes, these cultures are really affecting" _ TS.*

Apart from the local cultural influence on digital access and digital literacy, customers' age is another important factor. Comparatively, younger generations have more access to digital technology and hold significant knowledge about it. Although the younger generation is more knowledgeable about digital literacy, their involvement in financial activities is lower than the older generation, who are more in need of Internet banking access. Therefore, despite having a necessity and interest in Internet banking, the older generation is unable to get the benefit of having Internet banking.

"Actually, you know that people are not literate about computers or mobile banking apps. People like younger generations are literate about mobile banking apps or computers, and they know how to operate them, but a majority of the people who are businessmen they're not our age and do not have financial and digital literacy. You know about that. That's the problem, the main problem. I think the main thing is that customers do not have digital and financial literacy, as they do not know how to use a computer or mobile apps and how to conduct banking overall." _ E.m

The location of customers is another important key factor for having a lack of financial and digital literacy. People in rural areas are less exposed to the new digital innovation, especially in the case of Internet banking. On the other hand, their dependency on the traditional banking system made them comfortable with over-the-desk banking, where they totally depend on the bank employees without having financial knowledge to conduct banking. So, when it comes to Internet banking, most of the customers in rural areas are unable to perform Internet banking

activities despite having access to digital excess in some cases. Bank manager 'Su' illustrated the rural scenario from her experience:

"I think the most necessary things to do to make the Internet banking services more usable to the customer because they don't have the literacy among most of the people in the village. You already know that fewer people in our country are living in the capital city who have most Internet banking access, but most of the people residing in other areas of our country with limited access. So, they are not definitely under the services that have been provided, they are not that much literate, and they are not coming under the services of the banking industry. So, I think financial literacy can play a role, and if they can be literate, then the services will be more effective they will. They will be more inclined to adopt the services from the banks and financial industry, and we have a lot to do in that respect. There's hardly any such conduct in the banking industry yet in our country." __ Su.

4.2.3.4 Main Theme 4: Segregation of Mobile Financial Service:

With the rapid inclusion of fintech innovation technological development and the gradual increase of mobile subscriptions and Internet users, mobile financial services have gained popularity in recent years in transferring money, conducting online shopping, university registrations, paying wages to workers and so on. However, only 15 banks in Bangladesh are providing mobile financial services, with 1.03 million agents countrywide. However, in spite of having massive popularity among ordinary people both in rural and city areas, most banks are not integrated with mobile financial services. As a result, customers are unable to connect their bank account to the mobile financial service to contact their banking activities. Bank manager EM addressed this issue in the interview as follows:

"Many Mobile banking financial services are getting popular in Bangladesh, and all of them are not connected with all the banks. That's why some customers face problems connecting their bank account to their mobile banking financial account, as their banking system is not integrated with that mobile banking financial service app. And ultimately, customers can't transfer money from the bank account to the mobile banking financial service." __ E.m

Despite not being integrated with many banks, customers are still experiencing difficulties connecting with the servers of the banks which are offering mobile financial services. Complaints from customers regarding this matter are very common among bank employees and bank managers. One of the bank managers acknowledged this lack in the interview as follows:

"Banking infrastructure is not well developed, and customers find the system very complicated because they have some problems especially, sometimes they cannot connect with the bank Internet system. Sometimes our server also shows some problems and so on" __SI

"And there are also some lacking from the banks' sides in terms of the technological advancement. Some of the banks are providing mobile financial services available to all customers, but most of the banks are yet to make a good amount of progress. Especially those banks who are new and not that technologically advanced " __Su.

4.2.4.0 Major Themes Reflecting Value Barrier of Internet Banking Adoption:

4.2.4.1 Main Theme 1: Usefulness

The usefulness of innovation refers to the degree of belief where customers expect that it will maximise their working performance. However, the usefulness of Internet banking refers to consumers' perception of the degree of benefits that it provides in their daily lives. One of the first conditions of Internet banking adoption is that potential customers must believe that Internet banking provides greater facilities and opportunities with greater ease that is ultimately very useful in their daily financial activities. Customers who resist adopting Internet banking perceive less value in it. So it is an important factor to highlight the importance of Internet banking and its usefulness to the customers. The bank manager (S.I) emphasised the benefits of having Internet banking in his own words: *"Internet banking, first of all, it's digital money, there is no connection with cash, Customers can send their money by using apps or bank website one account to another account, it saves their time, and there is no hassle of counting cash or fake money." _ SI*

However, dependency on traditional branch banking comes with a greater burden. Due to the closure of banks at the weekends, people cannot conduct their banking activities despite their necessity and urgency. Therefore, it is noticeable that people are relying on mobile financial

services provided by different financial companies. Bank manager EM highlighted this issue as follows:

"Internet banking can be very useful to them because you know, there are two holidays in the banking system in Bangladesh, Friday, and Saturday, but it's almost 48 hours, but in these 48 hours, the businessman or you know, people can't do any kind of financial transaction physically in bank premises. So as an alternative, they can use Internet banking apps. That's why these this kind of apps or Internet banking facilities are of too much use to them. That's why bankers and customers both are getting interested in Internet banking services, and they provide 24/7 financial banking services even in the holidays." _EM

Internet banking not only provides greater ease to customers' banking experience but also reduces the workload from banks. With traditional branch banking, bank employees have to face massive work pressure from customers visiting the bank's branch. Additionally, this is not a good sustainable way of banking in the current COVID-19 pandemic as well as the upcoming one. Bank manager SI expressed his expectations in the interview regarding the benefits of Internet banking as follows:

"So if most of the customer is used to Internet Banking, so we are happy because we will not have most of the pressure in our branches. Just think, if every day 500 customers come to our branches and we give them the services. However, among these customers, if 200 customers are using Internet banking apps at their home, So we can get less pressure from work through the customers." _SI

Due to the massive dependency on the traditional banking system, COVID-19 caused greater difficulties to customers during the pandemic due to the closure of bank branches for the sake of public health safety under the Bangladeshi government guidelines. Most of the banks were closed or operated with very limited services that provided massive inconvenience along with understanding the importance of having Internet banking. People who had Internet banking enjoyed the massive facilities of Internet banking during the pandemic without risking their lives to visit the bank branch. Bank manager SI shared his experience of the COVID-19 lockdown in the interview:

"Obviously, during the COVID-19, we have rostering systems (three days banking week with limited working hours per employee). But our server is always open 24/7. So, customers can

use their app through the Internet to do their banking, so it is good if they use their Internet banking as they do not need to go to the bank or come out of their homes as it is also less risky of being affected by COVID-19 and we also provide them information about the using of the Internet and the good sides of Internet Banking." _ SI

4.2.4.2 Main Theme 2: Slow Internet Speed and Cost:

Internet connection is a vital element of Internet banking, and the speed of the Internet and associated cost determines consumer satisfaction and their value to money. Although Bangladesh has recently entered 5G Internet connection and the 4G Network is well known to the people, there are still massive drawbacks regarding the Internet speed and the network issues. In terms of the cost of the Internet, the Internet connection cost is comparatively lower than last few years. Additionally, some banks are offering Internet connections to the customers to use the bank apps without having the need to connect with their Internet data which is pretty limited in numbers. However, the majority of people are facing problems due to the slow speed of the Internet. *"Actually, the most common problem they face sometimes, you know, in rural areas is that the Internet speed is not so good". _ EM.*

Banks are well aware of this problem as most bank managers and employees are the primary point of complaint for the customers. As bank branches are the primary places to motivate customers to use Internet banking, bank branches are also the first place where customers provide their feedback and complaints regarding their user experience. Bank manager TS shared her experience from her interaction with the customers regarding these issues:

"Customers face some problems which I receive complaints quite often, especially regarding Internet Banking. So, I think that Internet banking is basically based on online, and they require a good speed of Internet. So, the first problem they basically suffer is slow Internet speed. Internet connection is a big deal. Because, you know, the Internet connection we have right now is not that super-fast. It doesn't really comply with Internet Banking. I mean that much it does, but I would say it's not sufficient" _ TS

Despite having slow speeds, the familiarity of the Internet is increasing day by day in rural areas. People are using Facebook; even some farmers use the Internet to solve their problems in their fields and paddy problems. So, the use of the Internet is quite common in Khulna, but

because of the slow speed of Internet connection and high level of work, for example, Internet banking or Internet transactions are not really getting that much familiarisation because of this speed problem. However, the speed of the Internet in cities is much better than the rural areas, although occasional total shutdown is not uncommon.

"Especially in rural areas, speed is very low, but in City areas, the speed is okay to use Internet banking. In Khulna city, most of the places Internet speed is okay except sometimes the Internet service gets shut down completely" _Pro

So, compared to the Internet bill or Internet charges in other in the world, India and Bangladesh have very low charges because of having broadband lines in different areas. Many phone networks like Grameenphone, Airtel etc., provide Internet service. Internet cost is comparatively lower than before, but the Internet speed is still very slow in most areas of Bangladesh. To comment on Internet speed and cost, bank manager TS said:

"If you compare the charges, the service they provide is not that expensive. I think that's why they are not providing enough speed as well. I mean proper services because the Internet is not expensive and probably that's why the speed is not also that good" __TS

Compared with the usefulness of Internet banking, Internet banking is good for customers, but it can be costly for some customers, first of all. To use Internet Banking, obviously, customers need a well-configured mobile phone or computer or tablet, which is also costly in addition to the cost of the Internet, and the speed of the Internet is very slow. To explain how customers see the cost of Internet and Internet banking compared to the values provided, bank manager SI said: *"If I compare with the cost of Internet and the value Internet banking provides and the customer also unsatisfied about our banking experience, to be honest customer don't find value in using Internet banking as well." __SI*

4.2.5.0 Major Themes Reflecting Risk Barrier of Internet Banking Adoption:

4.2.5.1 Main Theme 1: Financial Loss

Any innovation in the marketplace comes with the inherited possible risk of financial loss. The risk of financial loss is much higher in developing nations than in developed countries. In the case of Internet banking in developing countries like Bangladesh, customers are always sceptical about their financial safety in Internet banking activities due to the omission of physical interaction between customers and bank employees. Customers are always fearful of making any sort of transition over the Internet. Bank manager Sa. U commented on this matter as:

"Customers think that it can be a risk because if they make any mistakes, the money will go to a different account. And of course, they're scared if they will get the money back or not." __ Sa.U.

This lack of trust and scarcity makes customers sceptical about using Internet banking. Customers need to provide basic personal information to conduct Internet banking, and they are always fearful that this information can be stolen by hackers to steal their money from their accounts and other fraudulent activities. Bank managers are very much familiar with this kind of opinion from the customers due to their day-to-day interaction with them. The bank manager shared his customers' perceptions in the interview as follows:

"Customers believe, some hackers can transfer their money from their own account to another account through the Internet because before using Internet customer have to provide their personal data to create Internet banking account" __ SI.

Although in most cases, customers' fear of losing money or their identity theft is over-exaggerated undoubtedly, there is a significant matter of concern regarding the security of Internet banking in Bangladesh. Recent history of this kind of incident fuelling the customers' doubt about Internet banking Which is a major issue in the development of Internet banking adoption. Although different banks deal with security issues differently, customers' concerns regarding the safety of their money have appeared to be similar for most banks. Another bank

manager (Pro.) Expressed her understanding of this matter from the customers' perspective as follows: *"Internet banking is useful, but there are some drawbacks, especially that security issue is a big drawback here. I think people don't feel it. Don't take it as a secure way of making transactions. I think this is because of hacking and fraudulent activities that happened recent banking history of Bangladesh. People mostly believe in traditional banking, and as Internet banking is new, so mostly they're not interested. They're afraid that they'll not be given back their money"* Pro.

One of the main reasons for fraud is that most Bangladeshi people are not highly educated or technologically sound. Or they are used to using the traditional banking system and always have a scarcity of using something new technology regarding their money, especially Internet banking. Even though some people have adopted Internet banking despite a lack of technical knowledge and awareness of fraudulent activities, some people often become the victim of fraud. Therefore, any fraud incidents rapidly spread the scarcity among the close circle of the victim. Bank manager SI Highlighted the factor of fraud in his own words:

"Basically, Internet banking is a digital wave for banking systems but honestly speaking; now we can't appreciate the customers using Internet banking because they are facing some scams. Also, mobile scam is a common matter, and we have lots of hackers inside our country outside our country. So, some customers are not able to use Internet banking properly, and in some cases, they share their passwords with another person online. So, this type of complaint we received frequently. As a result, Customers feel danger and risk of using Internet banking and share with us so those types of problems we face and we actually forbidding them to use Internet banking if they are not able to use the Internet banking safely" . __S.I

Although fraud is a massive risk factor for the financial industry and banks, Every bank has its own protection shield to prevent fraud. However, internal and external fraudsters and corruption cause tough fraudulent incidents to detect early for banks. However, most banks prioritise customers' interests and safety first during and after launching any online banking product. Although banks try to establish the safest safety net for protecting customers' interests, it is also the customers' responsibility to ensure the highest protection from their end. Customers' negligence and lack of knowledge in this regard are still a massive problem in preventing fraud. The bank manager is SU Pointed out customers' collective responsibility to protect their bank account and money in the interview as follows: *"I think on the other side,*

customers face the risk of fraud because they don't use essential protection frequently, and they actually don't have the idea of protection that they need to follow and use. So, I think these protection mechanisms are also needed to get better with a new type of fraud that is coming out." __SU.

However, in the matter of financial loss of customers, getting a refund is a significant factor for the customers as well as sharing the responsibility. Fraud can happen due to the lack of technological protection from the bank side as well as negligence and lack of awareness from the customer side. However, It is controversial which party is responsible for the fraud, but it is always the customer who loses the money. Bank manager TS described her opinion on this matter in her own words:

"Well, firstly, the level of security we do provide, we always make sure that customers do not lose their money. Now, if, hypothetically, the customer loses their money, there will be an inquiry on it. If the money is lost because of the customer's fault, there will be no refund because if the customer follows some link that he/she is not supposed to follow, which is not directly sent by the bank, or if the customer opens a message or an email, which normally goes to their spam, and they give their personal information even using our name. That's literally the customer's own fault. But if based on our inquiry, it comes up that something that we are not able to provide, I mean, because of our lack of security reason customers have lost their money. We always provide the full refund."- TS.

However, most of the banks in Bangladesh ensure the recovery of customers' money in case of a wrong transfer to the wrong account. This kind of problem is not unusual in the financial industry, but the customers can complain to their respective banks, and most of the banks look into the matter as soon as possible to give the customers a full refund or recovery of their money within three working days if the customer's complaint found to be true. Bank Manager SI explained the process taken by his banks in this situation as follows:

"We have some rules officially. We take some steps through the mother bank, you know, Bangladesh Bank is our mother bank, we can complain there, and Bangladesh Bank will take the necessary steps to remove or recover their problem, and we send back the money at the end".

However, he addressed his bank's policy of charging any amount for the recovery of lost money and the investigation process: *"It depends on the actual amount and the cost as well. And how did they lose their money? Basically, we are very conscious of Internet banking safety. Our server also is strict and secure. But sometimes customers face this problem, and it's a long process also. And we think about the amount, and how much money the bank has spent as cost, then we take some charges as well. Not the full or half. It has some percentage"* . __S.I

4.2.5.2 Main Theme 2: Performance Risk

Performance risk in Internet banking refers to consumer perception of Internet banking not performing properly compared to traditional banking. Customers' negative experience of using Internet banking causes the performance risk that ultimately deters customers from using Internet banking channels. Customers' negative experiences of using Internet banking may arise for different reasons. That could be customers' poorly configured mobile or electronic devices, slow Internet connections or banks' technical problems. Sometimes this problem acts as individually or collectively, which causes customers dissatisfaction with the service. Among all the causes, slow Internet is the main barrier to conducting Internet banking activities swiftly. Customers always compare the service of Internet banking to traditional banking. According to the customers' perceptions, they need to buy electronic devices and Internet data connections to conduct Internet banking; however, they do not need these kinds of devices or connections in traditional banking. Bank manager Sa.U expressed the customer's opinion on this matter as follows:

"Firstly, the Internet in Bangladesh is very slow and expensive to many customers. So, most of the customers' thinking is that they're wasting money and they cannot use the proper service because the Internet is very slow. And it's very hard to use the apps." _Sa.U

In addition to that, customers are directly engaged in banking activities in Internet banking, unlike traditional banking. Therefore, the margin of error is higher in Internet banking due to the omission of direct assistance from bank employees. However, customers always blame Internet banking for any error, and this can be overwhelming for them to continue to use Internet banking due to the distress caused by overall negative experiences as the margin of error is higher in Internet banking, the request for a refund is typically higher as well. but the

slow refund process makes customers frustrated. *"Banks do the refund, but the process is difficult and slow. Banks need to do a lot of investigations, and it's not like very developed technology. So it takes a lot of time, and the customer gets frustrated"* _Sa.U

4.2.5.3 Main Theme 3: Physical Risk

Physical risk refers to the harm possessed by the innovation to the person or property; therefore, customers show resistance to the innovation due to its effect on them. As most of the people in Bangladesh are not used to the use of technology in their daily life, the customers feel anxiety and stress before using any new technological device which caused them technostress.

"The first is not stressed; they become very tense. Okay. So, the first problem, I mean, problem or the complication they face they always feel like 'oh my god, I'm going to lose my money all my personal details might have been taken by someone else. I'm going to lose my money because of Internet banking; lots of hacking is going on. So, if they are not able to make the transaction right away, they feel like oh my god, I have lost my money, but they don't understand in terms of Internet banking; it takes some time to move the money from your account. The customer gets really stressed even if, after 10 minutes, the money is not in their account; they will keep calling the bank. yeah, this sort of stress demonstrates they feel" __ TS

However, customers with different age groups feel the stress differently. Especially younger generations are more familiar with new technology, and they have more digital literacy. Due to the common use of social media and different mobile apps, the young generation is much more familiar with digital knowledge that assists them in using Internet banking comfortably. However, those who don't have enough digital literacy and the higher age group are more reluctant and less capable of using Internet banking. Bank manager SU explained her observation in the interview on this matter as follows: *"The young people, they don't face any kind of stress or any kind of complexity using mobile banking apps. But the people who are not much literate about computer or mobile or our digital interface, the first time face some kind of problems like different anxious like they become really nervous about using something new."*

However, education is an important factor against technostress. Educated people face complexity and stress initially, but they are much more capable of understanding the concept of using Internet banking very quickly. Although educated people face difficulties when they

first use Internet banking, once they get used to using it, they don't find any difficulties or stress to deal with any inconvenience.

"Whenever customers install apps related to Internet banking, want to transfer money somewhere or make a transaction or buy something online, and then they feel anxious when they used it for the first time. But the other persons who are maybe familiar with using similar apps or who are more educated, for them that stress is lower, I think. Even though if they stressed, after using one or two or three times it automatically gets in the habit of using." _Pro

4.2.6.0 Major Themes Reflecting Traditional Barriers of Internet Banking Adoption:

4.2.6.1 Main Theme 1: Cash Dependency

Cash dependency refers to heavy dependence on cash use. A country is called a cash-dependent society if the country of this society uses cash for 70% of total transactions. Bangladesh is traditionally a cash-dependent society where most people prefer cash for their daily transactions. Although Internet banking is a new concept to Bangladeshi customers, many people are still adopting it, but unfortunately, that option process is slow. Many reasons are working collectively behind this cash dependency, and one of them is education. Bank manager Sa.U commented on this matter as follows: *"Normally the tradition in Bangladesh to carry cash and they are used to it. So, people don't want to change themselves. Most people don't want to give up this tradition. Also, most of the people are not highly educated, so they are not ready to take the new technology as they are used to with cash handling"* __ Sa.U

Apart from tradition and education, workplace policies and social structure are also responsible for the cash dependency in Bangladesh. Most of the high-level office jobs require a higher educational degree where their monthly salary comes through bank transport. On the contrary, most of the people in Bangladesh are either day labourers or associated with small and medium-level businesses where the payment method of salary is cash. Therefore, being associated with Internet banking is not convenient for them. Bank manager TS highlighted this problem in her own words in the interview as follows:

"Well, traditionally definitely, Bangladeshi people prefer cash. Also, in Khulna, most of the people, I mean, around 60% people are day labourers or farmers or doing some sort of other non-official jobs. In terms of non-official jobs, most of the payments are made in cash. So, coming to the bank then, depositing their cash and then using it by Internet banking, they always find it a hassle. So, they're getting the money by cash, and they're spending the money by cash. So, in terms of tradition, in terms of culture, definitely cash payment or cash transaction is much more familiar or comfortable to the people." __ T.S

Despite having all those factors behind cash dependency, shifting towards Internet banking has started. Adopting new services takes time which is not only in Bangladesh but also in any other country; if any services are offline or any services physical and then getting online afterwards, people need time to get adapted to that technology. People were more involved in having cash or transferring money hand to hand a few years ago, but now they're getting used to more and more financial services and money transfer apps like bkaash and other bank transfers. The habit needs time to change, but they're changing with time and technology. Everyone also tries to make their life easier. Therefore, the bkaash and Nogod are growing very fast in Bangladesh. The important thing is mobile banking financial systems like bkaash and Nogod; are being linked with other private and public banks. As a result, people are being so confident with this mobile banking financial services app. Bank manager SU emphasised these positive changes in her own words:

"Applying new things always comes with inertia. After breaking the inertia or after overcoming the inertia, people get used to it, but at first, they're having their earlier habits like all other habits that they have. The use of some mobile financial services is increasing here. So the changing of their habits already started." __SU.

Although people are using mobile financial services frequently nowadays and the new generation is very much interested in using mobile banking or Internet banking systems or QR Code Systems, still it has massive drawbacks. Some of the banks are connected with mobile financial services that allow the customer to transfer and monitor the account or other people's accounts. However, it is mostly used to transfer money and withdraw cash from the local agent's office.

"Most of the people in Bangladesh are very much familiar with bkaash, Nogod and other mobile financial services that allow customers to send money instantly from their account to another account. But in case of big payments, people still prefer cash, but in case of day-to-day activities, they prefer mobile banking financial service" __EM

4.2.6.2 Main Theme 2: Lack of Customer Banker Relationship

The traditional banking system in Bangladesh created is strong customer-banker relationship. People are more relaxed when did discuss their financial issues with bank employees. They

feel more satisfaction in visiting the bank branch than getting service online or getting solutions from customer service over the phone. So, visiting their bank branch for any financial activities and getting any sort of suggestion from the mouth of bank manager keeps them confident and satisfied. *"People prefer to get the information from someone professional from a bank physically. That's why they prefer to come to the bank and talk to the manager rather than reading something on the Internet or getting customer service over the phone. We do have all the information on our website, but they prefer to visit the bank rather than read it online. They prefer to talk to someone from the bank face to face and ask their query. So, branch banking is much more popular than Internet Banking" .__T.S*

4.2.6.3 Main Theme 3: Religious Restrictions

Religious restrictions play a vital role in the Bangladeshi perspective. Most of the people in Bangladesh are Muslims, and in the Muslim religion, any financial activities associated with interest are forbidden. Therefore, a significant percentage of people believe that traditional banking structures are not suitable for religious belief and therefore try to avoid it. Most of the Muslim people who follow the religion like Islamic banks that deal with money with Sharia system, like proper Islamic system, that's why most of the people that don't want to go for other traditional banking prefer Islamic banking. However, Islamic banks are limited in numbers as well as their Internet banking services. Therefore, a large majority of people are out of the service of contemporary banking networks.

"So, most of the people of my country are Islamic-minded. They are not clear; they don't provide us with clear decisions about Internet Banking. That's because interest is not allowed in Islam. We have two banking systems in Bangladesh, one conventional banking and one Islamic banking. So, conventional banking has a fixed interest rate on deposits, FDR, DPS or savings. However, an Islamic bank has no fixed interest. And most Muslim people are used to Islamic banking in my country. Some banking services are not linked with Internet Banking, and Internet banking services are not widely available for Islamic banks. Actually, in Islamic banking, we have eight Islamic banks in Bangladesh. So basically, most of the pious people who are highly linked with Islam and religion open their accounts mainly in Islamic banks at the Islamic bank branches, and they are not interested in other traditional banking" __SI

4.2.7.0 Major Themes Reflecting Image Barrier of Internet banking Adoption:

4.2.7.1 Main Theme 1: Banks' Bad Reputation

Bank image or reputation is an important factor for building trust among customers, especially in the case of Internet banking adoption. There were a few banks that had controversies regarding not fulfilling customer satisfaction, all involving themselves in fraudulent activities. There were a few banks where customer deposited their money and didn't get that back later. So, because of this kind of previous corruption, customers have a common negative perception of all banks.

"Because there were many fraudulent activities that happened many times. There were many banks that were not scheduled by the Bangladesh bank, and they took people's money and then they just suddenly went out of business and didn't give the money back. People didn't get their money. This kind of fraudulent incident happened. Some banks have done this kind of activity to their customers." __Pro

"I think this is because of hacking and fraudulent activities that happened in the recent banking history of Bangladesh. I think bank image is a very important factor. Banks with bad history, people usually don't trust those banks. In the case of Internet banking, surely, I think bank image is very important." __Pro

However, the majority of banks have good reputations, but the corruption of other banks affects the reputation of others. People build up a generalised perception about all banks in the case of any corruption or fraudulent activities in the banking industry. Recent hacking in Bangladesh Bank, which is the central bank of the country, maximises the scarcity of customers further.

"Even though we are a reputed Bank in Bangladesh yet, because of the bad reputation of other banks also affected the reputation of our bank. But we always do provide excellent services, and we always try to make customers believe that we are reputed one. We do have a good name. We have been serving in Bangladesh for a very long time, so they can trust us. But as you have asked, do these previous corruptions and all these previous fraudulent activities affect us? Yes!!, it does affect and also it does impact customers decision-making process" __S.I

Although the image is a significant factor for customer decision-making to be associated with any bank, especially in the case of Internet banking, ensuring customer satisfaction is also equally important to attract and hold customers. Customers' long-term commitment to banks actually depends on customer satisfaction. Although each and every bank tries to provide top-notch service to their customers, banks get maximum success in customer retention when they provide top-notch services through their digital banking apps to their customers and when a customer can transfer his money in a fast way from one banking financial services to another bank. When they are satisfied, they try to get services from that respective bank.

4.2.8 Demographic Factors:

4.2.8.1 Age:

Demographical factors such as customers' age group, their education, their location and their income are significant key elements that influence other factors in the process of Internet banking adoption. The degree of acceptance of new technology varies from age group to age group. Although the younger generation has a lower income level than the older generation, they are more capable of accepting new technology whereas older generations are reluctant to adopt something new, especially on the technological side, even though they have access to more income. In addition, massive development of social media and is the ability to attract younger generations made the younger generation more aware of new technology especially Internet banking than the older generation. The bank manager addressed this issue in his own words:

"People like our generation, they are literate about mobile banking apps or computer, and they know how to operate it but a majority of the people like who are businessmen, they're not our age and do not have financial and digital literacy" __EM

Apart from digital and financial literacy as well as the awareness of Internet banking, complete ability with Internet banking is essential for customer retention. Also, in this case, young people are much more capable of dealing with any complexity or inconvenience during the use of Internet banking than older people. Bank manager SU expressed her opinions on this matter as follows:

"But people whose age is like 20 to 30 years, they are very convenient in using mobile banking apps. Actually, young people don't face any kind of stress or any kind of complexity using mobile banking apps. I think it affects the older generation. They're not used to digital devices. They are more acclimated to the traditional way, but they are learning now. They're improving. They're adapting" .__S.U

4.2.8.2 Location:

There is a massive difference between city areas and rural areas in terms of Internet connection and speed. Although most of the people live in rural areas, the Internet infrastructure is not well developed compared to the main city area.

"If I say about decisions, most of the city dwellers are good for using Internet banking but who are come from the villages and the villagers they don't know about Internet banking" __SI

Although people in rural areas are familiar with the Internet due to the massive development of social media, the interaction online is limited due to the speed of Internet connection. However, farmers are now using online tools to communicate with the relevant authorities regarding their agricultural problems under government initiatives. But this communication is always gets interrupted due to the Internet barrier.

"But if you come even to our rural areas, people are using Facebook, even our farmers they use the Internet literally to solve their problems in their fields and paddy problems and everything. So, the use of the Internet is quite common in Khulna, but because of the slow speed or the level of Internet connection, it interrupts the progress" _TS

"You already know that fewer people of our country are living in the capital city who have most Internet banking access, but most of the people residing in other areas of our country with limited access. So, they are not definitely under the services that have been provided, and they are not that much literate, and they are not coming under the services of the banking industry." _SU

4.2.8.3 Education:

Educated people are much more open to accepting something new especially new technology, to make life easier for daily activities. Education plays a significant role in the adoption of Internet banking as educated people have the ability to learn quickly as well as be able to justify the benefits that Internet banking provides. On the other hand, less educated or illiterate people are much more sceptical about adopting something new without having the ability to justify that usefulness even though they have access to money and resources.

"And our customers who are illiterate, but he has money and deposit also, they don't know about the Internet banking and that decision is we don't need Internet banking" __SI

Even though less educated or illiterate people adopt Internet banking initially, they face problems with using the service continuously due to the associated technical matters that is hard to grasp due to the lack of education, such as complexity, convenience, stress, understanding of the concept and overall, how to use it.

"Stress is also an important matter because when educated people are using it, they know that they have control over it, and they understand all the terms and conditions. But there are people who have minimal education and experience the otherwise" __S.U

Chapter 5: Discussion of Results

5.1 Introduction:

The previous chapter (*Chapter 4*) has presented the outcomes of survey analysis and the interpretation of interview-based qualitative responses of bank employees on the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the Khulna region in Bangladesh. A total of 14 themes (reflecting five categories of innovation resistance factors adopted for this study from Innovation Resistance Theory) have emerged from the qualitative data analysis for this study in accordance with the literature review and which significantly illustrates the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. The identified themes and patterns in this study significantly enrich the quality of the study and describe how the cultural factors and local perceptions shape the customers' decision on Internet banking adoption and the role of infrastructure in the uptake of the Internet banking adoption process within the innovation resistance theory framework.

This chapter presents a discussion of the key findings from the data analysis covering the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. This discussion consisted of qualitative findings, quantitative findings and some other respondents' comments and opinions based on the questions asked. This discussion chapter is structured according to the conceptual framework of this study.

The summary of the whole process and findings are highlighted in the graph below:

Table- 5.1: The Process of Results from the Findings.

The above graph shows the process of results from the findings. Initially, interviews were conducted with different bank employees from lower-middle management to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city, Bangladesh, from their perspective. Then the transcribed interviews were used to conduct a thematic analysis. Additionally, collected survey data were analysed by statistical software. The findings of the collected data were obtained through critical analysis and the utilisation of adopted theories/ models.

However, the findings of this research indicate a number of factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city which are basically covered by the core themes of research questions such as cultural factors, local perceptions and lack of infrastructures to deliver Internet banking service. However, based on the researcher’s understanding, this research is

the first in nature conducted from a Bangladeshi perspective to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking through the lens of innovation resistance theory. The conceptual framework developed for this study provides a robust view of innovation resistance factors and how these factors affect the adoption of Internet banking. As the area of this research is continuously expanding, this research contributes to knowledge by providing an understanding of how different barriers/factors affect the adoption of Internet banking in a developing country perspective.

The following section is going to discuss the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh, according to the research questions as follows:

RQ - 1: How do cultural factors and local perception negatively impact the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh?

RQ - 2. How does a lack of infrastructure impede the delivery of Internet banking services?

Research Objectives:

- 1. To understand the current situation and practice concerning Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through in-depth analysis of existing literature review, current news articles and publications from banks.*
- 2. To identify the factors hindering the adoption of Internet banking in Bangladesh through conducting a survey among customers in the Khulna region and conducting interviews with senior bank employees due to their in-depth knowledge regarding the issue.*
- 3. To understand the demographic characteristics of current users of Internet banking by conducting survey on the population. Survey results help to understand customers' behavioural traits towards Internet banking adoption based on their age, gender, profession, and disposable income.*
- 4. To understand the banks' infrastructural position and its impact on the Internet banking adoption in Bangladesh through the review of existing literature and interviewing senior bank employees. Additionally, survey responses from customers will assist in achieving this objective by highlighting the key issues regarding banking infrastructure as primarily customers are more likely to face problems through service experience.*

5. *To understand the role of customer service in the uptake of Internet banking by analysing the customers' opinions through survey responses and banks' perspectives from the interview of the senior bank employees due to their closeness with the decision-making process.*
6. *To provide recommendations based on the findings of the research for the sustainable development of Internet banking in Bangladesh.*

5.2 Impact of Cultural Factors and Local Perception on Internet Banking Adoption:

The diffusion of innovations happens through five different stages such as *knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation* (Rogers, Singhal and Quinlan, 2008, Pp. 17; Rogers, 2003). As Internet banking is a service innovation, the adoption processes of Internet banking follow the same path of diffusion process as other innovations among the adopters, such as *innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards* (Lee and Kim, 2020; Rogers, 1962). Therefore, it is apparent that the influence of cultural factors and the perception of local communities have significant negative effects on the Internet banking diffusion and adoption process of Internet banking in Khulna city. The discussions of the factors are described below:

5.2.1 Complexity Due to Lack of English Literacy (Use Barriers)

This study found that complexity is a significant factor for customers to use Internet banking conveniently and easily (Anouze, A.L.M and Alamro, A.S., 2020; Duarte et al., 2018; Safeena et al., 2012; Chong et al., 2012). Complexity is closely related to ease-of-use Internet banking. Ease of use refers to the users' perception of conducting Internet banking with minimal effort (Jebarajakirthy and Shankar, 2021). Although this complexity or 'lack of ease of use' appears in different forms to different customers (Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Hettiarachchi, 2013), however, the majority of customers experience complexity in using Internet banking due to their poor grasp of the English language. Although English is the second official language in Bangladesh,

and most people study English in their secondary and higher secondary level of education, the effective utilisation of English in Bangladeshi social life is extremely minimal. Therefore, poor comprehensiveness of the English language among mass people is a common phenomenon in Bangladesh. Hence, the poor comprehensiveness of English demotivates people from using the English interface, especially in Internet banking settings. The outcome of the survey data highlights that the majority of respondents who have secondary and higher secondary qualifications only perceived that the Bangla interface for Internet banking makes the banking experience easier. Surprisingly the respondents with bachelor's degrees hold the same perceptions as the people with the lowest qualification that they prefer the Bangla interface for conducting Internet banking over the English interface. Although people with PhD or higher qualifications are comfortable with the English interface, however, a significant percentage of respondents with master's qualifications still prefer the Bangla interface for Internet banking. So, the question is, despite having higher qualifications comparatively or those people prefer the Bangla interface? The probable answer is most of the online services have English interfaces that are mainly designed focusing on Western customers. As a result, language appears to be a great resistant factor to Internet banking adoption (Perera, 2018). Additionally, this is probably due to being older generation; older generation people are less exposed to technology, and they are not comfortable with it and this notion is consistent with (Farida, Soesatyo and Aji, 2021). The complexity due to the poor English language skills also highlighted in the conversation with bank employees. Bank employees are more knowledgeable about the customers' preference and their expertise in handling and using Internet banking. Most of the bank respondents admitted in the interview that their customers lack English expertise. Although some banks provide the opportunity to use Internet banking apps in the Bangla interface, it does not eliminate the complexity for most of the customers in regard to Internet banking use (Perera, 2018). Bank managers addressed the reason behind is that although the customers have the opportunity to use Internet banking apps with the Bangla interface, the lack of other technical knowledge in terms of using Internet banking or other technological aspects as most of the banking and technological matters and the materials are associated with the English language which deterred those people from learning from it (Kelikume, 2021). This is totally different among the younger generation as they are more conscious and aware of the latest technology due to the rapid development of education quality in Bangladesh as well as the recent development, acceptance and popularity of social media, e-commerce apps and gaming apps (Raza et al.,2017; Mehrad & Mohammadi, 2016). Therefore, early exposure to the Internet and Internet-related products regarding new

technology on any technological concept, such as Internet banking raises awareness (George, 2015) and it is driving the young generation to adopt it confidently and swiftly (Siyal et al., 2019; George, 2015).

5.2.2 Lack of Digital Access and Digital Financial Literacy (Use Barriers)

This study found that lack of digital access and lack of literacy factors are affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city. However, the severity of the lack of digital access is not as significant as the lack of financial literacy. Digital access refers to consumers' ownership of a suitable electronic device to conduct Internet banking successfully, and digital literacy refers to consumers' ability and technical knowledge to navigate the digital device effectively to perform his or her Internet banking activities successfully. Although survey data suggests that the majority of respondents use mobile devices (55% respondents out of 200) regularly compared to the laptop/desktop computer (26.5%) or tablet (18.5%), most of the customers are still struggling to use the Internet banking and this is consistent with findings of Shahin (2006) who address that despite having the need for Internet banking services, customers with a lack of information technology compatibility might find it challenging to use IT-related services and this notion is aligned with (Kelikume, 2021) that digital literacy is more effective than financial literacy. The findings of this survey regarding digital access are contrary to the findings of (Jahan et al., 2020), which was conducted under the BRAC Institute of Governance and Development (BIGD), and there is a study found that 75% of rural households have no digital access. However, this rapid improvement of digital access probably increased due to the COVID-19 lockdown in Bangladesh. as most of the traditional services are completely shattered due to the government's effort to suppress the coronavirus transmissions among the population. Therefore, there was a massive effort to divert from traditional services to make them available online resulting in a significant increase in the number of mobile phone usage. Although the digital access rate has increased, the question is whether those devices are suitable for Internet banking activities. The answer to the question found by a survey investigation where results show that most respondents mention that Internet banking apps are not suitable for their electronic devices. That is probably due to the low-quality electronic device with poor configuration, which is unsuitable for Internet banking.

However, despite the increase in digital access, digital literacy did not increase overnight. Therefore, despite the need for Internet banking and the availability of electronic devices, many

customers are unable to get the benefit of having Internet banking which is consistent with the findings of (Musa et al., 2015; Shahin, 2006). Similar to digital access, customers' age is an important factor in the digital literacy of customers, which is a significant deciding factor in customers' income level. The survey data of this study reveals that 52.8% of respondents who mentioned that their income levels between 30K to 50K are 40 plus years old, and respondents with income levels more than 50K are 40+ years old, which is 66.7% of the total respondents in that category. However, more surprising findings of this survey reveal that unemployed categories, 91.2% of respondents are below 30 years old, and the unemployment rate is extremely minimal among older generations. These findings explain that, although the younger generations are much more confident in digital literacy and have a strong grasp on it, financial activities are obviously limited due to their lower income level compared to the older generations. Although older generations have much more access to finance, and they are more in need of financial activities, however, due to their poor digital literacy, their access to the benefit of Internet banking is limited (Safari, Bisimwa and Buzera Armel, 2020). These survey findings are consistent with the statements of bank employees during the interviews. Participants commonly acknowledged that age, location, income, and the customers' education in Khulna are significant factors determining customers' poor digital literacy and customers' struggle with the technology. Additionally, the interviews further reveal that customers struggle due to digital literacy much more apparent in the rural side of Khulna city than in the urban areas (Morgan et al., 2019). This is probably due to customers' poor digital skills and digital literacy despite having higher income levels (Jahan et al., 2020; Perera, 2018).

5.2.3 Performance Risk (Risk Barriers)

The findings of this research reveal that customers' negative perceptions of the performance of Internet banking have a significant effect on the adoption of Internet banking (Martínez-Navalón, Fernández-Fernández and Alberto, 2023). Performance risk is associated with the consumers' general perception of Internet banking, whether it is good enough to meet user expectations and satisfaction (Owusu Kwateng, Osei-Wusu and Amanor, 2019; Seth, 1989). Many factors stimulate performance risk individually and collectively leaving negative perceptions among users and through negative word-of-mouth.

One of the important findings emerged from the interview where bank employees shared their experiences on this matter. The findings revealed that due to the nature of Internet banking activities, users have to make their own decisions in the banking process; therefore, many customers cannot confidently use the Internet banking service (Kaur *et al.*, 2021). Thus, their margin of error increases along with time-consuming procedures to fix the problem. Therefore, customers need to contact their customer service or visit their bank branch to mitigate these problems. Therefore, an overall unpleasant experience causes this negative word-of-mouth to influence the potential users and among the users' social circle as social influence plays a significant role in eliminating the resistance to Internet banking adoption through recommendation (Matsuo, Minami and Matsuyama, 2018).

So the negative experience makes the customer avoid internet banking Even though they cannot conduct Internet banking activities successfully. The bank employees highlighted this factor in the interview, where they mentioned that customers make error that leaves them in distress. In some cases, it's overwhelming for them to use Internet banking when they have to wait for a refund from banks. It is often time-consuming due to the necessity of investigations and the lack of developed technologies, which causes time loss for customers (Featherman and Pavlov, 2003). Another significant factor that causes performance risk is the customers' poorly configured electronic devices, which are not suitable for conducting Internet banking. Service data shows that most respondents come from that Internet banking apps are not suitable for their electronic devices. Additionally, 20% of respondents out of 200 confirm that the Internet banking experience is convenient for them but not always faster (Opensignal, 2022).

5.2.4 Physical Risk (Risk Barriers)

This study found that technostress has a significant influence on the use of Internet banking. Customers face different problems using Internet banking technology that cause stress for the customers (Sheth,1989). As Bangladesh is culturally not advanced in technology use, customers always face anxiety and stress during the beginning of using new technology (La Torre et al., 2018). Although this stress appeared differently based on the age group of the users, this is more common in the older generation despite their educational level (Dunphy & Herbig, 1995). Bank employees highlight this problem based on their experience that the younger generation comparatively faces no problems in terms of technological stress due to their familiarity with other technological products and social media. But the older generation

with technological literacy faces problems conducting Internet banking. However, this stress is apparent at the beginning of using new technology, but once they are used to it, they are more confident and less nervous, which causes less stress as well (Ho et al., 2020). However, technostress causes more due to the lack of trust in the system and the negative impression on the overall Internet banking procedures. This problem is highlighted by the respondent that due to the fraudulent activities and hacking incidents; customers feel stress and anxiety if the money that was transferred to their account or other account does not appear quickly. Therefore, they suffer stress and anxiety due to the possibility of losing money, forcing them to contact a respected bank or customer service.

5.2.5 Cash Dependency (Traditional Barrier)

This study finds that dependency on cash affects the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city (Khan *et al.*, 2021). Bangladeshi people culturally used to use cash in their daily financial transactions. The survey findings of this research show that 54.5% of respondents acknowledge that they prefer cash in their daily financial activities. Although the number of digital financial transactions increased during the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the transactions ended up in cash withdrawals, which has diminished the purpose of digital financial transactions (Chowdhury, 2020). The interviews with bank employees reveal that customers' education and workplace policies play a significant role in the dependence on cash. Most of the people are day labourers, and they get paid in cash. Therefore, it's difficult for them to take that cash, deposit it in the bank and then use it, which is very complicated for this less-educated poor population. Although the high-level office jobs are different, those are limited in numbers.

Although shifting towards Internet banking from traditional cash dependency is a slow process, Bangladesh is making progress. This notion is emphasised by the bank employees in the interview that their customers are adopting Internet banking which is slow about making progress. With the introduction of new technologies such as the Internet, banking comes with inertia which is surely overcome by the people through using it. However, survey data shows that 54.5% of respondents prefer to use cash, and among those, 60.8% are male respondents, and 45% are female, which means the preference for using cash is higher among the male population than females (Manzoor *et al.*, 2021). The probable reason for that could be the income level and electronic device ownership of females (Islam, Basher and Enamul Haque, 2022). Findings suggest that women's income level is lower than men's in every category,

including the highest unemployment rate, which was 7.5% higher than that of men (Badar,2018; Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017). However, the progress of shifting toward Digital financial activities is mostly noticeable in the mobile financial service due to the rapid development of money-transferring apps such as Nagod and bkaash. Respondents from the interview confirmed the popularity of mobile financial services and the popularity and acceptance among people, which allow people to transfer a limited amount of money instantly; however, for large payments, people are still heavily dependent on cash.

5.2.6 Lack of Customer Banker Relationship (Traditional Barrier)

This study has found that the traditional banking system has created a strong customer-banker relationship. Customers are heavily dependent on their respective bank branches and the bank employees. Survey site visit shows that 15% of respondents visit their bank branch every day, whereas 17% visit the bank branch regularly. Where 28.5% of respondents mention that they visit their bank once a month, it is apparent that despite being time-consuming and closely related to transportation, customers do not mind visiting their bank branch regularly just to have a conversation with bank employees (Afshan and Sharif, 2016). The bank employees also acknowledged this factor during the interviews, but the bank employees shared their daily experiences from this perspective. Respondents stated that customers prefer to do something from the bank manager or bank employees rather than reading online what other information sources are available (Al-Ajam and Md Nor, 2015). They further added that any suggestion or assurance from bank managers regarding their finances makes them assured and satisfied during the face-to-face conversation despite having all the information banks generally provide to the customers (Neil and Boshoff, 2021; Serener, 2019). However, this statement appeared contradictory to the outcome of the survey result where 48.5% of the customers believe that Information regarding Internet banking is not available in the media, and 52% responded that banks do not frequently inform, encourage or provide training for customers to use Internet banking. This unexpected contradiction reveals that there is a communication gap between banks' initiatives to inform customers and the customers' ability to absorb all that information to improve their banking experience.

5.2.7 Religious Belief (Traditional Barrier)

Another unexpected finding emerged from the study that a significant number of bank customers avoid the traditional banking system due to their religious beliefs (Uddin and Ahmmed, 2018). As interest is forbidden according to Islamic belief, most of the religious people who follow Islam very strongly have a natural tendency to not be involved in the traditional banking system (Khan and Mohomed, 2017) as the traditional banking system is very often associated with fixed-rate interest on deposits, FDR or DPS (Mushtaq & Siddiqui, 2017). These people generally avoid any banking system. However, shifting toward Islamic banking has increased in recent days (Hoque et al., 2022), although the number of Islamic banks is limited in Bangladesh compared to the traditional banking system. Therefore, the opportunity to have Internet banking services from Islamic banks is also narrow. However, conversation from bank managers highlights that many conventional banking systems have recently introduced the Islamic banking window in parallel to the conventional banking system. Therefore, customers with Islamic minds can have the opportunity to get Internet banking services as well as conventional banking services easily. However, it is difficult for banks to understand those customers' demands and develop banking products accordingly because those people are not associated with branch banking either (Hassan et al., 2023). Therefore, it's a great challenge for the traditional conventional banking system to understand the significant portion of the population who are Islamic-minded and bring them under the umbrella of Internet banking service.

5.2.8 Bad Reputation of the Bank (Image Barrier)

Banks' reputation is a significant element for gaining consumer trust and promoting Internet banking services. This study finds that previous fraudulent activities in banks, including hacking fraud or insolvency of the banks, create a negative impression among consumers who are reluctant to adopt Internet banking. Therefore, these customers generally do not trust banks even though most of the banks are conducting banking activities with the highest transparency and reliability. Thus, this negative image of a bank diminishes the positive perception of a particular bank and other banks in the banking industry, creating an unfavourable impression of the bank and industry and generating image-related barriers (Lian and Yen, 2013). However, this study found that this negative impression is comparatively lower among younger

generations than the older generation. Findings reveal that 50.5% of respondents out of 200 believe that Internet banking is not secure enough for their personal data and money. Within this group, only 19.8% of respondents who are aged below 30 years believe that Internet banking is. On the contrary, 80.2% of them are over 30 years old. This explains that trust in Internet banking is lower among older people than in the younger generation, which is consistent with the study by (Kaur et al., 2020).

The findings from the interview of bank employees indicate that previous corruption and previous fraudulent activities negatively impact consumers' decision-making process to adopt Internet banking. However, ensuring and offering high-quality banking service is useful to mitigate this barrier and is found to be useful in establishing consumer trust and belief regarding the safety and security of their money and personal data, which ultimately boosts the adoption rate of Internet banking (Laukkanen, 2016; Yu & Chantatub, 2016).

5.3 Impact of Lack of Service Infrastructure on the Internet Banking Adoption:

5.3.1 Slow Internet Speed and Cost (Value Barriers):

Having an Internet connection is a vital element of using Internet banking. This study finds that slow Internet is one of the most important factors in adopting Internet banking (Arif et al., 2020). However, the cost of the Internet is lower than the speed of the Internet in Khulna city. According to the findings of the survey, 38.5% of respondents said that Internet speed is very slow, and only 19% said the cost of Internet connection is expensive. It is noticeable that Internet connection has reached not only urban areas in Bangladesh but also spread to rural areas (Opensignal, 2022). This is probably due to the government initiative to maximise digitalisation across the country. This is acknowledged by the bank employees during the interview, and they shared their experience with rural customers that even farmers are using the Internet for social media or other Internet experiences, but the most common objection they get from the customers is that those customers can't do the heavy task using their Internet due to the slow speed such as conducting Internet banking activities. Despite the expansion of Internet connection, the Internet speed did not increase along with it; therefore, there is a

massive opportunity to spread Internet banking adoption, but the poor Internet connection is holding it back.

However, the average cost of the Internet in Bangladesh is not high compared to the other South Asian countries, but this may be still high for the poor people, especially those who are at the base of the pyramid. In addition to that, they have to spend money to purchase the phone or other required electronic devices. Also, these people have lower purchasing power and price sensitivity, which shape their consumption patterns toward basic commodities (Chipp and Corder, 2009; Guesalaga, 2008). Therefore, the cost of the Internet is a significant factor for them, especially if they have to compromise with value-to-price due to poor Internet speed (Chaimaa, Najib and Rachid, 2020). So, assistance from banks and the government sides is essential in this matter which is evident from the finding of survey results where the majority of the respondents think that banks should provide a cheaper Internet connection to their customers.

5.3.2 Segregation of Mobile Financial Services (Use Barriers):

The unexpected findings of this resource reveal that mobile financial services such as Nogod, bkaash etc., have gained massive popularity among customers due to the recent development of fintech innovation. Mobile financial services provide similar facilities to the customer as Internet banking, such as transferring money, doing online shopping, paying workers wages etc. Despite having more than one million agents providing financial services to people, only nine banks are integrated with these mobile financial systems. Therefore, a large number of customers can't access their bank accounts through this system because of not integrated with the bank services. This restricts customers' opportunity to transfer money from their bank account to the mobile financial system for making transactions or doing daily shopping (Wisuwat Sunhem and Kitsuchart Pasupa, 2020). The bank employees also highlighted these problems as they shared their experiences with the customers. The customers always complain about this issue which is very familiar to the bank. Some banks are trying to integrate their services with mobile financial services, but due to the lack of technological advancement and poor investment in banks' technology, this progress is not as sufficient as supposed to be (Ahmed et al., 2022). Another important factor associated with mobile financial service popularity is that most people accept mobile financial services as a substitute for Internet banking services (Chawla and Joshi, 2017). And this is another critical factor for not increasing

the adoption rate of Internet banking. However, most of the transactions through mobile financial services end up with cash withdrawals which totally suppresses the usefulness of having Internet banking or the government and banks' ultimate goal to become cash-lite Bangladesh (Khan *et al.*, 2021).

5.3.3 Difficult to Set up Bank Accounts (Use Barriers):

The outcome of the findings revealed that some customers face difficulties setting up their bank accounts, especially customers with lower digital literacy. Although the setting up process is easier, some customers find difficulties due to the additional authentication and verification required for the security of the account (Castillo-Villar and Castillo-Villar, 2022). Furthermore, design constraints are also significant factors which may cause additional difficulties. Difficulties in setting up bank accounts create a negative impression initially, even before customers start using Internet banking. This may cause customers not to continue using the service even though they are successful in setting up the account although this is contradictory to the findings of (Kala Kamdjoug *et al.*, 2021). Findings from the interview highlight that customers face difficulties initially that lead them to visit their banks to set up their bank accounts. Even some cases, customers have to visit their banks' branches multiple times to fix the problem, which causes negative impressions as well as stress among customers (Musa *et al.*, 2015). This also creates work pressure on the bank employees as bank employees mention in the interview that customers very often disturb them for minor issues regarding their Internet banking account (Al-Ajam and Md Nor, 2015).

5.3.4 Inconvenience Banking Process (Use Barriers):

An inconvenient banking process creates negative experiences among customers, which is one of the main reasons for affecting the adoption process (Duarte *et al.*, 2018). The reasons for the inconvenient banking process can be different factors such as design constraints of banking apps, bank websites, issues with banking servers as well as the Internet connection. Despite which factor is affecting it, customers always assume that the issues arise from the bank side (Fu and Mishra, 2021). Survey data reveals that the majority of respondents believe that their banking apps or websites are not user-friendly (Schnieder, 2012). However, findings from bank employees suggest that although there are some issues in bank servers that may cause problems sometimes due to the infrastructure in Bangladesh is still in the early stage, in most

cases, customers' poor configured mobile phones or other electronic devices which is not compatible with banks' website or app (Wisuwat Sunhem and Kitsuchart Pasupa, 2020). Therefore, they face problems during online shopping or making transactions. The reason behind this could be there are lots of cheaper smartphones that can provide an Internet experience in limited scope for customers. Still, those mobile devices are not suitable for Internet banking. In addition to that, many customers find banking procedures through the Internet very difficult because of their inherent inertia due to the long dependency on the traditional banking system (Rawashdeh, 2015). Therefore, although they adopt the initiative of using Internet banking in the process of utilisation, they find it inconvenient and distressful as they always compare with their previous experience through traditional branch banking, where they mainly depend on the bank employees to do the banking for them but on the contrary, Internet banking solely depends on the customers own initiative and performance. Additionally, one of the most common uses of Internet banking is to do online shopping where they need to connect to their Internet portal to make payments. However, sometimes it's difficult to connect to the e-commerce portals (Kaur and Malik, 2019). In addition to that, customer needs to use their PIN and secure password for the security of the account, which is very common for some customers to forget. Therefore, their inability to successfully reset the password may cause the blocking of their account initially. Consequently, they need to contact their customer service or respective banks to resolve this problem which may appear to be stressful and inconvenient for some customers as they need to visit the bank branch (Serener, 2019) unless they are able to fix the problem through online support, and this is always time and money consuming. However, inconvenience and complexity appear differently in different age groups as well as location which is consistent with the findings of (Hettiarachchi, 2013). Younger people, both in cities and rural areas, are much more capable of solving any difficulties (Siyal et al., 2019). The older generation in the rural areas lacks this ability. Therefore, the combination of multiple factors contributes to creating a negative impression about Internet banking and the service provided by the Internet bank.

5.3.5 Poor Customer Service (Use Barriers)

Customer service is the fundamental element of providing and ensuring an excellent Internet banking experience. Resolving any technical issues and conflicts faced by customers determines customer retention in Internet banking (Nghah, ABD.Ghani and Rahi, 2020). The

findings of this research reveal that the majority of customers are not satisfied with their banks' customer service (Sharif and Raza, 2017). Findings from the interviews with bank employees revealed that banks are trying their best to ensure the best customer service. Banks provide both face-to-face customer service as well as online customer service. So, if any customer faces any problem, they can contact online customer service and get help. However, it may not be possible for many customers to follow a step-by-step procedure provided by the customer service assistant due to their lack of technical knowledge (Hanif and Lallie, 2021). Therefore, those customers having the problem have to visit their physical bank to resolve the issues (Serener, 2019). In that case, the whole purpose of Internet banking diminished as the customer had to use their traditional way of service. It has also appeared that the service assistant's lack of empathy and professionalism can be a factor as it is a common problem in developing countries which can be solved by introducing the chatbot to provide customer service (Sarbabidya et al., 2020). Additionally, it is also customers' tendency to meet with the bank manager for their problems rather than take the initiative to solve them personally. Also, as most people are heavily dependent on physical banking (Khan *et al.*, 2021), the massive workload of bank employees may affect to provide the best customer service, which is also a significant factor especially considering the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic, where most banks of limited service. Therefore, people's inability to resolve the problem through online customer service and a short period of banking window due to lockdown affected customers to get good customer service from banks and resolve their issues quickly and efficiently.

5.3.6 Financial Risk (Risk Barriers)

Internet banking is associated with the inherited potential financial risk of losing money like many other innovations (Sheth, 1989). This risk factor is comparatively severe in developing countries like Bangladesh, where the lack of sophisticated advanced technology makes the service infrastructure of banks vulnerable to fraud and hacking that contribute to customers' financial loss (Sarker et al., 2020). The missing physical interaction with bank employees and the past incidents of fraudulent activities in the banking industry make customers sceptical about putting their trust in Internet banking (Asif, Aslam & Hwang, 2020) which is evident from the findings of a survey where half of the customers confirmed. They believe that Internet banking increases the risk of fraud. On the contrary, a quarter of respondents believe that Internet banking is safe for their money. The further belief of losing money due to mistakes

from both parties and the uncertainty of the recovery of that money through refund refrain customers from trusting the Internet banking process and adopting Internet banking to its optimum level. This finding is consistent with the findings of (Alalwan, 2018; Mayer et al., 1995) that a lack of trust in the banking system negatively contributes to the shaping of customers' perceptions and intention of adopting Internet banking, considering the lack of human interaction between both parties. Therefore, system reliability in terms of data protection and the financial safety of customers, along with banks' integrity and ethics, are the fundamental critical elements of consumers' trust in banking system infrastructure (Moghavemi et al., 2021). This notion is consistent with the findings from the interview where bank employees highlighted the customers' concern about their personal data security in the process of creating their Internet banking account by using their personal information. Although customers expect that the bank will ensure their data security, without any significant possibility of being opportunist, survey data shows the contrary notion of customers regarding this matter. A significant number of respondents pointed out thus security concerns as one of the main reasons for the unpopularity of Internet banking which is consistent with the findings of (Ali et al., 2021). This is probably banks' failure to establish their consumer trust through good communication and providing information. This lack of communication and information regarding the assurance of safety and safety of customers' personal data and money creates uncertainty avoidance in Khulna, Bangladesh. Higher uncertainty avoidance hinders customers' decision-making process from adopting Internet banking which can be resolved by providing information regarding the safety and security, and reliability of Internet banking (Li et al., 2021). However, the majority of the respondents from the survey opined that there is a significant lack in taking initiative from the banks' side to inform and encourage customers on this matter.

Although customers' concern for security is often exaggerated perceptions undoubtedly, there is a significant matter of concern regarding the safety measures of Internet banking in the Bangladeshi banking industry due to the lack of advanced technology to prevent cyber security threats and respond to the incident once detected (Ahmed et al., 2022). This is consistent with the study of (wang et al., 2020) that a developing country like Bangladesh is often the target of hackers and fraudsters due to the use of sophisticated advanced technology used for hacking which is often insufficient to prevent security threats. However, the statement from different bank employees highlights that most banks have established strong security infrastructure to prevent security breaches differently. However, in most cases, fraud and security breaches happen due to the lack of customers' lack of technical knowledge and their negligence.

Customers share their ID and password over the Internet with an unknown person in most fraud cases. Mobile scamming is a common problem in developing countries, and Bangladesh is not an exception. Customers with a lack of technical skills and digital literacy are always the victims of fraud, where the fraudsters often act as bank employees or government people (Ahmed et al., 2022). Additionally, older generations are the most vulnerable to fraud risk as they often lack technical and digital knowledge along with necessary preventive measures to protect their personal data and money, which is the deterrent factor of adopting Internet banking not only in developing countries but also in a developed country (Hanif and Lallie, 2021). These concerns were also highlighted by the bank employees in the interview, where they added that they always instruct the victims not to use Internet banking anymore due to their potential risk of being affected, which not only creates a negative perception among victims but also deters other potential users in the close circle of victims (Rashid,2022). The customer is the main victim of fraud despite the fault of which parties, and it creates massive economic and psychological stress among customers' trust in Internet banking. It is always a controversial and often complex procedure to get a refund from the customers' perspective as investigations are time-consuming and, in some cases, it is difficult to identify the responsible party Countries (Roškot, Wanasika and Kreckova Kroupova, 2020). The findings of this study show that customers get a full refund in the case of a wrong transaction from one account to another bank account. However, customers lose money due to their negligence is difficult to get back their money in most cases (Van Der Meulen, 2013). Therefore, strong regulations to protect the customers' interests and clear guidelines are essential that will boost customers' confidence in Internet banking despite of inherent financial risk which is associated with poor Internet banking service infrastructures (Maryna Utkina, 2023).

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Research Contribution

6.1 Introduction:

The previous chapter (*Chapter 5*) presented a discussion of the key findings from the data analysis covering the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. This discussion consisted of qualitative findings, quantitative findings and some other respondents' comments and opinions based on the questions asked.

This chapter will conclude the study by summarising the key research findings in relation to the research aims, objectives and research questions as well as the value and contribution of the research. It will also review the limitations of this study and propose opportunities for future research.

6.2 Summary of the Thesis:

Internet banking is a relatively new concept among bank customers in Bangladesh. Despite having massive necessity and usefulness, the expansion of Internet banking in Bangladesh has been relatively slow due to many factors since its first introduction. Therefore, this study is designed to investigate the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. The process of this investigation has started by critically analysing the existing literature to understand the context of the research background. The findings from the review of existing literature highlighted that research on this background is very limited in Bangladesh, especially in the Khulna region. Additionally, the existing literature is mostly based on the quantitative method focused on the relationship between variables using quantitative data and whether the variable is significant or not to the research problem. So, there is a necessity for in-depth investigation with a better methodological approach along with a robust methodology which will allow the comparison of findings and ensure validity, creditability, and reliability of findings through triangulation. Therefore, seven lower to mid-senior-level bank employees and 200 active and dormant users of Internet banking from Khulna City were chosen for the mixed methodological approach. Collected data were analysed through thematic analysis and quantitative analysis.

The purpose of this study is to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh, from cultural, local perception and service infrastructural perspectives. Therefore, this study is conducted to answer the following questions:

RQ-1: How do cultural factors and local perceptions impact the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh?

RQ-2: How does a lack of infrastructure impede the delivery of Internet banking services?

A total of seven interviews and 200 survey questionnaires were conducted to address the research questions where interviews were analysed through thematic analysis and the questionnaires were analysed statistically using descriptive analysis in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 presented the findings from qualitative analysis and quantitative analysis, and chapter 5 presented the comparison and interpretation of the findings. The purpose of this study is to develop our understanding of Internet banking adoption problems and the associated factors acting as a barrier to preventing the expansion of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh. Therefore, five resistance factors, use a barrier, value barrier, risk barrier, image barrier, and traditional barrier (address the cultural factors, local perceptions, and infrastructure perspectives), have taken consideration to find the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna city, Bangladesh.

Most of the existing literature identified the variables that are associated with the Internet banking adoption problem as well as prospects and challenges. However, no study investigated the perspective of cultural factors, local perceptions, as well as infrastructure perspectives, and therefore, this study is the first in nature conducted in Khulna City, Bangladesh, to understand the resistance factor of Internet banking adoption from both customers' and banks' perspectives. This study reveals that different elements of cultural factors and local perceptions such as the complexity of using Internet banking faced by the customer due to poor English literacy, lack of digital access and digital and financial literacy, customers' scepticism due to performance risk of Internet banking, technostress associated with physical risk, customers dependency on cash, lack of customers bankers relationship established through traditional way of banking, religious belief and negative reputation of banks affecting the Internet banking adoption. Additionally, lack of infrastructural factors such as slow Internet speed and Internet cost, segregation of mobile financial services, consumers' difficulties in setting up bank accounts, inconvenient banking process, poor customer service and associated financial risk due to theft

of personal data of customers, fraud and security breach shaping the negative environment to flourish the Internet banking service across the Khulna city Bangladesh.

6.3 Research Findings & Conclusion

6.3.1 Impact of Cultural Factors and Local Perception on Internet Banking Adoption:

6.3.1.1 Language Barrier:

This study investigates how cultural factors and local perceptions negatively impact the adoption of Internet banking. The findings of this research conclude that the complexity of using Internet banking arises from multiple perspectives, and demographic factors such as customers' age, education, income level and gender appear as the mediating factor that determines the level of complexity a customer faces. One of the most important factors is English language barriers. Despite being included in the educational curriculum and second official language in Bangladesh, most people lack English competency, and this is found to be severe among the older generation. Although some banks have introduced the Bangla interface as a substitute for the English interface, however, due to a lack of technical knowledge and incompatibility with learning through online sources, which are mostly in English, failed to resolve the language barrier issue. However, this factor is different among the younger generation due to the recent acceptance and popularity of social media, different e-commerce apps and gaming apps (Mohammadi, 2016; Raza et al., 2017). Therefore, the findings of the study, which are consistent with (George. 2015; Siyal et al., 2019), suggest that early exposure to the new technology boosts awareness and acceptance, which can maximise its adoption.

6.3.1.2 Lack of Digital Access and Digital & Financial Literacy:

Digital access refers to consumers' ownership of electronic devices, and digital literacy defines customers' ability to navigate the electronic device. Financial literacy in Internet banking refers to customers' ability to understand Internet banking and conduct banking activities successfully. However, the findings of this research show that consumers' access to digital devices has increased over COVID-19, Which is contrary to the findings of (Jahan et al., 2020). The reason behind this improvement could be the diversion from traditional services to online services in order to suppress COVID-19 transmission in Bangladesh following the

government-imposed countrywide lockdown. Despite of increase in digital access, survey data revealed that the compatibility of those devices with Internet banking apps is questionable due to the poor configuration of those devices.

This study also finds that digital and financial literacy did not increase along with digital access despite having the need for Internet banking and the availability of required digital devices, which is consistent with the findings of (Shahin, 2006; Musa et al., 2015). This study also highlights that customers' age and income level are closely associated with financial literacy and digital access. Although the younger generation is much more compatible with digital devices and has comparatively higher digital and financial literacy, their income level restricts them within limited Internet banking activities due to the lack of financial access. On the contrary, despite having access to finance and higher necessities, older customers are struggling to use Internet banking due to their lack of digital financial literacy. This problem is most severe in the rural side (Perera, 2018; Jahan et al., 2020) of Khulna city, where customers are not getting the benefit of Internet banking despite having access to higher income.

6.3.1.3 Performance Risk:

Performance risk associated with customers' perception of Internet banking adoption. Performance risk is associated with general perceptions of the customers wanting Internet banking and whether Internet banking would be able to meet their expectancy and perform accordingly to meet customers' demands. Different factors may influence performance risk, which causes negative word of mouth in the customer's social circle. Unlike traditional banking, the performance of Internet banking depends on individuals' initiative and capability. Therefore, the margin of error is higher from the customer's perspective which causes customers to go through a time-consuming process of mitigating the problem unless they can solve it themselves with or without the help of online customer service. Therefore, this negative experience causes distress to customers that affect other potential Internet banking users through negative word of mouth (Matsuo et al., 2018). Despite customers' inability to conduct Internet banking and the errors that occurred due to inability, negative experiences refrain active users from using Internet banking regularly. Additionally, a lengthy investigation process and lack of sophisticated technology hinder banks from responding quickly in the case of any refund issue and this contributes to negative experiences due to time loss (Featherman and Pavlov, 2003). Also, poorly configured electronic devices cause unpleasant service experiences.

6.3.1.4 Technostress:

This study finds that technology stress caused by using new technology has a significant effect on customers. Generally, Bangladeshi people are not technologically sound, and this factor is much greater among older generations despite their education level (Dunphy & Herbig, 1995). Therefore, stress and anxiety related to Internet banking are common factors for them. However, unlike the older generation, the young generation is much more confident and familiar with the Internet banking concept due to their familiarity with other similar products related to social media and gaming apps. However, technostress is temporary during the initial adoption of Internet banking, but the most common factor that causes stress is a lack of trust and confidence in the Internet banking system due to the fraudulent and hacking incidents that stimulate fear of losing money and personal data.

6.3.1.5 Cash Dependency:

Bangladesh is a cash-dependent society, and this practice is traditionally and culturally embedded in the society. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has caused a sharp increase in digital financial transactions; however, most of the transactions end up in cash withdrawals, which diminishes the purpose of digital transactions (Chowdhury, 2020). Workplace policy is also responsible for this factor as most of the customers in Khulna are day labourers or work in a non-official job and they get paid in cash. Therefore, depositing their salary in the bank and using it for digital payment is quite inconvenient for the general people. Although shifting towards Internet banking is slow but making progress, women are far behind men due to their lack of access to electronic device ownership and income. Additionally, parallel to Internet banking, mobile financial services such as Nogod and bKash are gaining popularity among the rural population for digital transactions. However, most transactions end up in cash withdrawals.

6.3.1.6 Lack of Customer Banker Relationship:

This study finds that the traditional banking system has created a strong customer-banker relationship. The findings of the research suggested that most of the customers frequently visit their banks despite time-consuming and travelling travel costs. The finding reveals that customers find assurance and confidence if they get suggestions from bank employees directly. Acknowledgement from bank employees addresses the consumers' behaviour that customers like to listen to bank employees directly rather than reading the same information online. On

the contrary, findings from the survey revealed that customers believe that there is not enough information provided from the bank side to inform them enough about Internet banking. That suggests that there is a lack of communication gap exists between customers and Internet banking service providers.

6.3.1.7 Religious Belief:

Bangladesh is a Muslim-majority country, and the transaction associated with interest is forbidden according to Islam. Therefore, most people who follow Islam strongly avoid conventional banking due to its association with interest (Mushtaq & Siddiqui, 2017). Although, the Islamic banking system is gaining popularity among these people. However, Islamic banks are limited in numbers. Therefore, Internet banking services from these banks are limited. However, many conventional banks are providing Islamic banking windows parallel to conventional banking. However, it's not quite appealing to the target population due to the fact these people are not associated with branch banking either. Therefore, understanding the demand and bringing them under the umbrella of Internet banking services is challenging for conventional banks.

6.3.1.8 Bad Reputation of Banks:

This means that banks' previous association with fraudulent and hacking incidents or insolvency create a negative perception of banks. This negative perception not only affects the particular banks but also affects other banks as well, it leads customers to develop negative perceptions that create image-related barriers. Although this negative impression is comparably lower among the younger generation, however, older generations are more sceptical in this regard (Kaur et al., 2020). Although previous corruption and fraudulent activities are responsible for the negative image of bank service, research finding suggests that ensuring quality service can overcome this barrier (Laukkanen, 2016).

6.3.2.0 Lack of Infrastructure Impedes the Delivery of Internet Banking Service:

6.3.2.1 Slow Internet Speed and Cost:

Internet connection is a vital element of conducting Internet banking. However, the findings of this research show that poor Internet connection is one of the most significant factors that are affecting the adoption of Internet banking. Although the cost of the Internet is reasonable, which is similar to the neighbouring country in South Asia, the speed of Internet connection is slower than in other countries. Government initiatives have assisted the spread of Internet users in the big cities; however, findings suggest that people in rural areas use the Internet in a very limited context due to the poor speed of the Internet that restricts them from conducting Internet banking and other heavy tasks. Although the cost of the Internet is not found as significant as Internet speed. However, the cost of the Internet is an important factor for people who have price sensitivity and lower purchasing power as they shape their purchasing choices toward basic commodities (Guesalaga, 2008). Therefore, government and bank initiatives are essential for them.

6.3.2.2 Segregation of Mobile Financial Service:

Mobile financial services such as Nagod and bKash have gained popularity in recent years. Mobile financial services are similar to Internet banking; however, despite having massive popularity and more than one million agents providing this service across the country, only nine banks have integrated their systems with mobile financial services. Therefore, the majority of people can't access their money from their bank account. Although banks are taking initiatives to integrate mobile financial services into the banks' system, lack of technological advancement and insufficient investment are the main obstacles to that. Although mobile financial service gives customers a similar experience to Internet banking, most of the transactions of mobile financial services end up with cash withdrawals which suppress the usefulness of having Internet banking and the governments initiatives to make cash lite society.

6.3.2.3 Difficulties in Setting up Bank Accounts:

Difficulties in setting up bank accounts due to the additional authentication and difficult banking process to secure customers' data and money can restrict customers from getting

Internet banking services. Furthermore, design constraints to Internet banking apps may add additional difficulties for customers with lower literacy. Therefore, customers perceive a negative impression of Internet banking even before they start using it. As a result, customers can reject the Internet banking service even though they are successful initially in setting up an online bank account. Findings show that customers had to visit the bank multiple times due to problems regarding their bank accounts. This has not only created a negative impression and distress for the customers but also increased the workload of bank employees.

6.3.2.4 Inconvenient Banking Process:

The inconvenient banking process creates a negative perception in customers' minds that affects Internet banking adoption. Inconvenient banking process is associated with banking app constraints, problems with bank websites and issues with banking servers including Internet connection. Survey data shows that customers believe the problem lies within the banking process. However, findings from bank employees reveal that although the banking infrastructure is not developed enough, in most cases, the incompatible electronic devices of customers are not suitable for bank apps or websites. This is due to the availability of cheaper smartphones which are good for social media browsing but not suitable for conducting heavy tasks like Internet banking. Inertia is a common factor in adopting new technology; any inconvenience in the banking process makes it distressful to customers who are generally used to traditional banking services. One of the most common uses of Internet banking is online shopping. However, many E-commerce platforms are not compatible with bank servers for making online payments. Therefore, inconvenience and complicity with the banking process create a negative experience that forces customers to discontinue Internet banking services even after initial adoption.

6.3.2.5 Poor Customer Service:

Customer service is the fundamental element of providing good Internet banking service and maximum customer retention. Being culturally dependent on face-to-face banking services and lacking educational, financial, and digital literacy, the lack of encounters with customer service is higher in Bangladesh than in other countries. The finding shows that higher customer dissatisfaction with customer service failed to assist and mitigate their technical issues.

Although bank employees believe that they maintain better customer service from the bank's perspective contradicts the customers' response. Therefore, it is evident that there is a communication and understanding gap exists between customers and banks. Initially, customer service providers' professionalism and empathy are important. However, customers' inability to resolve their problems through online consultation combining their preference to get face-to-face customer service encourages them to visit the bank. Thus, a countrywide lockdown due to COVID-19 and a short- period of banking window affected customers getting the Internet banking service.

6.3.2.6 Financial Loss:

Although Internet banking comes with inherent potential financial loss due to fraud and security breaches, poor banking infrastructure to prevent and respond to security threats not only increases the lack of trust in the Internet banking system but also refrains existing users from using it (Alalwan, 2018). The finding shows that the majority of customers do not feel secure with their money and personal data. The lack of physical interaction with banks and security concerns influences customers' scepticism about adopting Internet banking. Additionally, scammers often distinguish themselves as bank employees in their fraudulent activities. Therefore, it is difficult for general customers, especially in rural areas, to identify the fraud. Also, in some cases, bank employees' lack of ethics and integrity is also questionable due to their association with fraudsters. Therefore, customers shape overall generalise negative perceptions. In addition to that, recent corruption and hacking of the Bangladesh central bank expose the weakness in cyber security and necessary measures to prevent fraud both internally and externally. Furthermore, poor technological infrastructure, lack of investment in cybersecurity and lack of skilled workforce delays the investigation of fraudulent activities and the recovery of money not only deterring providing Internet banking services but also creating a negative impression among existing and potential customers.

6.4.0 Research Contribution

6.4.1 Theoretical Contributions:

Internet banking and the adoption of Internet banking have created a massive platform for research. There have been many investigations conducted to understand the factors affecting

the adoption of Internet banking. However, most of the studies were conducted in developed countries; limited studies have been conducted in developing countries like Bangladesh. Furthermore, most of the previous studies conducted based on DOI (Diffusion of Innovation Theory) (Rogers, 1995); TRA (Theory of Reasoned Action) (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975); RDT (Resource Dependency Theory) (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003); TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) (Davis et al., 1989); TPB (Theory of Planned Behavior) (Ajzen, 1991). However, most of the research was conducted focusing on customers' acceptance behaviour of Internet banking through testing variables, and these existing frameworks do not focus on examining resistance factors towards Internet banking adoption (Gupta & Arora, 2017).

The focus of innovation resistance theory (IRT) is to explain consumers' resistance to any innovation in terms of barriers such as uses barrier, value barrier, risk barrier, traditional barrier, and image barrier, which provides the theoretical basis for investigation toward innovation.

This thesis has contributed to knowledge incorporating Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) in the Bangladeshi context (*cultural factors & local perceptions, and infrastructural perspective*) to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna City, Bangladesh through the lens of Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT). Many studies have been conducted adopting the innovation resistance theory from different digital innovation perspectives (Lian et al., 2012; Lim et al., 2013); Laukkanen, 2016; Yu & Chantatub, 2016; Borraz-Mora et al., 2017; Gupta and Arora, 2017). However, based on the researcher's understanding, this research is the first in nature conducted from a Bangladeshi perspective to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking through the lens of innovation resistance theory. The conceptual framework developed for this study provides a robust view of innovation resistance factors and how these factors affect the adoption of Internet banking. As the area of this research is continuously expanding, this research contributes to knowledge by providing an understanding of how different barriers/factors affect the adoption of Internet banking in a developing country perspective. Theoretically, this study complements other empirical studies. The findings of this research present some uniqueness and variances to other research and contribute to further knowledge.

6.4.2 Policy Contribution:

The robustness of this study identifies different flaws in the banking industry to maximise the adoption of Internet banking across the country and deliver effective and convenient banking

services. The findings of this study pointed out the necessity of adopting different policies for the effective implementation of Internet banking services from both the government side as well as Banks. Effective and favourable government policy for the banking industry in the expansion of Internet banking is essential to meet government targets to make Bangladesh digital. This study highlights the key areas of both customers' and banks' perspectives where supportive policy implementation is necessary. This study highlights the necessity of developing policies to safeguard customers' interests due to their financial loss. Additionally, this reveals the necessity of financial assistance from the government for building a strong Internet banking infrastructure and supporting private-owned banks. Finally, the government needs to consider the fact before implementing new policies that blanket policy will not be equally effective for every bank. Rather implementing policy based on individual cases will boost banks' development and sustainable growth.

6.4.3 Practical Contribution and Contribution to Knowledge:

This study has investigated and highlighted different factors associated with Internet banking services. Different factors are associated with different issues connected with banks' internal and external environment, cultural factors, and customers' perspectives. This study finds that people face complexity in using Internet banking due to their poor English skills, especially the older generation. In combination with a lack of English skills, the lack of digital literacy of customers is also a barrier that restricts the ability of potential and existing customers. Additionally, their limited access to digital devices to conduct Internet banking does not support their interest in using Internet banking. Their doubt about the effectiveness of Internet banking and the stress caused by using new technology affects them negatively. Being culturally dependent on cash use prevents them from breaking the inertia of using digital banking services. Other negative perceptions of Internet banking are caused by religious beliefs and the negative image of banks keeping people away from Internet banking. Along with cultural factors and local perception, lacking the service infrastructure of banks significantly contributes to the cause. Therefore, slow Internet service technically affects smooth Internet banking. Additionally, the cost of the Internet connection is sometimes a burden for low-income people. Lack of investment in banking technology affects banks to integrate mobile financial services with Internet banking networks. Design constraints of Internet banking apps and inconvenient banking procedures failing banks to attract people towards Internet banking adoption. In addition to that, poor customer service from the banks' side to resolve customers'

issues and concerns driving customers away from the Internet banking network towards traditional branch banking. Lastly, increase in fraudulent activities and scam incidents spreading a negative perception of Internet banking. Therefore, people's concern regarding safety of their personal data and money preventing them to be involve in the Internet banking in their daily financial transactions.

This study highlights many determinant factors which will assist managers in understanding the issues clearly and taking necessary actions to mitigate the issues from the banks' perspective. It will assist in understanding the customer's perspective in-depth and help banks provide customer service based on customers' demand and necessity. As this study collaborates both customers' and banks' perspectives together, existing customers, as well as potential customers, will have a clear understanding of Internet banking that will help banks indirectly as well for the expansion of Internet banking.

Additionally, this research offers a greater contribution to practice. For example, this study finds that people face complexity in using Internet banking due to their poor English literacy, especially the older generation. This finding of the research indicated that the existing banking interface does not assist some customers, more specifically the older generation to operate the Internet banking service freely and therefore, quick attention and rapid developments are needed to counter the language barriers. In addition to the language barriers, this study finds that the lack of digital literacy is also affecting the adoption, therefore, this study highlights the necessity of providing learning materials by banks to educate customers on how to conduct Internet banking by using their own digital devices. Additionally, this study presents the major issues of the adoption process such as limited access to digital devices and limited access to the Internet for a large number of people in rural areas and to solve these issues, banks need to address the issues promptly and take effective initiative to ensure that customer in rural side can have access to digital devices and Internet. Customers' doubt on the effectiveness of Internet banking indicated that further communication between customers and banks is required. Good communication increases awareness about the products and services and the findings of this research indicated that the existing process is not fruitful enough and a new approach is required. As a result, customers especially older and less educated people will find Internet banking less stressful while navigating through their digital devices. Slow Internet speeds indicated that existing infrastructure is not supporting enough and needs faster and more effective development. Existing Internet speed is slow but costly and banks are required to address these problems and offer solutions such as providing cheaper or free data connection to their customers. This study found that many mobile financial services are gaining popularity

such as “bkash”, “Nagod” but they are not fully integrated into the mainstream banking channels. This study highlights that people find these financial services useful and if banks can fully integrate these financial service mediums, adoption of Internet banking will gain rapid pace. This research also presents that existing banking apps and banking interfaces are required to be upgraded regularly according to the customers’ needs. Furthermore, customer service found to be less helpful to the customers indicates effective training programs on how to offer greater customer service is required. The existing way of customer service is not helpful to most of the customers and turning them away from using Internet banking. Lastly, banking security is not well established and safeguarding against fraud and scams is needed to remove customers’ uncertainty caused by negative banking incidents that are common in Bangladesh. Existing measures are not strong enough to provide higher degree of confidence towards Internet banking process and its full adoption.

6.5 Recommendation:

The findings of this study will help banks, customers, government, investors, third parties, and academics to understand core research problems and to develop appropriate policies to implement in practice. In addition, this study will help banks understand the main factors preventing customers from adopting Internet banking from the customer perspective. Furthermore, this research provides an in-depth understanding of the core aspect of this research to the stakeholders of banks, as well as provides scope for further research for academics. This study identified key factors from the social-cultural and infrastructural perspectives that are reflected in the conceptual framework incorporating Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT), and this will provide a new understanding of the Internet banking adoption process. The following paragraphs are going to provide recommendations for research, policy, and practice:

6.5.1 Recommendations for Future Research:

This study is conducted focusing on Khulna, which is one of the major cities in Bangladesh. However, future studies can be conducted focused on other cities in Bangladesh such as

Dhaka and Chittagong. Dhaka is the capital of Bangladesh with a massive diverse population. Additionally, most of the banks and government decisions directly affect these areas including any new development of infrastructure and policies. Chittagong is the port city and the second most important financial hub in Bangladesh. Therefore, future research focusing on this area will enrich the understanding of issues concerning the adoption of Internet banking.

Also, this research can be replicated in developing countries where a large number of populations live in rural areas. There are many South Asian countries such as Sri Lanka, and Pakistan share similar socio-economic environments with different demographic characteristics. Additionally, future research should be conducted on other African developing countries such as Ghana, Nigeria, and South Africa as they have different demographic characteristics with similar economic development. Therefore, it will be beneficial to understand the effectiveness of this research framework in different economic environments.

This study analyses the qualitative data collected from seven different banks in Khulna City and the quantitative data collected from 200 respondents. However, the sample size can be increased in future research to get more comprehensive insights. A larger sample size increases the credibility and generalizability. Also, qualitative data was collected from lower and middle-level bank employees as they have close associations with customers. Therefore, future research can include senior-level bank employees to have a robust understanding of banks' decision-making perspectives regarding Internet banking adoption. Additionally, future research data should be collected through face-to-face interactions as it will provide the researcher with robust and rich data. In future research, interviews with customers can be included in the study as it will provide further clarification of the research problems. Also, future research can be conducted on top employees and decision-makers in the banking industry and this help to understand the decision-making process.

Additionally, future research can include 'Mobile Financial Services (MFS)' as an additional variable in the research framework as it appeared in the finding of this research as a significant factor within the Internet banking adoption perspective. It can act as an alternative way of doing financial activities and appears to be an influential factor that can shape the Internet banking adoption choice of customers. Applying the existing model with this additional variable '*Mobile Financial Services (MFS)*' will help the researcher to get

new insights regarding customers' behavioural traits and customers perceptions towards Internet banking.

Many databases are ideal for publishing research papers such as Scopus, PubMed, ScienceDirect, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and JSTOR. However, this research is intended to be published in any Scopus-indexed subject-relevant journal preferably within Q1 and Q2 rating journals.

6.5.2 Recommendations for Policy:

- The government needs to introduce and implement favourable policies to support Internet banking adoption based on individual banking sectors rather than establishing a blanket policy that will not assist equally every sector of the banking industry. Such as the central bank should provide guidelines to merge one or multiple banks, and non-bank financial institutions to merge with banks (TBS Report, 2024). Bangladesh Bank should offer incentives, including regulatory relaxations regarding Minimum Capital Requirement (MCR), provisioning, Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR) requirements, Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), and Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR). In addition, the government should provide policy support for the banks upon their request through the central bank and provide clear guidance to protect the employment of the transferor bank employees (Haque, 2024).

- The government needs to introduce strict rules and regulations to prevent fraud and corruption in the banking industry to create a positive image among customers within the country as well as internationally (Maryna Utkina, 2023). The massive heist by international hackers in Bangladesh Bank which is the central bank of Bangladesh has significantly damaged the reputation of the Bangladeshi banking system and customers' confidence in it. The bank was a soft target, with no firewall and simple \$10 electronic switches connecting it to the SWIFT global payment system used by more than 11,000 financial institutions globally. This indicated the lack of attention to the security of the banking system which required government funds and strong regulatory policy (Ings Simon, 2023).

- The government needs to allocate the budget for the development of banking sectors, especially for the banks that are relatively new in the industry and lack advanced technology to establish a strong Internet banking infrastructure. In addition, the Bangladesh government strongly focused on borrowing from Bangladeshi banks. The government should focus on foreign financing and not be heavily dependent on borrowing from local banks otherwise it leaves little chance for the private sector to get loans. Therefore, banks will be unable to finance the development of their infrastructure and ultimately hinder the development of Internet banking (Byron and Rahman, 2024). The government also needs to relax the existing regulations and introduce supportive regulations to encourage foreign direct investment in Bangladesh for the development of Internet banking (Belinda et al., 2021).

6.5.3 Recommendations for Practice:

- Banks need to take strong initiative for promoting Internet banking adoption among customers concentrating on both rural and urban areas equally, which will assist banks in reducing cost, maximising profit, customer retention and overall bank growth. Banks need to adopt Internet banking to sustain themselves in the competitive market and meet customers' demands and expectations. Without banks' strong initiative to promote Internet banking, the bank will miss all those opportunities.
- Banks need to focus on achieving customer satisfaction through providing excellent and smooth banking service. Most people are not satisfied with the customer service provided by the banks (Sharif and Raza, 2017) although the perception of banks says otherwise. Therefore, it is apparent that there is a massive communication gap exists between customers and banks. Providing effective training and developing customer customer-centric work environment for the banking service providers will help to ensure the highest customer satisfaction in a developing country like Bangladesh. Banks need to modify the existing methods of understanding customer perspective. Robust surveys and online and offline feedback options could mitigate this communication barrier. Also, partnerships with foreign successful banks will allow Bangladeshi banks to learn and implement effective service structures from a Bangladeshi perspective (Nghah, ABD.Ghani and Rahi, 2020).

- Most of the customers have problems with the Internet connection. Customers use broadband Internet connections and mobile data services provided by different companies. Banks can introduce their own Internet service through mobile data at the free of cost or lowest cost (Jaruwachirathanakul and Fink, 2005). Banks need to ensure the highest data speed, which is one of the most important factors that deter the customers from conducting Internet banking smoothly. Partnerships with local mobile phone companies and mobile data service providers will allow banks to mitigate this problem and will help to build a strong Internet banking service infrastructure in Bangladesh. Therefore, banks will be able to provide the electronic device to conduct Internet banking with a discount or monthly instalment payment option. This way, customers with lower income will have the opportunity to get the benefit of Internet banking (Baishya and Samalia, 2019). Additionally, the banks need to have strong control over the Internet banking infrastructure through regular maintenance. Banks also need to provide free antivirus software for those devices as well.
- This study found a lack of initiative from banks to raise awareness and communication among customers. In line with the thinking of Pavithra and Al, (2021), banks need to maximize the awareness program among customers through newspapers, social media, and other communication channels. Customers believe that banks are not taking the strong initiative to make them aware of the relevant Internet banking product and how to use it. Arranging different social events, welfare programs, and cultural events are effective way of raising awareness among customers. In addition, offering free training sessions for customers and keeping video tutorials on the banks' websites regarding how to use Internet banking its service will assist people with a lack of digital and financial literacy.
- Banks need to provide a strong assurance of financial recovery against fraud and other incidents where customers lose their money. Banks should focus on the speed of recovery of lost money. Providing assurance will establish customer trust in banking services that will boost Internet banking adoption through positive word-of-mouth (Li et al., 2021). In line with Nnachi et al. (2020), banks should implement an 'Innovative Modification Strategy' that allows banks to use biometric technology systems such as fingerprints, face recognition, voice recognition and iris recognition to access the Internet banking account by customers. Using biometric technology to access Internet

banking accounts and conduct financial transactions and other banking activities provides higher simplicity and safety assurance (Melnychenko, Volosovych and Baraniuk, 2020).

- Banks need to incorporate the existing digital financial services in Bangladesh. In this way, the customer will have the benefit of accessing their money from their bank account easily. Integrating all the financial service providers with banks will make cashless transactions easy and convenient and small businesses will come under the shadow of Internet banking services. Thus, dependency on cash will decrease significantly.
- Banks need to develop a skilled workforce that can solve any problem within the Internet banking infrastructure. This way, banks will not have to rely on skilled foreign workers. Collaboration with other Bangladeshi banks and foreign banks will help to build a strong skilled workforce and enhance the rapid improvement of the Bangladeshi banking industry.

6.6.6 Limitation of the Study:

The research was conducted based on a mixed methodology using qualitative and quantitative data. Qualitative data was collected through purposive sampling, which is a commonly adopted strategy in phenomenological investigations with drawbacks due to lack of generalizability (Yin, 2003). In addition, the researcher explored a single social field; therefore, the findings are not transferable to other fields. This research could be conducted based on a single approach either qualitative or quantitative approach as well. Furthermore, qualitative data through interviews were collected from seven different banks without considering the degree of their representation in the industry. Future research can include more banks with financial data, and it will further enhance the understanding of the issues. The study focused on identifying the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in the overall banking industry; therefore, the results present only overall generalizable outcomes rather than highlighting any particular banking sector individually. Future research can be conducted on different industries similar to the banking industry using this research framework. Additionally, quantitative data was collected through survey questionnaires to understand customers' perspectives where additional focus could be given to collect robust data if the survey was conducted in person.

The expected sample size was 385. However, due to COVID-19 and the online data collection process, it was not possible to collect all the expected data. Therefore, future research can be conducted on a larger sample size.

However, COVID-19 was one of the most significant barriers to the data collection process as it restricted the researcher from collecting data due to travel restrictions from the UK government. Therefore, the researcher was restricted to collecting additional data; however, it did not exclude the researcher from obtaining rich data from interviews and survey responses. It wasn't possible to conduct face-to-face interviews due to COVID-19, therefore, all the interviews were conducted using social communication media such as telephone, WhatsApp, Skype, and Google Meet. Although personal interviews could provide richer data through informative conversations, it wasn't possible to have face-to-face interviews by any means. All the interviews were conducted in English, and some interviewees struggled to accumulate their ideas and express them in English as English is their second language. Therefore, the researcher had to reconfirm some responses further, which actually entered the data triangulation. Future research could focus on the language barrier of the participants and the interview and survey questioners can be written in their native language such as Bangla in Bangladeshi perspective. Another limitation the researcher had to face was the Internet connection. Poor Internet connection in Bangladesh interrupted the smooth conversation and caused some call drops during the interview. Additionally, some interviews were conducted in the home environment of respondents due to the COVID-19 lockdown, which ensured a relaxed environment for the conversation. However, some interviews were conducted in an office environment where respondents were interrupted by their colleagues due to official queries. Although, it did not significantly affect the quality of the interview, but uninterrupted interview could provide a more enriched response.

The researcher was also affected by COVID-19 illness which significantly affected the researcher physically, mentally, and financially. Additionally, the recent death of a close family member of the researcher significantly affected mentally, which caused significant time loss.

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Appendix - 1: (Interview questionnaire):

Factors Affecting the Adoption of Internet Banking:

A study in Khulna city, Bangladesh.

This semi-structured interview is a part of the DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) thesis conducted by Md Mehedi Hasan at the University of the West of Scotland.

The focus of the interview is to identify the factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Khulna, Bangladesh.

The data collected from this interview will be used solely for this research. The information of the participants will be treated with the highest confidentiality. You are requested to participate in this interview as your contribution will be highly appreciated.

A consent form and participant's information sheet have been sent to you as this will help you answer any questions you may have regarding this research. You are free to skip questions, but it would be appreciated if you could answer all questions.

Interview Questionnaire:

1. What are the problems customers face to use the Internet banking system?
 - How convenient the Internet banking is? What kind of complexity customer face to use Internet banking?
 - What do you think about your customers digital and financial literacy?
 - How is your customer service?
2. What do customers think about “*the cost of Internet and PC/Mobile*” vs “*the usefulness*” of Internet banking?
 - How do customers think about the usefulness of Internet banking?
 - The cost of the Internet is too high, and the speed of the Internet is very slow.
 - Compared to the costs and unsatisfactory banking experience, customers don't find value in using Internet banking.
3. How do risk factors affect customers' decision to use Internet banking?
 - What action do you take for fraud?
 - Do customers trust Internet banking system?
 - What is your refund policy?
4. How does the tradition of customers affect their decision to adopt Internet banking?

- How do you explain your customers cash dependency?
 - What do they think about Internet banking compared to branch banking?
5. How does the image of banks affect customers' decision to adopt Internet banking?
 - How do your customers evaluate conventional banking to Islamic banking?
 6. What steps your bank has taken so far to encourage more people to adopt Internet banking?
 7. What recommendations will you give to support more uptake of Internet banking and sustainable development of Internet banking in Bangladesh?

Appendix 2: Interview Consent Form

Research Consent Form

For (Md Mehedi Hasan)

Name of department: Business and Creative Industries at UWS

Title of the study: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

-
1. I _____ voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
 2. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
 3. I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my Survey/Interview within two weeks after the survey, in which case the material will be deleted.
 4. I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing, and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
 5. I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
 6. I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
 7. I understand that in any report on the results of this research, my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my survey, which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
 8. I understand that a copy of my Survey/Interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for 5 years.
 9. I understand that under freedom of information legalization, I am not entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
 10. I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

➤ Researcher: MD MEHEDI HASAN/

4. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

It can be assured that no risk or harm is involved in taking part in this research.

5. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The research outcome will be beneficial for the banking sector and the government of Bangladesh in terms of policymaking and measures taken by the banks and government.

6. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. The confidentiality of your participation will be given first priority by the researcher.

7. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

No, there is no recording requirement in the survey, but you can give personal contact details if you wish to provide.

8. What type of information will be sought from me, and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

All the research questions were designed to understand the factors affecting the adoption of Internet in Bangladesh. Your answers to the questions are very valuable to understand the research problems and meet the research objectives.

9. Who will publish the research?

The University of West Scotland will publish the research.

Appendix 4: Survey Questionnaires

Factors Affecting the Adoption of Internet Banking: A study in Khulna, Bangladesh.

This survey is a part of the DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) thesis conducted by Md Mehedi Hasan at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The focus of this survey is to identify the factors affecting the adoption of internet banking in Bangladesh.

The data collected from this survey will be used solely for this research. The information of the participants will be treated with the highest confidentiality. You are requested to participate in this survey as your contribution will be highly appreciated. You are free to skip questions, but it would be appreciated if you can answer all questions. Thanks.

* Required

1. Name:

2. Email Address (Optional):

Demographic Information of Participants.

3. 1. How would you describe your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

Male.

Female.

4. 2. What is your age? *

Mark only one oval.

- 18 or below.
- 18 – 25 years old.
- 25 – 30 years old.
- 30 – 40 years old.
- 40 – 50 years old.
- 50 + years old.

5. 3. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed? *

Mark only one oval.

- SSC/HSC.
- Bachelor's degree.
- Master's degree.
- PhD or Higher.
- Trade school.

6. 5. What is your monthly income? *

Mark only one oval.

- 10,000 BDT or below.
- 10,000 to 20,000 BDT.
- 20,000 to 30,000 BDT.
- 30,000 to 50,000 BDT.
- 50,000 BDT +
- Unemployed.

Screening
Questions.

(To complete this survey, you need to be a bank
account holder.)

7. 1. Do you have a bank account or banking experience? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

Survey Questions:

8. 1. Do you think Internet Banking is more effortless than Traditional Banking? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes.
 No.
 I'm familiar with it and planning to use.
 I'm familiar it but not interested to use.

9. 2. How did you learn about Internet Banking? *

Mark only one oval.

- TV.
 Newspaper.
 Social media.
 Search engine.
 Recommendation from a friend.

10. 3. Which of the following device do you have or use regularly ? *

Mark only one oval.

- Mobile.
 Tablet.
 Laptop/Desktop Computer.

11. 4. How often do you get notification from banks regarding Internet Banking services? *

Mark only one oval.

- Everyday.
- Once a week.
- Once a month.
- Once in 6 months.
- Regularly.
- Never.

12. 5. What do you think about the internet service in Bangladesh? *

Mark only one oval.

- Internet is expensive.
- Internet speed is slow.
- Internet is not available everywhere.
- Internet speed and cost are satisfactory.
- Internet service is good.

13. 6. How frequently do you visit your bank branch? *

Mark only one oval.

- Everyday.
- Once a week.
- Once a month.
- Once in 6 months.
- Regularly.

14. 7. What do you think about Internet Banking for not being popular yet? *

Mark only one oval.

- Not easy to open an account.
- Security concern.
- Not available in many banks.
- Don't see any real value in having this type of account.
- Lack of knowledge.
- Internet banking has english interface and most people don't know english.

15. 8. Do you think banks should provide training and cheaper internet connection *
to promote Internet Banking?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes.
- No.
- Not sure.

16. 9. I will open an Internet Banking account within next 12 months. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
- Disagree.
- Not Sure.

17. 10. Which problem have you faced mainly using internet banking? *

Mark only one oval.

- Convenient but not always faster.
- Difficult to access my account.
- It does not fulfill my needs.
- Lack of personal banker relationship.
- Limitations on deposits.
- A limited scope of services.

18. 11. Which kind of Internet Banking service do you use frequently? *

Mark only one oval.

- Online shopping.
- Balance checking.
- Money Transfer.
- Apply for a credit card, loan or opening bank account.
- Set up direct debit or Standing order.
- Using bank internet portals.

19. 12. It is easy to do banking tasks more effectively if banks use Bangla interface in their system for Internet Banking. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree
- Disagree
- Not Sure

20. 13. I think Internet Banking increases the risk of fraud. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree
- Disagree
- Not Sure

21. 14. The Internet Banking app/website of my bank is not user friendly. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree
- Disagree
- Not Sure

22. 15. Internet Banking app is not suitable for my electronic device. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
- Disagree.
- Not sure.

23. 16. I prefer to use cash. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
- Disagree.
- Not Sure.

24. 17. I am not satisfied with bank's customer service regarding my Internet Banking problems. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
 Disagree.
 Not Sure.

25. 18. I think Internet Banking is not secure enough for my personal data and money. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
 Disagree.
 Not Sure.

26. 19. I will recommend my friends and family to use Internet Banking. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
 Disagree.
 Not Sure.

27. 20. The media is full of reports, articles and news that suggest using Internet Banking. *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree.
 Disagree.
 Not Sure.

28. 21. Banks frequently inform, encourage and provide training for customers to use Internet Banking. *

Mark only one oval.

Agree.

Disagree.

Not Sure.

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